

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute

Volume 3: No. (3), September 2020

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Abbreviation of the Journal: Egypt. J. of Plant Prot. Res. Inst.`

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute

Volume 3: No. (3), September 2020

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Life table parameters of tomato russet mite *Aculops lycopersici* (Acari: Eriophyidae) at different temperatures in Egypt

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 1 /7 /2020

Accepted: 24/8 /2020

Keywords

Life table, tomato, tomato russet mite, *Aculops lycopersici*, temperature and Egypt.

Abstract:

The tomato russet mite *Aculops lycopersici* (Masse) (Acari: Eriophyidae) successfully developed from egg to adult stage when reared on safeera tomato cultivar at different constant temperatures and 45 % RH. The effect of temperature on the development, reproduction and population growth was investigated. At least of 21.50 % of generation time was spent in the egg stage at 31 °C. Fecundity was highest at 31 °C with 64.2 eggs per female. Life table parameters showed that the population of *A. lycopersici* on safeera tomato cultivar leaves multiplied 41.18 times in a generation time of 15.17 days at 31 °C and multiplied 25.53 times in a generation time of 24.22 days at 18 °C under the same conditions.

Introduction

Tomato russet mite (TRM) *Aculops lycopersici* (Masse) (Acari: Eriophyidae) is an important pest of tomato *Solanum lycopersicum* Mill and can be considered on exception to the general statement that eriophyoid mites are highly specialized plant parasite (Lindquist and Oldfield, 1996). It has been first discovered in Australia (Tryon, 1937) and until 1986 there were 47 countries which have reported the occurrence of TRM (Nemato, 2000). Now it has become a worldwide serious pest with tomato plants as main host. The exception is in southern and northern latitudes below and above 60 degrees, respectively (Perring, 1996). Adult stage very small, requiring a 14 X hand lens to be observed. This eriophyid mite is tapered, and wedge shaped, with only two pairs of legs at

the brooder head end and two long hairs on the tapered, posterior end. Generally, translucent and yellowish, or pink in color.

The acquisition of data on TRM biology has been ascribable to a wide range of climatic or laboratory conditions. It seems able to tolerate considerable variations. In temperature and relative humidity (Fisher and Mourrut- Salesse, 2005). The effect of temperature can be described by specific rate functions of temperature on survival, reproduction, population growth and developmental growth (Ray *et al.*, 2002). Most of the fundamental studies on TRM biology are same tens of years old. Badey and Keifer (1943) observed that at 21 °C, TRM females laid about 15 eggs in their life time. The life cycle was 6.5 days under optimal

conditions (21 °C and 30 % RH.) (Rice and Strong, 1962). Experimental conditions of 25 °C and 70 % RH., males developed in 4.62 days and females in an average of 5.15 days mentioned by Abou-Awad (1979) . Al-Azzazy and Alhewairini (2018) reported that the population of TRM multiplied 18.14 times in a generation time of 14.45 days at 32 °C and lowered to 4.25 times in a generation time of 26.38 days at 11 °C under the same conditions.

The current work aims to study the life history and life table parameters of TRM at different temperatures.

Material and methods

A stock culture of *A. lycopersici* was collected from heavily infested leaves of safeera tomato cultivar (*S. lycopersicum*) at the farm of Modern Agriculture Company (PICO-Group), Tahrir province, El-Behera Governorate. Clean disc 1.5 cm in diameter of excised well developed uninfested tomato leaves were carefully examined, placed upper surfaces downwards on water saturated cotton, in a large uncovered petri dishes, 15 cm in diameter. Forty new adult stages were obtained from the aforementioned heavily infested tomato leaves and placed singly on the discs by mean of a human eyebrow, fastened to a handle.

Each female could deposit 1-2 eggs, and then it was removed. Leaf discs were placed in the incubator at different constant temperatures (18, 23, 31 and 45 % relative humidity) and a 16 / 8 light / dark period. Rearing leaf discs were removed every four or five other days, and some drops of water were added daily by drop bottle in petri dishes. Mite development was observed twice daily. After the last of either sex and to insemination by spermatophores

produced by males, each newly emerged female was transferred, for 24 h., to a leaf disc previously inhabited by an adult male, then females and males were transferred back to their original leaf discs. Keifer (1954) used three steps recipes for fixation and embedding. Life table parameters were calculated according to Hulting *et al.* (1990).

Results and discussion

Adults and nymphs of the tomato russet mite *A. lycopersici* have piercing sucking mouthparts and feeding on the undersides of lower leaves and on petioles and stems, produces a greasy appearance, which becomes bronzed. Leaves may yellow, curl upwards, dry out and drop. Damage starts at the bottom of plants and moves upwards and may be confused with nutritional deficiencies, plant disease on water stress. TRM was able to develop successfully from egg to adult through the entire life history at constant temperatures between 18 and 31 °C and 45 % RH. Eggs are spherical, yellowish, and translucent when first laid, latter becoming opaque as a result of development of the embryo. The fertilized female lays eggs scattered on the lower surface of the leaf, particularly alongside the veins. An embryo develops within the egg which then hatched into a first instar nymph which resembles the adult in many respects, but it is smaller, without external genitalia. The first nymph is translucent, 73–81 µm long. It passes through a nymphocrysalis before molting into the second instar nymph, which is very similar to the first, yellow white in clear, 137–143 µm long and more active (Figure 1).

Figure (1): Nymphs and adult stage of the tomato russet mite *Aculops lycopersici*. A: Anteroventral view of second nymph; B: Cephalothoracic shield of second nymph; C: Cephalothoracic shield of female; D: Male genitalia; E: Side skin structure; F: Side view of female; G: Female genitalia; H: Ventral view of second nymph; I: Featherclaws and J: Side view of first nymph.

The second nymph passes through an imagochrysalis before molting, giving rise to the adult; 207 – 223 μm long, 55 – 57 μm wide; spindle form, narrowed posteriorly, arched strongly in lateral view. Unfertilized females, fertilized females and the molting behavior of TRM were like the olive rust mite *Tegalophus hassani* (Keifer) (Abou– Awad *et al.*, 2005). The mean developmental times of *A. lycopersici* at each of three constant temperatures are shown in Table (1). Egg duration decreased with an increase in the temperature up to 31 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Nymphal durations also gradually decreased with an increase in temperature up to 31 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The total life cycle was completed in 12.79 and 11.51, 9.41 and 8.14 and 5.35 and 4.82 days for females and males at 18.23 and 31 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. Males developed

faster. The life cycle results of Barkè *et al.* (1972) on the peach silver mite *Aculus cornutus* (Banks), Easterbrook (1979) on the apple leaf mite *Aculus schlechtendoli* (Nalepa) and Abou-Awad *et al.* (2005) on the olive rust mite *T. hassani* are nearly in agreement at some of the previous temperatures. A generation took 12.41 days at 23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, an increase of 8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ reduced this time by only 5.06 days, where as a decrease of 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ increased it by 4.92 days; at least of 21.5 % of the generation time was spent in the egg stage at 31 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Barkè *et al.* (1972) mentioned that at 29.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the mite was extremely active, and by 31 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ the adults began to slow down and cease all activity. In the present study, mites appeared to show normal behavior at 31 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the difference between 23 and 31 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ of the generation time was significant.

Table (1): Average duration (in days) of various stages and oviposition rate of *Aculops lycopersici* surviving on safeera-tomato cultivar at different constant temperatures and 45 % RH.

		<i>Aculops lycopersici</i>		
		Mean \pm SD		
		Temperatures ($^{\circ}$ C)		
Mite stage	Sex	18	23	31
Egg	Female	4.92 \pm 0.38a	3.63 \pm 0.21b	1.58 \pm 0.09c
	Male	4.46 \pm 0.37a	3.04 \pm 0.22b	1.57 \pm 0.10c
First instar nymph	Female	3.83 \pm 0.24a	3.00 \pm 0.21b	2.04 \pm 0.19c
	Male	3.46 \pm 0.25a	2.64 \pm 0.20b	1.89 \pm 0.17c
Nymphochrysalis	Female	0.48 \pm 0.12a	0.40 \pm 0.11b	0.37 \pm 0.12b
	Male	0.36 \pm 0.13a	0.18 \pm 0.11b	0.14 \pm 0.10c
Second instar nymph	Female	3.10 \pm 0.16a	2.08 \pm 0.17b	1.15 \pm 0.12c
	Male	2.86 \pm 0.18a	2.00 \pm 0.16b	1.00 \pm 0.09c
Imagochrysalis	Female	0.46 \pm 0.11a	0.29 \pm 0.07c	0.21 \pm 0.06d
	Male	0.38 \pm 0.09a	0.29 \pm 0.10b	0.21 \pm 0.07c
Life cycle	Female	12.79 \pm 0.43a	9.41 \pm 0.36b	5.35 \pm 0.24c
	Male	11.51 \pm 0.41a	8.14 \pm 0.31b	4.82 \pm 0.21c
Preoviposition	Female	4.54 \pm 0.31a	3.00 \pm 0.28b	2.00 \pm 0.19c
Generation	Female	17.33 \pm 0.61a	12.41 \pm 0.40b	7.35 \pm 0.36c
Oviposition	Female	10.98 \pm 0.45a	13.46 \pm 0.38b	16.24 \pm 0.41c
Postoviposition	Female	4.39 \pm 0.31a	4.06 \pm 0.24 a	3.56 \pm 0.23 b
Longevity	Female	19.91 \pm 0.25a	20.53 \pm 0.21b	21.80 \pm 0.24c
	Male	17.71 \pm 0.24a	18.82 \pm 0.20b	19.43 \pm 0.23c
Life span	Female	32.70 \pm 0.64a	29.94 \pm 0.51b	27.16 \pm 0.41c
	Male	29.22 \pm 0.53a	26.96 \pm 0.43b	24.2 \pm 0.42c
% surviving	Female	100	100	100
	Male	100	100	100
Number of observations	Female	26	26	25
	Male	14	14	15

Mean marked with the same letters in a horizontal column are not significantly different (F-test, $P < 0.05$, < 0.01).

The longevity of ovipositing females decreased with increased temperature. Longevity at 18 $^{\circ}$ C was 19.91 days, about 0.91 times as long as at 31 $^{\circ}$ C. Total fecundity gradually increased with an increase in temperature. Females deposited an average of 38.90, 48.90 and 64.20 eggs, during an oviposition period that averaged 10.98, 13.46 and 16.24 days; while Abou-Awad *et al.* (2010) reported that total fecundity of the peach silver mite *Aculus fockeui* (Nalepa and Trouessart) (Acari: Eriophyidae) gradually increased with an average in temperature up to 29 $^{\circ}$ C, but at 32 $^{\circ}$ C, it again decreased. Females of TRM survived for 4.39, 4.06 and 3.56 days at the same temperatures, respectively (Table 1). The highest number of eggs per female was observed to be 64.2 at 31 $^{\circ}$ C and decreased with a decrease in

temperature. It could be concluded that 31 $^{\circ}$ C as an optimum temperature accelerated the rate of development and induced greater production of *A. lycopersici*. The greatest fecundity, as well for ovipositing females of the tomato rust mite *A. lycopersici* was 51.7 eggs at 25 $^{\circ}$ C (Haque and Kawai, 2003). It is possible, however, that the reproductive capacity of an eriophyid mite might be better under favorable conditions. The life history took 32.70 and 29.22, 29.94 and 26.96 and 27.16 and 24.20 days for females and males at the same temperatures, respectively. In general, life histories studied by Putmann (1939), Keifer (1942), Minder (1957), Abou-Awad *et al.* (2000 and 2005) in agreement. A few days after fertilization by spermatophores, the progeny was predominantly females, with a sex ratio of 2:1, while unfertilized females produced only

males. This is an agreement with the results reported for this work (Table, 2). Similar findings were reported on *Phyllocoptrata oleaver* (Ashmead) and *Aculus pelekassi* Keifer (Burditt et

al., 1963), on *Aceria ficus* (Cotte) (Abou-Awad et al., 2000) and on *Aceria oleae* Nalepa and *T. hassani* (Abou-Awad et al., 2005).

Table (2): Life table parameters of the tomato russet mite *Aculops lycopersici* survived on safeera- tomato cultivar at different temperatures and 45 % RH.

Parameters	<i>Aculops lycopersici</i> Temperatures (°C)		
	18	23	31
Net reproduction rate (R_o)	25.53	31.39	41.18
Mean generation time (T.)	24.22	18.90	15.17
Intrinsic rate of increase (r_m)	0.134	0.182	0.245
Finite rate of increase (e^{r_m})	1.143	1.201	1.278
50 % mortality (in days)	30.00	28.00	26.00
Mean total fecundity	38.90	48.9	64.2
Mean daily rate	3.54	3.63	3.95
Sex ratio (Female / total)	26/40	26/40	25/40
Sex ratio (Female : male)	2.00:1	2.00:1	2.00 :1

Parameters of population growth of *A.lycopersici* at three temperatures are shown in Table (2). The intrinsic rate of increase (r_m) increased with temperature to a maximum of 0.245 at 31°C. Net reproductive rate (R_o) was the largest (41.18 times) and the generation time was the shortest (7.35 days) at the same previous temperature and 45 RH. It is of interest to note that not only temperature but also humidity affects the population growth of eriophyoid mites. The population growth rate of *P.oleavora* decreased as the humidity dropped (Hobza and Jepson, 1974). A suitable temperature in the field as well as better food conditions and an absence of a natural enemy would have brought about a rapid population growth of the tomato russet mite *A.lycopersici* which is disastrous mite on tomato cultivars.

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Queensland, pp. 49-63.

**Effect of garlic oil as a rodenticide for black rats *Rattus rattus* (Rodentia: Muridae)
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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 5 / 7 /2020

Accepted: 2 /9 /2020

Keywords

Garlic oil, rodenticide, *Rattus rattus*, toxicity and histopathological.

Abstract:

This research focuses on the toxicity study of the garlic oil in *Rattus rattus* (L.) (Rodentia: Muridae). The used of 22 rats has been selected to study acute and chronic toxicity to start a trial in non-choice test. Nine animals were used for 2, 4 and 8 % garlic oil bait for a preliminary experiment, and the 13 number, for 0.5, 1 and 1.5% for the main experiment in non-choice laboratory test. Results indicated for a preliminary experiment that 2% of garlic oil highest toxicity concentrations after 48 hrs. was recorded 40% and acceptability 44.45% . It is very clear that the deadly effect of all concentrations according to the histopathology study on kidney and uterus was effective. The main experiment, the high mortality percent of the rat was 60% for 1% garlic oil bait and acceptability 51.57 was recorded while in 1.5% garlic oil bait record 40% mortality and 46.16 acceptability. Histopathological changes in kidney showing glomerular capillaries with very thin basement membrane mesangiolysis and destructed walls, uterus showed degeneration and necrosis of uterine gland and fibrosis in lamina propria of endometrium, the ovaries showed atrophy of the growing follicles and free from any stages of maturation. The testis tubuli lumen exhibited necrosis and degeneration of spermatogonium cells and epididymis free of spermatozoa and some of lumen full of degenerated necrosed.

Introduction

Rodents are one of the most dangerous pests in Egypt. Among the common types of rodents (Black and Norway rats). Rodents were also considered a serious pest on agricultural crops and stored goods and have behavioral phenomena such as high intelligence and a strong sense of smell, which makes it difficult to control rodents. The repeated use of chemical rodenticides, in agriculture pest control programs, led to the development of

many serious problems affecting the control success. From these problems are pest resistance to these rodenticides and the pollution of the environment. Therefore, there is a growing need to find new natural extractions, which have a strong effect against pests but safe and friendly to the environment in order to ensure the future safe of agriculture food required for the world population without destroying the ecosystems. To reach these goals,

researchers began to explore alternative, less expensive and environmentally friendly, pesticides derived from naturally toxic plants.

The researchers study the effect of some different plant products (Garlic oil, garlic extract, garlic powder and drugs). Oils on the control against rats such as garlic oil is a product that can be manufactured at home, does not need many steps and, garlic oil has the properties of disinfectant and the quality deadly bacteria and viruses, and man can eat oil in small quantities and do not constitute harm to health. Chegu *et al.* (2018) showed the daily intake of these aqueous plant extracts may help full to prevent the cardiovascular diseases. And Ozougwu *et al.* (2014) suggested that the administration of *Allium sativum* extracts protected against paracetamol liver damage in rats. Garlic oil significant rise in urea and D-aspartate aminotransferase and inhibition of alkaline phosphatase in serum were observed in rats fed garlic extract (Joseph *et al.*, 1989). But other authors Hammami and El May (2012) which could have another potential negative effect about spermatogenesis. Also, must note the potential interference that may exist between drugs and garlic consumption. Abdelmalik (2011) who described morphological aspects suggesting apoptosis of somatic and myoid cells of adult rat after treatment with 20% of crude garlic for 4 months. Several studies Dixit and Joshi (1982) reported that chronic administration of 50 mg of garlic powder to adult rat over 70 days induced a spermatogenetic arrest at the primary spermatocyte stage. Moreover, aqueous garlic extract have spermicidal effects on adult rats (Chakrabarti *et al.*, 2003).

The aim of this study is to develop a method to control of the rats by using natural plant extracts environmentally safe that have no side effect on non-

target (Human , animal and plant) in the environment.

Materials and methods

1. Garlic oil:

Commercially available garlic oil from EL-Captain Company For Extracting Natural Oil Plant and Cosmatic. Info@elcaptain eg.com. The garlic bait was prepared by garlic oil mixing 95% crushed maize, and 5% powder sugar.

2. Tested animals:

Healthy animals elected black rats *Rattus rattus* (L.) (Rodentia: Muridae), from Abou-Rawash district, Giza Governorate. . Rats were individually caged in wire cages (50 x 30 x 20 cm), acclimatized for at least 2 weeks. Food (dried bread) and water were provided *ad libitum*. Inactive (unhealthy) rats were excluded. The choice of 22 rats has been selected to start trial in non-choice test. Nine animals were used for 2, 4 and 8 % garlic oil bait for preliminary experiment, and the 13 number, for 0.5,1 and 1.5% for main experiment in non-choice laboratory test.

3. Cage tests:

Studies were conducted on rats to test the effect of garlic oil toxicity/bait formulations and its histopathological effect.

4. Preliminary experiment:

A known amount (40g) of crushed maize was placed in a buttery dish, and a known amount (40g) of 2, 4 and 8 % garlic oil mixed with crushed maize were provided daily to each of 3 caged rats for 3 days in pre-treatment and treatment test, respectively. Water was provided to rats *ad libitum*. Consumption have been, number of died rats were daily recorded. The acceptability and mortality of rats were calculated. Finally, observation to period 28 days with plain bait (crushed maize) *ad libitum*. . Rats of each group were sacrificed by an overdose of chloroform, the testes as well as the

epididymides, kidney, uterus and ovary were dissected out for gross as well as for histopathological examination. Rats were sacrificed after diet for all group.

5. Main experiment:

A known amount (40g) of crushed maize was placed in a buttery dish in pre-treatment and a known amount (40g) of 1.5, 1 and 0.5 % garlic bait (Garlic oil mixing 95% crushed maize, and 5% powder sugar) were provided daily to each of 5, 5 and 3 caged rats for 4 days in treatment test. Water was provided to rats *ad libitum*. Consumption have been, number of died rats were daily recorded. Rats of each concentration were sacrificed by an overdose of chloroform, kidney, uterus, ovary and the testes as well as the epididymides were dissected out for gross as well as for histopathological examination. Males and females of the group were sacrificed after 60 days of treatment, the acceptability and mortality of rats were calculated. Finally, observation to period 4 weeks with plain bait (Crushed maize) *ad libitum*. The acceptability and mortality of rats were calculated. Using the following equation (Mason *et al.*, 1989).

$$\text{Acceptability \%} = \frac{\text{Average daily consumption of treated food (g)}}{\text{Total average daily consumption of (treated + untreated) food (g)}} \times 100$$

6. Histopathological examination:

For histopathological examination, the collected specimens were fixed in 10% neutral buffered formalin for at least 24 hrs. and then routinely processed by conventional method and finally stained by heamatoxylene and eosin (Suvarna *et al.*, 2013). The preparations were examined by the light microscope for identifying the presence of histopathological changes for kidney, testis, uterus and ovary for different concentration of garlic oil.

7. Statistical analysis:

The results were statistically analyses using the standard statistical methods LSD- test was applied in the analyzed by SAS (2006).

Results and discussion

1. Preliminary test of the effect of different averages of garlic oil bait for black rats daily consumption, acceptability and mortality:

Table (1) showed that the average daily consumption 2% garlic oil bait were height than 4% and 8%. The acceptability percent was 44.45%, 39.46% and 43.58% for 2%, 4% and 8% garlic oil crushed maize baits, respectively. Rats mortality was observed during the treatment and after 48 hrs. of treatment in case of 2% bait. In case of 4% mortality was after 29 days of treatment, while the mortality in between 44 and 66 days of treatment in case of 8% garlic oil bait. The bait consumption of 2% garlic oil bait in the first second and third day about the same 12.42, 12.13 and 12.68g, respectively. Daily consumption decreased gradually 8.33, 6.82 and 6.75g for 4% bait. From data mention above the effective concentration of garlic oil bait is 2%. Saxena *et al.* (1995) conducted laboratory experiments against *Mus musculus* of 2% garlic pulp and other plants as bait attractants and their palatability was recorded. Garlic pulp almost significantly decreased consumption compared to plain bait. (Roasted bajra). Chegu *et al.* (2018) aimed to evaluate the possible anticoagulant effect of aqueous extract of garlic and were tested for invitro prothrombin time (PT) test. Its results demonstrated that aqueous extract of garlic posse pharmacologically active anticoagulant component which could helpful in prevent blood clot.

Table (1): Preliminary test of the effect of average 2%, 4% and 8% of garlic oil bait for black rats daily consumption ($g \pm SD$), acceptability and mortality under laboratory conditions.

C.	R.	Average daily consumption of rat (g)								M.	A.
		Pre-treatment				Treatment					
		1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	A.	1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	A.		
2%	5	15.49 ± 5.21	12.57 ± 5.22	14.10 ± 7.76	14.11 $\pm 5.67^A$	12.42 ± 7.37	12.13 ± 4.51	12.68 ± 8.99	11.29 $\pm 6.83^A$	40	44.45
4%	2	11.18 ± 0.21	11.44 ± 1.13	9.62 ± 0.83	10.75 $\pm 0.75^B$	8.33 ± 3.91	6.82 ± 0.48	6.75 ± 1.51	7.30 $\pm 1.97^B$	0	39.46
8%	2	11.31 ± 2.29	9.33 ± 2.30	6.90 ± 0.50	9.18 $\pm 0.17^B$	9.22 ± 1.09	5.92 ± 3.53	6.14 ± 1.26	7.09 $\pm 1.96^B$	0	43.58

C.: Cocentration R. : Replecates A. : Average M. : Mortality A.: Acceptability.

The vertical columns marked with the same letters are not significantly different by SAS (2006).

2. Histopathology studies:

It is very clear that the deadly effect of all concentration according to the histopathology study on kidney (Figures 1-3) and uterus (Figures 4-6) was effective, but the occurred early

death in a 2% garlic bait be the optimal concentration of treatment. There was histopathological findings observer in ovary, testes which probable cause in main is pyelonephritis.

Figure (1): Kidney of rat 2% showing sever dilation and congestion of the intertubular blood vessels (BV) FE X40.

Figure (2): Kidney of rat 4% identify the pus formation and liquefaction in the renal pelvis and medulla HE X40.

Figure (3): 8% Kidney showing inflammatory cells infiltration surrounding the dilated blood vessels (BV).

Figure (4): Uterus female rat showing oedema in lamina propria (o) HE X 40 2%.

Figure (5): Uterus of rat showing massive number of inflammatory cells infiltration (LU) in the mucosnl, muscular (M) and serosol layer(S) HE X 40 8%.

Figure (6): Uterus of rat showing hyperplastic and metaplastic of the mucosal lining epithelium 8% (HE X 40).

Histopathological changes in kidney, uterus, ovary, testis and epididymis in survived rat fed garlic oil crushed bait during 4 days in non-choice test after 60 days of treatment in the following.

2.1. 0.5% garlic oil bait:

The histopathological changes in kidney showing glomerular capillaries with very thin basement membrane mesangiolytic and destructed walls (Pink arrows), very thin basement membrane cells (Green arrow) and loss of glomerular tuft with empty glomerular corpuscle (Yellow arrow) (Figure 7). Joseph *et al.* (1989) who recorded significant rise in urea and D-aspartate aminotransferase and inhibition of alkaline phosphatase in serum were observed in rats fed garlic extract (2 ml/100 g body wt., intragastrically) for 10 days. Richard *et al.* (2000) impaired reproductive function accompanies chronic renal

insufficiency (uremia) in experimental animal. Clinical hypogonadism occurs in both genders. Anti-ovulatory effects of uremia in the female rat was record. The ovaries showed regressed atrophied fibrosed ovaries (Yellow arrow) (Figure 8). The uterus revealed mucoid degeneration of the of endometrial lamina propria (Figure 9). That results supported by Musk and Clapham (1997) who found that daily sulfide (DAS) and daily disulfide (DDS) from garlic oil, were tested for cytotoxic and genotoxic effects in a Chinese hamster ovary cell line who found both compounds were found to induce both chromosome aberrations and sister chromatid exchanges (SCEs) with DDS but DDS was found to be more cytotoxic than DAS. Mucinous metaplasia is an uncommon type of endometrial epithelial metaplasia, often associated with hyperestrogenic states or hormone replacement therapy.

Figure (7): Kidney (H&E; EX200).

Figure (8): Ovarian (H&E; EX100).

Figure (9): Uterus (H&E; EX200).

Complete loss of spermatogonium cells and the basement membrane of testis tubuli appear bar of the cells, severe vacuolations of sertoli cells (Pink arrows) thrombus blood vessel (Blue arrow) degeneration, necrosis in leydig cells. In other words, the severely stiffed wall of testis tubuli fibrosed increase hyalinization of the basement membrane with severely damaged wall of testis tubuli and disruption of blood testis barrier and loss of all spermatogonium cells and thrombi in the blood capillaries (Figure 10). Uhrin *et al.* (2000) who found protein C inhibitor (PCI) is a nonspecific, heparin-binding serpin (serine protease inhibitor) that inactivates many plasmatic and extravascular serine proteases by forming stable 1:1 complex. Proteases inhibited by PCI include the

Figure (10): Testis (H&E; EX400).

2.2. 1% garlic oil bait:

Which showing changes in kidneys, atrophy of the glomerular tufts was recorded in male kidneys with necrosis and degeneration of the glomerular capillaries walls (Figure 12). That results agreed with Muralidaran *et al.* (2018), who found a remarkable attenuation in the mesangial expansion and proliferation, glomerular and tubular basement membrane thickening, and the tubular lipid deposits. And found that garlic oil blend significantly promoted renal podocin gene expression by 3.98-fold ($p < 0.001$) and attenuated increased urinary podocin level by 2.92-fold ($p < 0.01$). The changes recorded in testis with garlic oil appeared in 1% as edema

anticoagulant activated protein C, the plasminogen activator urokinase, and the sperm protease acrosin. PCI circulates as a plasma protein but is also present at high concentrations in organs of the male reproductive tract. Infertility was apparently caused by abnormal spermatogenesis due to destruction of the sertoli cell barrier, perhaps due to unopposed proteolytic activity. The resulting sperm are malformed and are morphologically similar to abnormal sperm seen in some cases of human male infertility. Epididymis free of spermatozoa and some of lumen full with degenerated necrosed cells showing honey comb cellular contents in the epididymal lumen (Yellow arrow) (Figure 11). This concentration is sterile for rat and not cause death

Figure (11): Epididymis (H&E; EX400).

(Stars) in between testis tubuli (Blue arrow) and severe shrinkage in basement membrane of testis tubuli with destruction of myoid cells (Yellow arrow) and the testis tubuli lumen exhibited necrosis and degeneration of spermatogonium cells with loss of abundant number of spermatogonium cell (Green arrow) with vacuolations and necrosis of sertoli cells and atrophy of leydig cells (Figure 13). Abnormal germ cells present in the lumen of the epididymis (Figure 14). This concentration caused kidney failure and sterile for male rats and cause death for female rat". According to Dixit and Joshi (1982) treated male rats with garlic powder (50 mg garlic powder for 45 days or 70 days by oral route). After

oral administration of 50 mg of garlic powder for 45 days, the testes showed degenerative changes but in most of the tubules normal stages from spermatogonia to spermatids have been seen; seminiferous tubule and leydig cells nuclei were shrunken. After oral administration of 50 mg of garlic powder for 70 days, severe testicular lesions were seen. Spermatogenesis was arrested at the primary spermatocyte stage; sertoli cells also showed degenerative changes (Hammami *et al.*, 2008). The treatment resulted in a significant decrease in testosterone serum levels (at 10, 15 and 30%) associated with a significant increase in LH serum levels. Testicular histology showed a dose-dependent increase in the percentage of empty seminiferous tubules. Moreover, testicular function was affected and Hammami *et al.* (2009) showed that feeding with crude

garlic inhibited leydig steroidogenic enzyme expression and sertoli cell markers. These alterations might induce germ cell death (spermatocytes and spermatids) via an apoptotic process. to and added that crude garlic-feeding induced apoptosis in testicular germ cells (Spermatocytes and spermatids). This cell death process was characterized by increased levels of active CASP3 but not CASP6. Expression of the caspase inhibitors BIRC3 and BIRC2 was increased at all doses of as while expression of XIAP and BIRC5 was unchanged. Moreover, expression of the IAP inhibitor DIABLO was increased at doses 10% and 15% of As. The germ cell death process induced by as might be related to a decrease in testosterone production because of the reduced expression of steroidogenic enzymes.

Figure(12): Kidney (H&E;EX600)

Figure (13): Testis (H&E;EX200)

Figure (14): Epididymis lumen (H&E;EX600)

2.3.1.5% garlic oil bait:

Remain of remnant of glomerular capillaries was highly recorded in this group with presence of erythrocytic casts in the glomerular corpuscle space and in the lumen of renal tubules (Blue arrows) (Figure 15). That was supported by Joseph *et al.* (1989) who significant rise in urea and D-aspartate aminotransferase and inhibition of alkaline phosphatase in serum were observed in rats fed garlic extract (2 ml/100 g body wt., intragastrically) for

10 days (Fowotade *et al.*, 2017), who found pronounced degeneration of the tubular epithelial cells lining of the bowman's capsule and enlargement of the bowmann's space due to garlic toxicity.

The uterus showed degeneration and necrosis of uterine gland and fibrosis in lamina propria of endometrium (Figure 16). Two the ovaries showed atrophy of the growing follicles and free from any stages of maturation (Figure 17).

Figure (15): Kidney (H&E;EX600)

Shown severely edematous testis tubuli and severely degenerated necrosed testis tubuli , the basement membrane appeared bar of the spermatogonium cells (Blue arrow) with sever loss of myoid cells (Yellow arrow) ,degeneration and necrosis of leydig cells (Green arrow) start of accumulation of coagulated blood (Pink arrow), in rete testis (Figure 18). Epididymis showing destroyed

Figure (16): Ovarian (H&E;EX100)

Figure (17): Uterus(H&E;EX600)

degenerated immature spermatozoa with reduction in number (Figure 19). We also find effect like the above and that no deaths occurred. From this study, we can consider the concentration of garlic oils as a substance that affects the death and sterility of rats for both sexes and it preferable to use a 1% for deadly and sterile enrichment at the same time.

Figure(18): Testis (H&E;EX 400).

Figure (19): Epididymis(H&E;EX200).

3. Main test of the effect of different averages of garlic oil bait for black rats daily consumption, acceptability and mortality:

This discrepancy of the studies could be linked of differences in garlic concentration and the period length of treatment. Table (2) showed that the high average daily consumption and acceptability of rats was 0.5% of garlic oil bait, 11.19g and 54%, respectively. The high mortality percent of rat was 60% for 1% garlic oil bait. Non-significant change between the average daily consumption in pre-treatment and treatment test for rats in all

concentration. In 0.5% the average daily consumption in pre-treatment and treatment test were 9.48g and 11.19g, respectively with increased 1.18-fold. The acceptability and mortality percent's were 54.14% and 0%, respectively. In 1% garlic oil bait the average daily consumption in pre-treatment and treatment test were 7.69 g and 8.19 g, respectively with increased 1.07-fold in crushed maize . The acceptability and mortality percent's for rats were 51.57 and 60%, respectively. While than 1.5% garlic oil bait the average daily consumption in pre-treatment ant treatment test for rats

were 10.72 g and 9.19 g respectively with decreased 0.009-fold in crushed maize. The acceptability and mortality percent's for rats 46.16 and 40%, respectively. From the data mention above the acceptability decreased when

increased concentration and not in mortality. The one percent (1%) garlic oil bait is the effective concentration, (60% mortality) for rats control than 0.5 and 1.5%.

Table (2): Effect of average 0.5%, 1% and 1.5% of garlic oil bait for black rats daily consumption (g±SD), acceptability and mortality under laboratory conditions.

C.	R.	Average daily consumption										M.	A.
		Pre-treatment					Treatment						
		1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	4 th day	A.	1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	4 th day	A.		
0.50%	5	11.45 ± 4.85	9.33±3.32	8.53±3.29	8.53±3.29	9.48±3.51 ^B	11.15±4.21	11.41±3.52	12.00±4.51	10.19±1.50	11.19±3.33 ^B	0	54.14
1%	5	8.58±1.35	7.89±1.52	7.59±1.92	6.72±1.42	7.69±1.31 ^B	8.20±0.85	8.95±1.25	7.69±1.73	7.9±1.50	8.19±0.83 ^B	60	51.57
1.50%	3	11.73±2.66	11.05±1.33	9.80±1.82	10.32±2.10	10.72±1.65 ^B	9.31±2.14	8.99±1.73	9.32±1.67	9.14±1.77	9.19±1.55 ^B	40	46.16

C.: Cocentration R. : Replecates A. : Average M. : Mortality A.: Acceptability.
The vertical columns marked with the same letters are not significantly different by SAS (2006).

This study summaries that different garlic oil concentration has different histopathology properties and the impact of 1% garlic oil bait is the most consistent in atrophy of leydig cells of testes, atrophy of the glomerular tufts was recorded in male kidneys and all female is died. This review may be a good reference on relations between male and female sexual function for rat.

Other studies, Arla *et al.* (2004) found that product containing garlic oil show considerable promise as inexpensive, environmental benign and non-lethal bird repellents. Evaluation of acute toxicity of essential oil of garlic and its selected major constituent compounds against overwintering *Cacopsylla chinensis* (Yang and Li) (Hemiptera: Psyllidae) was studies by Zhao *et al.* (2013). His results, the two main constituent compounds , diallyl trisulfide and diallyl disulfide, exhibited strong acute toxicity against overwintering *C. chinensis*, with LC50 values of 0 .64 and 11.04 ug per adult, respectively.

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An aspect of resistance management in *Tribolium castaneum* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) against some insecticides

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 6 /7 /2020

Accepted: 26 /8 /2020

Keywords

Tribolium castaneum, malathion, pirimiphos-methyl, resistance, cross-resistance, chlorphyifos, methomyl and permethrin.

Abstract:

Most of the stored product insects acquire resistance against many chemical pesticides used in control of these important insects *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) beetle. Some laboratory experiments were conducted to determine the common resistance and resistance of the insect mentioned against four insecticides that belong to two groups: the organophosphorus (OP) pesticides including malathion, chlorpyrifos and pirimiphos-methyl and carbamate pesticides including methomyl using the thin film residue. The study also included the use of anise volatile plant oil as stimulant of the studied insecticides. The results obtained indicated that pirimiphos- methyl was the most toxic insecticide and about 5.9, 8 and 84 times as toxic as methomyl, chlorpyrifos and malathion, respectively. Results also revealed that increasing the period of exposure from 24 to 48 hours resulted in an increase the mortality of beetles. Furthermore, selection pressure on susceptible *T. castaneum* adults from chlorpyrifos induced moderate tolerance and selection with malathion and primiphos- methyl showed moderate resistant (< 40- fold), whereas pressure from methomyl achieved high resistant (>40- fold). The resistant strains have very little or no cross-resistance to the pyrethroids insecticides, permethrin and only less than two-fold cross-resistance to the OP insecticide chlorpyrifos. The level of cross-resistance in resistant strains varies with a compound. For synergism studies results refers to greater synergism of all insecticides was achieved in the resistant strains. Also results indicated that there was net gain towards synergism in the resistant strains compared to that of susceptible strains. The findings obtained include the possibility of using anise oil to synergies the action of tested insecticides to reduce, delay and prevent resistance in the flour beetle against pesticides under study.

Introduction

Pest resistance to the action of chemical pesticides reduced crop productivity, increases the cost of control, deteriorates the quality of

stored products and increases the loss of them. The incidence of pesticide resistant is a growing problem in stored product protection. Resistance to one or more pesticides has been reported in at least 500 species of insects and mites (Georehiou, 1990). An insecticide resistance problem in different stored product insects has been reported from many countries including Australia, Bahrain, Canada, Central African Republic, China, Cyprus, Egypt, Ethiopia, Gambia, Germany, Greece, Guyana, India, Japan, Kenya, Malawi, Malaysia, Morocco, Nepal, Nigeria, Pakistan, Philippines, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Syria, Taiwan, Uganda, United Kingdom, USA and Zambia (Dyte and Halliday, 1985; Prickett, 1987; Rassman, 1988; Sayaboc *et al.*, 1992; Yao and Lo, 1995; DARP, 2003; Benhalima *et al.*, 2004 and Abo-Elkasem *et al.*, 2018).

Stored product insect pests were found to be resistant against several insecticides including bioresmethrin, carbaryl, chlorpyrifos, chlorpyrifos-methyl, cyfluthrin, cyfluthrin, cypermethrin, DDT, deltamethrin, diazinon, dichlorous, ethylene dibromide, fenitrothion, lindane, malathion, methyl promide bromide, permethrin, phosphine, phoxin, pirimiphos-methyl, promecarb, propoxure, pyrethrins, temephos, tetrachlovinphos (DARP, 2003). The publications documented the extend of the resistance to different groups of conventional insecticides in stored product insect pests around the world. This frustrating situation indicates the powerlessness of conventional pest management strategies against insect pests of stored products. The development of cross-resistance (to different members of the same pesticide group) and multi-resistance (to different pesticides groups) in insect strains of many important insect species is a serious concern all over the world (Dyte

and Halliday, 1985; Zettler and Cuperus, 1990; Chaudhry, 1997 and Talukder, 2009).

More than 20000 species of pre- and post-harvest pests destroy approximately. One-third of the world's food production valued annually at more than 100 billion dollars among which the highest losses (43% of potential production) occur in developing Asian and African countries (Talukder, 2009). *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) and *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) are of the insect species which cause misfortune wastages to wheat grains and their products (Abo-Elkasem *et al.*, 2018). Many researchers recorded pyrethroid cross-resistance *T. castaneum* and *Rhyzopertha dominica* (Fabricius) (Coleoptera: Bostrichidae) (Collins, 1990; Guedes *et al.*, 1996; DGLISH *et al.*, 2003 and Abo-Elkasem *et al.*, 2018). The increasingly serious problems of resistance to pesticides and contamination of the biosphere associated with the large scale use of broad spectrum synthetic pesticide have directed the need for development of alternative strategies, such as: biorational chemicals, biological control agents and physical and ecological methods (Heyde *et al.*, 1984; Talukder and Howse, 1995; Hermawan *et al.*, 1997 and Talukder and Miyata, 2002).

Therefore, the current study was designed to determine the extent of resistance and cross-resistance of one of the important harmful insects of stored products namely *T. castaneum* adults to chemical pesticides chlorpyrifos, malathion, pirimiphos methyl, methomyl and permethrin using thin film method in addition to evaluate role of volatile plant oil, anise as synergetic agent as well as the negative cross-resistance between the tested

insecticides to reduce, delay or prevent this phenomenon.

Materials and methods

1. Insect strains:

The test insects were susceptible adults of red flour beetles *T. castaneum*, 2-3 weeks old was reared in a Laboratory of Stored Product Department, Sakha, Kafr El-Sheikh without insecticidal pressure or contamination for twelve generations. The insects were reared in a mixture of wheat seeds and wheat flour under laboratory conditions of $26 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 5\%$ RH. medium contained also 5% dried yeast.

2. Isolation of anise volatile oil:

Seeds of anise *Pimpinella anisum* L. Fam. Umbelliferae were purchased from the market, washed and dried under 50°C . The volatile oil was extracted by steam distillation using an oil trap.

3. Insecticides:

3.1. Lannate:

Common name; Methomy1
Chemical name: S-methyl N-(methyl carbamoyl oxy) thioacetimidate.
Oxime carbamate produced by it 11 Chemical Co. (90% soluble liquid).

3.2. Dursban:

Common name: Chlorpyrifos
Chemical name:
0,0-diethyl-1-0-3,5,6 - trichloro -2 pyridyl phosphorothioate.
48% E.C. produced by Dow Chemical Co.

3.3. Actellic:

Common name: Pirimiphos methyl
Chemical name: 2-diethyl-amino-6-methyl pyrimidin-4-yl 0.0-dimethyl phosphorothioate.
E.C. 50% produced by ICI Co.

3.4. Malathion:

Common name: Malathion
Chemical name: O.o-dimethyl phosphorodithioate ester of diethyl mercaptosuccinate
E.C.57% produced by Sumitomo Chemical Co.

3.5. Permethrin:

Common name: Permethrin
Chemical name: (3-phenoxyphenyl)-methyl (+ or -) cis-trans-3- (2,2-dichloroethy 1) -2,2) dimethyl1-cyclopropane-caropoxylate.
A synthetic pyrethroid produced by FMC corp. and ICI Americas

4. Bioassay procedures:

4.1. Exposure to treated surface (Thin film residue):

Stock dilution (W/V) of each toxicant was prepared by dissolving the desired quantity of material in acetone and subsequent serial dilutions were prepared with acetone. Toxicity tests were carried out on films achieved by spreading aliquot of one ml of each concentration, at the bottom of a petri-dish of 9 cm in diameter and left to dry. After complete dryness of the insecticide film, ten adult beetles (2-3 weeks old) were placed in each of the treated petri dishes. The same number of insects also was confined on petri dishes treated with acetone only and served as control. Mortality was recorded after 24h of exposure and corrected by Abbott's formula (1925). The LC50 values for all insecticides were calculated by the method of Litchfield and Wilcoxon (1949).

4.2. Resistance and cross-resistance studies:

Adults of susceptible strain (2-3-week-old) were exposed to the LC25 for tested insecticides for 24 hrs. by thin film technique. The survival insects were transferred into clean jars containing clean and sterilized medium which was preheated in an oven at 70°C for 2 hrs. After 15 day the parent adult individuals were eliminated. After 60 day the adults of the new generation were treated in the same manner as mentioned before and so on. At every generation LC50's of the tested insecticides were determined using thin film technique. To determine the cross-resistance patterns, concentration

response tests for each resistant strain to each insecticide were carried out and compared with those from susceptible strain.

4.3. Synergism studies:

To assess the effect of anise oil on the toxicity of tested insecticides, the dilutions of each insecticide and oil were mixed in the ratio of 1:10 after which the petri dishes were treated with different concentrations. After evaporation of acetone, ten adults of *T. castaneum* were introduced into each dish. Mortality was recorded after 24 h of exposure. The LC50 values for each combination was calculated by the method of Litchfield and Wilcoxon (1949). Synergistic ratio (S.R) was calculated according to Metcalf (1967) as follows:

$$SR = \frac{\text{LC50 of insecticide alone}}{\text{LC50 of insecticide in mixture}}$$

Results and discussion

1. Toxicity of various insecticides against laboratory susceptible strain of *Triboleum castaneum*:

Table (1) presents toxicity data of various insecticides to susceptible adults of *T. castaneum*. According to

the LC50 values, it is quite clear that pirimiphos-methyl was the most toxic insecticide and about 5.9, 8 and 84 times as toxic as methomyl, chlorpyrifos and malathion, respectively. Results also revealed that increasing the period of exposure from 24 to 48 hr. resulted in an increase in the mortality of the beetles. This conclusion agrees with the result of Fathia (1967), Abo-Elkasem *et al.*, 2018 and Abo Arab and Salem (2019). The red flour beetle *T. castaneum* is one of the most damage insect species invading warehouses and mills around the world (Rees, 2004; Almaši, 2008 and Mahroof and Hagstrum, 2012). Regarding the control of that and some other stored product pests, a variety of factors decide the effectiveness of contact insecticides, the most important of which is insect resistance (Subramanyam and Hagstrum, 1996; Kljajić and Perić, 2005, 2006; Boyer *et al.*, 2012 ; Opit *et al.*, 2012 and Kljajić *et al.*, 2009). Differences in the responses of the tested insect to insecticides may ascribe to the behavioural and alimentary habituations.

Table (1): Toxicity of various insecticides against *Triboleum castaneum* after 24 and 48 hrs. exposure to treated surface using thin film technique.

	24 hrs.				28 hrs.			
	LC50 ug/cm ²	Confidence Limits		Slope	LC50 ug/cm ²	Confidence Limits		Slope
Malathion	0.126	0.099	0.158	2.86	0.08	0.07	0.09	3.03
Chlorpyrifos	0.012	0.0097	0.014	2.7	0.0097	0.009	0.011	3.4
Methomyl	0.0088	0.005	0.016	1.13	0.002	0.001	0.004	1.27
Pirimiphos-methyl	0.0015	0.001	0.002	2.4	0.0009	0.0008	0.00094	1.39

2. Development of resistance to tested insecticides in susceptible *Triboleum castaneum*:

The development of resistance in the laboratory susceptible strain of *T. castaneum* after successive exposure to chlorpyrifos, malathion, methomyl and pirimiphos-methyl, for 5 generations was studied.

2.1. Against chlorpyrifos:

The chlorpyrifos selection pressure for 5 generations failed in building up more than 7.6-fold resistance as shown in Table (2). This result indicates that the development of resistance against chlorpyrifos is slower than that of each of the tested insecticides.

Table (2): Comparative levels of resistance in *Triboleum castaneum* selected by chlorpyrifos for 5 generations.

Generation	S ¹		R ²		R F
	LC50 ug/cm ²	Slope	LC50 ug/cm ²	Slope	
1	0.012	2.7	0.028	2.13	2.37
2	0.012	2.7	0.075	2.36	6.21
3	0.012	2.7	0.084	3.13	7.03
4	0.012	2.7	0.089	3.3	7.43
5	0.012	2.7	0.091	3.4	7.6

S = Susceptible strain R = Resistant strain

$$RF = \text{Resistance factor} = \frac{\text{LC50 of R strain}}{\text{LC50 of S strain}}$$

2.2. Against malathion:

Data in Table (3) showed the rate of development of resistance against malathion. Maximum resistance level obtained within five generations was 35-fold. It is also observed from the same table that malathion resistance

in *T. castaneum* was relatively slow in developing. This finding agrees with Parkin (1965) who reported that malathion resistance in stored-product insects was relatively slow in developing.

Table (3): Comparative levels of resistance in *Triboleum castaneum* selected by malathion for 5 generations.

Generation	S		R		R F
	LC50 ug/cm ²	Slope	LC50 ug/cm ²	Slope	
1	0.126	2.86	0.205	1.4	1.63
2	0.126	2.86	0.370	1.37	2.94
3	0.126	2.86	1.04	1.4	8.25
4	0.126	2.86	4.25	2.0	33.75
5	0.126	2.86	4.41	3.2	35.0

R = Resistant strain S = Susceptible strain RF = Resistance factor

2.3. Against methomyl:

It is clear from Table (4) that methomyl selection pressure succeeded in building up resistance in the strain. Maximum resistance level obtained

within 5 generations was 78.6-fold. It is also observed in contrary to malathion that methomyl resistance in *T. castaneum* was relatively fast.

Table (4): Comparative levels of resistance in *Triboleum castaneum* selected by methomyl for 5 generations.

Generation	S		R		R F
	LC50 ug/cm ²	Slope	LC50 ug/cm ²	Slope	
1	0.0088	1.13	0.017	2.13	1.88
2	0.0088	1.13	0.132	2.30	15.0
3	0.0088	1.13	0.181	2.2	20.54
4	0.0088	1.13	0.629	3.3	71.43
5	0.0088	1.13	0.692	3.4	78.6

S = Susceptible strain R = Resistant strain RF = Resistance factor

2.4. Against pirimiphos-methyl:

Selection pressure with pirimiphos-methyl (Table 5) had increased the LC50 nearly 30.6 times by the time F5 generation was reached.

During the first 2 generations of selection, the LC50 increased by 15 times, from the original 0.0015 ug/cm² to 0.023 ug/cm².

Table (5): Comparative levels of resistance in *Triboleum castaneum* selected by pirimiphos-methyl for 5 generations.

Generation	S		R		R F
	LC50 ug/cm ²	Slope	LC50 ug/cm ²	Slope	
1	0.0015	2.4	0.0016	2.5	1.07
2	0.0015	2.4	0.023	1.9	15.31
3	0.0015	2.4	0.034	1.9	22.45
4	0.0015	2.4	0.041	1.75	27.55
5	0.0015	2.4	0.046	1.7	30.6

S = Susceptible strain R = Resistant strain RF = Resistance factor

In conclusion, selection pressure on susceptible *T. castaneum* adults from chlorpyrifos induced moderate tolerance and selection with malathion and pirimiphos-methyl induced

moderate resistance (< 40 - fold), whereas pressure from methomyl induced high resistance (> 40 - fold) as shown in Table (6).

Table (6): Rates of development of resistance in the red flour beetle *Triboleum castaneum* after insecticidal pressure and selection for 5 generations.

Resistant strain of:	R F
Chlorpyrifos (Rc)	7.6
Malathion (Rm)	35.0
Methomyl (Rmo)	78.6
Pirimiphos-methyl (Rp)	30.6

Rc = Chlorpyrifos - resistant strain. Rm = Malathion - resistant strain.

Rmo = Methomyl - resistant strain. RF = Resistance factor Rp = Pirimiphos - methyl resistant strain.

These results revealed that the development of resistance against chlorpyrifos is slower than that of pirimiphos-methyl, malathion and methomyl. Currently, there are 122 insect pest species which are resistant to malathion (DARP, 2003). Malathion resistance in stored product insect-pests has been reported from all over the world (Rassman, 1988; Sayaboc *et al.*, 1992 and Zettler and Cuperus, 1990). Malathion specific resistance is widespread and stable in natural populations even in the absence of pesticide exposure. *T. castaneum* showed the greatest ability to develop resistance to pirimiphos-methyl and malathion exhibiting the highest frequency of resistant individuals mainly to malathion (Pacheco *et al.*, 1994).

2.5. Cross-resistance:

A comparison of susceptibility of susceptible and resistant strains,

susceptible strain (S) , chlorpyrifos - resistant strain(Rc) , malathion - resistant strain (Rm) , methomyl - resistant strain(Rmo) and pirimiphos - methyl resistant strain (RP) of *T. castaneum* to each of the tested insecticides is given in Tables (7, 8, 9 and 10). The resistant strains had very little or no cross-resistance to the pyrethroid insecticide, permethrin and only less than two-fold cross-resistance to the OP insecticide, chlorpyrifos. The level of cross-resistance in resistant strains varies with a compound, e.g. in chlorpyrifos- resistant strain, the level for each compound was 67.9-fold for methomyl and 13.8-fold for pirimiphos-methyl (Table 7). The level of cross-resistance in malathion resistant strain were 67.9-fold for methomyl and 14.3-fold for pirimiphos - methyl as shown in Table (8) .

Table (7): Cross resistance patterns in chlorpyrifos resistant red flour beetles.

Insecticide	LC50 ug/cm ²		Resistance factor (RF)
	S	Rc	
Pirimiphos-rnethyl	0.0015	0.021	13.8
Malathion	0.126	1.07	8.5
Methomyl	0.0088	0.598	67.9
Permethrin	0.519	0.078	0.15

Table (8): Cross resistance patterns in malathion resistant red flour beetles.

Insecticide	LC50 ug/cm ²		Resistance factor (R F)
	S	Rc	
Methomyl	0.0088	0.598	67.9
Permethrin	0.519	0.016	0.03
Chlorpyrifos	0.012	0.021	1.76
Pirimiphos-rnethyl	0.0015	0.022	14.30

In methomyl - resistant strain, the levels of cross-resistance were 5-fold for malathion and 18.4-fold for pirimiphos - methyl (Table 9). The

levels of cross-resistance in pirimiphos-methyl resistant strain were 8-fold for malathion, 50-fold for methomyl as shown in Table (10).

Table (9): Cross-resistance patterns in methomyl- resistant red flour beetles.

Insecticide	LC50 ug/cm ²		Resistance factor (R F)
	S	Rc	
Permethrin	0.519	0.093	0.18
Malathion	0.126	0.63	5.0
Pirimiphos-rnethyl	0.0015	0.028	18.4
Chlorpyrifos	0.012	0.023	1.89

Table (10): Cross-resistance patterns in pirimiphos-rnethyl- resistant red flour beetles.

Insecticide	LC50 ug/cm ²		Resistance factor (R F)
	S	Rc	
Malathion	0.126	1.008	8.0
Methomyl	0.0088	0.44	50.0
Permethrin	0.519	0.005	0.01
Chlorpyrifos	0.012	0.018	1.49

In malathion resistant of *T. castanum*, cross-resistant to the pyrethroid, permethrin was not detected (Zettler and Jones, 1977). Attia and Frecker (1984) reported that, OP-resistant strain of *O. surinamensis* showed low level of resistance to dichlorovos, bioresmethrin and pyrethrins (< 10-fold). Bansode and Campbell (1979) found that, malathion resistant strain of the red flour beetle *T. castanum* did not show cross-resistance to 4 other organophosphorus insecticides but exhibited tolerance to these insecticides (0.8-1-fold).

Generally, in order to have effective control methods available in the eventuality that resistance in insects increases to the extent that present chemical controls are no longer

effective, it is important to test new materials and methods against strains of insects. The tested OP compound, chlorpyrifos-methyl might satisfy the criteria of these materials against the red flour beetle in this respect. No indication of resistance to chlorpyrifos-methyl was found in different strains of *T. castanum* (Halliday *et al.*, 1988; Zettler and Cuperus, 1990 and Zettler, 1991). Mribeiro *et al.* (2003) surveyed insecticide resistance and synergism in Brazilian population of *Sitophilus zeamais* (Motschulsky) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) using the discriminating concentrations established from LC₉₅'s estimated for a standard susceptible population against chlorpyrifos-methyl, malathion and pirimiphos-methyl and three

pyrethroids (Cypermethrin, deltamethrin and permethrin). Collins *et al.* (2003) investigated the resistance that had emerged against fumigants and protectants. Andric *et al.* (2015) stated that in insecticides choices need to be made carefully, considering the target species of stored product insects and their susceptibility to malathion and other insecticides. Attention should also be focused on a crucial role of insecticide selection of different stored grain insect populations in order to enable predictions of resistance evolution in individual populations and, based on such knowledge, sound choices of the most adequate resistance management strategy. There is cross-resistance to permethrin in two strain, but no clear evidence of cross-resistance to pirimiphos-methyl and chlorpyrifos-methyl was found in any of the strains tested (Lorini, 1997).

3. Synergism studies:

Many workers used synthetic synergists to overcome the resistance of *T. castaneum* to insecticides such as Ardley (1976), Dhingra and Sarup (1983), Hasan *et al.* (1983), Udeaan and Kalra (1983) and Binns (1986). In this work anise oil was isolated from the

seeds of (*Pimpinella anisum* L.) and tested for its activity as synergist for the toxicity of the tested insecticides in susceptible and resistant strains. Table (11) presents effects of anise oil on the toxicity of the tested insecticides to resistant and susceptible strains. Greater synergism of all insecticides was achieved in the resistant strains. Notably high synergistic ratios were obtained for methomyl (2.93 x), malathion (2.15 x), pirimiphos-methyl (2.0 x) and chlorpyrifos (1.75 x). However, a comparison of the synergistic ratios for the resistant strains and susceptible strain indicates that there was a net gain toward synergism in the resistant strains, e.g. the synergism of methomyl was increased from 1.04 in the S strain to 2.93 in the Rmo strain. Therefore, the addition of anise oil strongly synergized all the tested insecticides and reduced the resistance factors of resistant strains. The reduction was greatest for methomyl and pirimiphos-methyl, as shown in Table (11). However, it did not enhance the susceptibility of the resistant strains of the extent of reaching the susceptible strain level.

Table (11): Comparative synergism of insecticides by anise oil in adults of susceptible(s) and resistant (Rc, Rm, Rme, Ro) strains of *Triboleum castaneum*.

Insecticide (I)	Strain	I+synergist (oil)	LC50 ug/cm ²	SR	RF
Chlorpyrifos (C)	S	C only	0.012	-	-
		C + oil	0.011	1.12	-
	Rc	C only	0.091	-	7.6
		C + oil	0.052	1.75	4.8
Malathion (M)	S	M only	0.126	-	-
		M + oil	0.07	1.8	-
	Rm	M only	4.41	-	35
		M + oil	2.05	2.15	28.9
Methomyl (MO)	S	Mo only	0.0088	-	-
		Mo + oil	0.0063	1.4	-
	Rmo	Mo only	0.692	-	78.6
		M + oil	0.236	2.93	37.5
Pirimiphos-methyl (P)	S	P only	0.0015	-	-
		P + oil	0.0014	1.04	-
	Rp	P only	0.046	-	30.6
		P + oil	0.023	2.0	15.9

SR = Synergistic ratio RF = Resistant factor

Therefore, non-chemical methods with special reference to biological control including behavioral, botanical and microbial control can be practiced solely or in combination as effective alternative to chemical control. Few natural products such as volatile oils and their constituents can also be used to control stored grain insects. Further, volatile repellents after evaporation in the medium after insects from feeding and cause high mortality rate in insects (Deb, 2019). The development of resistance can be delayed by using binary combinations of insecticides, keeping in view the importance of synergism as well as the concern about environmental hazards and emergence of resistance these insecticides (Riaz *et al.*, 2019). Researchers are currently seeking new classes of naturally occurring pesticides might be compatible with newer pest control approach. Plant-derived materials have been found to be highly effective, more readily, biodegradable, less likely to contaminate the environment and to have lower potential to produce resistance, making them viable alternatives to synthetic pesticides (Talukder and Howse, 1995; Shaaya *et al.*, 1997; Talukder and Miyata, 2002; Park *et al.*, 2003 and Khan and Chumbs, 2003). The essential oil of *Artemisia annua* L. was found to be toxic and repellent against *T. castaneum* and *Callosobruchus maculatus* Fabricius (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) (Tripathi *et al.*, 2000). The essential oil vapours distilled from anise, cumin, eucalyptus, oregano and properties, causing 100% mortality of the eggs of *T. confusum* and *Ephestia kuehniella* Zeller (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) (Tunc *et al.*, 2000).

The best way to manage pesticide resistance is to focus on three strategies: avoid, delay, and reversal. Avoid the development of pesticide resistance problems with the

use of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) programs, which reduce reliance on chemical control. Delay resistance by using pesticides only when needed, as indicated by monitoring, and when pests are at a susceptible stage. Delay can also be achieved by using pesticides from different chemical classes (e.g., Organophosphates, carbamates, pyrethroids, biologicals, etc.) and rotating their use. Reversal of some resistance can occur by allowing time between applications of a class of pesticide to permit resistant populations to become diluted by pesticide-susceptible individuals. Key elements of resistance management include minimizing pesticide use, avoiding tank mixes, avoiding persistent chemicals, and using long-term rotations of pesticide from different chemical classes (US pest Management Guidelines, 2019).

The current study estimating the resistance and cross-resistance of some chemical pesticides belonging to three different chemical groups namely malathion primiphos-methyl, methomyl, chlorpyrifos and permethrin in the red rust flour beetle *T. castaneum*. The study used anise oil to break the resistance phenomenon in the insect by mixing anise oil with studied pesticides and estimating the synergistic factor. The result obtained showed the insect's rapid acquisition of resistance to some pesticides and its tolerance to other as well as the absence of cross-resistance between some pesticides, as well as a clear stimulating effect of anise oil. The study suggests using anise oil as synergist agent for the studied pesticides. As well as using pesticides that have a negative cross-resistance to break the insect resistance in question for the tested pesticides. Ultimately, a key to the successful management of resistance to insecticides is its early detection and proper characterization. All resistance

data are being stored in an integrated database for future reference on trends and frequencies of resistance. The present study suggested application of sequence of different groups to prevent or delay the resistance and cross-resistance to certain insecticides specially that used in the current study.

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Crow counted and its control with zinc phosphide bait methods in Giza Governorate

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 8/7 /2020

Accepted: 9 /9 /2020

Keywords

Birds, crow, zinc phosphide bait, control and Giza.

Abstract:

Crows of birds are wide world, with some harmful environmental effects. It was recorded in many Governorates of Egypt, attacking plants and animals production causing visible losses. This study was conducted at Al-Saff district, Giza Governorate to survey species and their numbers in different habitats during 2018-2020 and how to control them with zinc phosphide. Only species, hooded crow, *Corvus corone* L.) Aves: Corvidae) recorded in old agriculture land, reclaimed land and city. The highest number recorded during spring in May then decrease through autumn, summer and winter the lowest count in February at old agriculture land and reclaimed. In city the count was highly during autumn in October then reduce in spring, summer and winter the lowest birds recorded in February. The total numbers increase from 2018 to 2020 and the increase percent were 15.5, 17.9 and 8.8% to each habitat respectively. The population crow was highly in reclaimed land comparing with old land and city, the average number were 255, 232 and 166 birds to each habitat respectively. When using fish bait 1% and 0.5% zinc phosphide directly the reduction percent of birds reach to 52.5% and 48.5%. While the percentage of reduction increased to 54.5% with fish without Zinc phosphide as pre-baiting before zinc phosphide fish bait 0.5%.

Introduction

Crows are one of the world's most widespread birds. Barry *et al.* (2003) mentioned that the species of crows are spreading in more than 25 region including Africa, Middle East and Southeast Asia. These species are associated with human activity, acclimatized in different habitats, and have a negative impact on the environment. India is the home of house crows, *Corvus splendens* Vieillot)Aves: Corvidae) while,

Australia is the home of the hooded crows, *Corvus corone* L. (Aves: Corvidae). Crows are rapidly growing as the House crows have grown 30 times in 2033 compared to 1985 in Singapore. Their numbers are increasing due to the availability of shelter, food, and absence of vital enemies and control programs. Ryall (1992) and GISD reported that crows feeding on wide range of foods, small reptiles, amphibians, birds, mammals,

insects, fishes, domestic animals, crops, vegetables, fruits and food waste. In Egypt, some species of crows existed in different habitats, where they recorded the economic limit of the damage. Goodman *et al.* (1989) reported that hooded crow, *C. corone* recorded in parts of Nile delta and valley of south to Aswan, Suez Canal, Fayoum and Northeastern Sinai. Hassan (2008) surveyed hooded crow *C. corone* in all habitats of Qalubya, Sharkia, Ismailia, Suez and Sohag Governorates. In Ismailia, the numbers of crows were differently according to months, seasons and areas. Generally, the highest numbers recorded during spring, autumn, summer and winter, respectively. Tharwat, 1997; Khattab, 2002 ; Bonnah, 2007; Dhinds *et al.* (1991) and Feare and Watson (1990) clear that crows are environmentally harm because of their disturbing sound and the terror they cause to humans to steal food and attack crops, vegetables, fruits and animal production farms. Kamel (2014) reported that, house crows *C. splendens* established in Ismailia governorate and the crows are perceived as a risk to human health and their crops. They have damage fruits, mango, guava, cantaloupe, dates, fig, tomato, cucumber, grape, strawberry, watermelon and crops, wheat, green beans, cabbage, barley, peanut, rice in Abou Swier and Almaif cities. She recommended, pay attention to hygiene and capture for adult birds, especially before meeting season, and to conduct more of the biological and behavioral studies to controlling crows. Crows transmit many diseases to people and domestic animals as cholera, dysentery, yellow fever...etc., (Cooper, 1996 and Roy, 1998).

To reduce damage of crows some studies were conducted to control them. From the general methods of controlling birds, the environments of crows can be changed and disturbed by

the imagination of combat, shooting, ultrasound, nest destruction and limitation of food supplies or nesting status. El-Bahrawy *et al.* (2007) found that klerat® (anticoagulant rodenticide) was the most effective then methomyl® and zinc phosphide® against crows.

This study aims to determine the species of crow and numerical movements during two years of study in the three habitats, the delta lands, reclaimed lands and cities at Al-Saff district, Giza Governorate. In addition, the appropriate taste of zinc phosphide baits to reduce their numbers and reduce their harm.

Materials and methods

1. Tested habitats:

1.1. Old agriculture lands:

These lands are in the west, near the Nile and villages. It is cultivated with crops, wheat, corn and clover. Also, some vegetables tomato, cucumber, eggplant and cabbage. Irrigate by immersion. Arbors spread over the land to protect cattle and sheep that feed on the remaining crops. Animal waste also piles up.

1.2. Reclaimed lands:

This land is desert and located in the east far villages. It reclaimed cultivation with fruit, mango, figs, date palm and some planted with crops of wheat, clover and vegetable such as tomato, green pepper and eggplant. These lands irrigated by sprinklers and droppers. Spread not far away from city dumps wastes.

1.3. City:

It is residential area crowded with residents and buildings located in center. Three habitats located in Al-Saff district, Giza Governorate.

2. Census crows:

During 2018-2020 Crows counted in three tested habitats. For each habitat a plot (40*500 M.) were determined with discretionary lines. Monthly for 4 consecutive days the

crows on the ground, perched and plane were counted before sunset for 15 minutes, according to Sarker *et al.* (2009) by binocular field 10*50. Crows identified using Collins bird guide (Svensson *et al.*, 2010) and the number of crows species recorded for comparison.

3. Chemical control:

Zinc phosphide acute poison rodenticide (Zinc phosphide 94% active ingredient) obtained from Kafr-Zayate for pesticides, Egypt. Fish slices (3*1 Cm.) were mixing with concentration of 0.5 and 1% Zinc Phosphide. A distance of 2 Km, one feddan was chosen for each treatment. First and second treatments applied with Zinc phosphide bait 0.5 and 1% directly. While in third treatment fish slices without poison applied for 3 days then poison bait 0.5% for one day. In the early morning, distribute the baits (100 gram) in the monitor place. Numbers of birds counted before and after treatment and the population reduction calculated.

Results and discussion

In three habitats, old agriculture land, reclaimed land and city through two years only species of crows was

found, hooded crow, *C. corane* in Al-Saff district, Giza Governorate. It is spread in Europe and Middle East in Egypt and Turkey (Hadoram and Lars, 2018). Attia (2013) found that from the resident birds in Egypt species recorded as harmful birds in Ismailia hooded crow, *C. corone cornix* and house crow, *C. splendens*, order Passeriformes. Ahmed *et al.* (2018) recorded hooded crow, *C. corone* in sheep farm at Ras-Seder, South Sinai. Data in Table (1) and Figure (1) showed that in old agriculture lands, reclaimed lands and city habitats the number were lowest in Jan. (8, 8), (9, 12) and (4, 4) birds to each habitat during two tested years respectively. In the same years the highest number were (30, 32) and (33, 35) birds in May to old and reclaimed lands. In city, the highest number of birds was 20 and 21 bird in Apr. The total number of birds for two years was 206 and 238, 240 and 283 and 159 and 173 birds and the number were 232.5, 255 and 166 birds to each habitat respectively. The average density of crows records 23.3 at old land 25.5 at reclaimed land and 16.6 per100m at city.

Table (1): Numbers of crows in different habitats at Al-Saff district, Giza Governorate.

Month	Old Agriculture Lands			Reclaimed Land			City		
	First	Second	A.	First	Second	A.	First	Second	A.
May	30	32	31	33	35	34	20	21	20.5
Jun.	21	23	22	22	24	22.5	16	16	16
July	21	21	21	19	24	21	16	17	16.5
Aug.	18	17	17.5	20	23	20.5	13	12	12.5
Sep.	23	25	24	26	28	26	17	19	18
Oct.	26	25	25.5	24	27	25.5	20	19	19.5
Nov.	20	21	20.5	20	24	22	18	18	18
Dec.	10	12	11	10	13	12.5	12	13	12.5
Jan.	8	8	8	9	12	10.5	4	4	4
Feb.	7	10	8.5	10	12	11	6	8	7
Mar.	15	16	15.5	17	24	19.5	11	12	11.5
Apr.	28	28	28	30	32	31	18	18	18
Total	206	238	232.5	240	283	255	159	173	166
Av.	17.16	19.8	19.4	20	22.5	21.25	13.25	14.4	13.8
L.S.D.	5.61								

A. Average

Data in Table (2) and Figure (2) clear that the maximum number of crow recorded during spring, 74.5 and 84.5 birds in old agriculture lands and reclaimed lands decrease to 70 and 73.5 ,60.5 and 64 ,72.5 and 34 birds in autumn, summer and winter at two habitats . While the maximum numbers recorded during autumn 56 in city, reduced to 50 birds in spring, 45 birds in summer and the minimum were 23.5 during winter. Analysis results clear that the numbers of crow increase from year to year and the rate of increase was

17.9, 15 and 6.9% at reclaimed lands, old lands and city, respectively. These results due to the availability of shelter and food suitable for crows in each habitat, particularly in reclaimed land which recorded the highest number of crows and the rate of increase compared with other habitats. Chong *et al.* (2012) reported that crows are rapidly adaptable in different environments, and the number of crows increased from 6000 up 10909 at the last 10 years in Ismailia Governorate.

Table (2): Average numbers of crows through different seasons during 2018-2020 at different habitats.

Seasons	Old agriculture land	Reclaimed land	City
Winter	72.5	34	23.5
Spring	74.5	84.5	50
Summer	60.5	64	45
Autumn	70	73.5	56
L.S.D.	24.59		

During spring months crows start mating and search of food after decrease activity during winter months so that the number were highly. The end of spring parent is busy with forming the nest and incubating the eggs and feeding their young's. With autumn, the crow number increase again due to the activity of adult birds and young's before entering the winter. In city, the houses may be not suitable for reproduction so that, crow search for another place to breeding and the numbers reduce compare with autumn. Khattab (2002) stated that abundance and distribution of hooded crow were highly during the breeding season and declined at the non-breeding season. In

Table (3): Effect of pre-baiting method and concentration on crows reduction with zinc phosphide baits.

Treatment	Number of birds		Reduction%
	Before treatment	After treatment	
Bait 0.5% without pre-baiting	33	17	48.5
Bait 1% without pre-baiting	40	19	52.5
Bait 0.5% with pre-baiting	35	17	54.5

addition, the numbers differ during year months. Bonnah (2007) reported that, the numbers of hooded crow increased annually during spring followed by autumn and decreased during summer and winter. Data in Table (3) and Figure (3) showed that the population reduction of crows was 48.5 and 52.5% to fish bait 0.5 and 1% without pre-baiting. The reduction reaches to 54.5 at fish bait 0.5% with pre-baiting. Looking, the results clear that the population reduction increased to 4% and with fish bait 1% compare with fish bait 0.5% without pre-baiting. But using pre-baiting method with fish bait 0.5% the reduction increased to 5.9%.

These results may be attributed to crow's reassurance and consuming Zinc phosphide bait using pre-baiting method. Ahmed *et al.* (2018) found that using methomyl, zinc phosphide 0.5 and super caid (Anticoagulant rodenticide) more effect on hooded crows, *C. corone* during April and the population reduction was 46.8, 53.1 and 73.3% to each chemical respectively.

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Effect of storage on the stability on some organophosphorus formulation and their impurities.

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 2 /7 /2020

Accepted: 27/9 /2020

Keywords

Fenitrothion,
malathion , sun light ,
UV ray , storage and
impurities.

Abstract:

The present work was carried out to study the persistence of somathion Kz 50% (W/v) EC (Fenitrothion) and malatoxs 57 % (W/V) EC (Malathion) under storage at 54 °C for 28 days. The stability of fenitrothion and malathion active ingredient were 50.43 and 57.17 % before storage for all fenitrothion and malathion become after storage at the end of experiment 39.52 and 36.56% for 28 days storage respectively. The impurities of fenitrothion 50 % EC before storage were UND S-methyl fenitrothion , TMP Tetramethyl pyrophosphorothioat and water become after storage 1.17 % , UND and UND after 28 days from storage at 54 °C respectively . Also, malathion 57 % EC before storage meooops, mooSPs, malaxoin and isomalathion after storage 0.75 , 0.217 , UND and 2.89 % respectively. Fenitrothion and malathion degradation after 28 days product S –methyl Fenitrothion and O,O S triethyl ester , malathion product isomalathion.

Introduction

Organophosphate pesticides (OPs) are used worldwide in agriculture, municipal hygiene, and household pests control (Edwards and Tchounwou, 2005 ; Zheng *et al.*, 2007 and Yang *et al.*, 2008). OPs compounds such as malathion, fenitrothion ,cholrpyrifos, parathion is commonly used as insecticides for over 50 years. OPs work by attacking the nervous system; they are essentially the nerve poisons. Specifically, these compounds inhibit acetylcholinesterase enzyme involved in the hydrolysis of the neurotransmitter, acetylcholine at cholinergic synapses in the central and peripheral nervous systems (cholinergic syndrome) (O'Malley, 1997; Solberg

and Belkin, 1997 and Musilek *et al.*, 2005). Malathion and fenitrothion are used in agriculture to control a wide range of sucking and chewing insect pests in a variety of field crops, fruits and vegetables. Malathion can also be used for insect control on livestock, in stables and on stored products.

In this paper, we studied the effect of storage and influence sun light direct and UV lamp of pesticide on (Fenitrothion and malathion) during storage for 28 days at 54 °C .

Materials and methods

1. Source of sample pesticides: Center Agric. Pesticides Laboratory and formulation of pesticides (Table 1).

Table (1): Showed the formulation of pesticides.

Treed name	Active ingredient	Formulation Types	Impurities	Structure
Somathioen (Kz) 50%	Fenitrothion	EC	1- S-methyl fenitrothion Maximum: 2.5% 2- Tetramethyl pyrophosphorothioat (TMPP) Maximum: 0.3 % 3- Water Maximum: 2 g/kg.	
Malatoxs 57 %	Malathion	EC	1- Malaaxon Maximum: 0.1% 2- Isomalathion) Maximum: 2.5% 3- O,O,Strimethyl ester). Maximum: 1.6% 4-MeOOOPS-triester Maximum: 0.5%	 Malathion

2. Sample preparation for tested pesticides:

Accurately weighed enough samples formulation equivalent to 10 mg of standard in a different 25 ml volumetric flask for each sample, and slowly mixed with methanol and the volume was completed with methanol.

3. Sample preparation for impurities:

One g. tested formulation samples in 25 ml volumetric flask for each sample were prepared and slowly mixed with methanol and the volume was completed with methanol.

4. Storage stability tests:

The Previously pesticides (Malathion and fenitrothion) formulation were stored in oven at 54 °C for 14 days according to the (CIPAC Hand book F., 1995 and CIPAC Hand book, 1983) respectively 14 days storage. During the storage period the samples were taken at 0, 1, 3 ,7 , 14 , 21 and 28 days from storage to determine the active ingredient for formulation under testes.

5. Influence of direct sunlight and UV ray:

The pesticides (Malathion and fenitrothion) formulation were influence of direct sunlight .The

samples were taken at 0, 1,5 ,12 , 24 , 36 and 48 hrs. from influence direct sun light to determine the active ingredient and impurities content for formulation under testes if is present .

6. Determiation of pesticides by GC/Ms:

Apparatus Agilent B, 5977 AMSD gas chromatography equipped with an Agilent mass spectrometric detector , with a direct capillary interface and fused silica capacity Colum (30 m x 0.025 mm HP -5 0.25 microm 60 to 325/325 °C). Samples were injected under the following condition; Helium was used as carrier gas at approximately 1 ml /min, pulsed split mode, split ratio (10:1) split flow 10 ml /min. The solvent delay was 4 min and the injection size were 1 UL. Oven temperature program , %0 °C for O<5 min , the 10 /min ramp to 190 °C followed by a 10 °C /min ramp to 210 °C for 1 min followed by a 10 °C /min ramp to 300 °C and held for 2 min, total run time followed by a injection temperature was set at 280 °C. Wiley mass spectral data was used in the identification of the separated peaks .

7. Determination of active ingredient and their impurities by GLC apparatus:

Fenitrothion, malathion and their impurities were determined according to the method of CIPAC Hand Book E. (1993) and CIPAC Hand Book (1983) with some modification using Hewlett-Packard 6890 gas liquid chromatography equipped with flame ionization detector (FID), capillary column HP-50% (15m x 0.53mm i.d. μ m film thickness), and the carrier gas was nitrogen of flow rate 10 ml/min. Oven temperature 100 °C, 160 and 180 °C, respectively for the above pesticides and its impurities, injector temperature was 250°C and detector temperatures, 200°C. Under these conditions the retention times for dimethoate and its impurities were (2.45, 2.86 and 3.72 min), the results of the pesticides and their impurities were quantitatively determined by comparison with the active ingredient standards of known purity under the identical GLC conditions.

8. Determination of water in formulation which contains water impurities:

The water was determined by using isotropic method (Danstark apparatus), the apparatus consists of glass flask connected by a tube to cylindrical tube fitted with graduated receiving tube and reflux condenser. The receiving tube is graduated in 0.1 divisions so that the error of reading does not exceed 0.05 ml. The preferred source of heat is an electric heater with rheostat control. The upper portion of the flask and connecting tube could be insulated. Thoroughly the receiving tube and condenser of the apparatus were cleaned by rinse with water and allowed to dry. 200 ml of toluene and about 2ml of water were introduced into dry flask. The flask was heated until the liquid distillation over period of 2 hours

and allowed to cool for about 30 min and reading off volume of water to an accuracy of 0.05 ml (first distillation). A quantity of the material was weighted accurately to give about 2-3 ml of water for 15 min and transfer to the flask gently. When boiling begins, distillate rate of 2 drops per second until most of the water has still over then the rate of distillation was increase to about 4 drops per second. As soon as the water has been completely distilled, the inside of the condenser tube was rinsed with toluene. The distillation was continued for 15 min, the heat was removed, and the receiving tube could cool to room temperature, and the tube was dislodged by tapping. The water and toluene layer could separate and the volume of water were read off (second distillation) (CIPAC Hand Book F., 1995). The content of water as percentage was calculated using the formula: $\% = 100 (n_1 - n) / W$.

Where: W= the weight of the material being examined.

n= the number of ml water obtained in the first distillation of ml.

n₁= the number of ml water obtained in both distillations.

Results and discussion

1. Effect of storage temperature on stability of soumithion and malatoss active ingredient at 54°C:

The Present data in Table (2) illustrated that the stability of fenitrothion and malathion active ingredient were 50.43 and 57.17 before storage for all fenitrothion and malathion become after storage at the end of experiment 39.52 and 36.56 for 28 storage respectively. According to International Organization WHO specification storage at 54 °C for 3 days and FAO specification storage at 54 °C for 14 days. In general, storage under high temperature above 35 °C show negatively affect the stability if organophosphorus (Fishel, 1993).

Table (2): Effect of storage temperature on stability of soumithion Kz and malatoxs active ingredient at 54°C.

Storage periods (Days)	Soumithion Kz 50 % %		Malatoxs 57 %	
	Fenitrothion 50 %	Loss %	Malathion 57 %	Loss %
0*	50.43	00	57.17	00
1	50.43	00	57.10	0.12
3	50.21	0.43	57.00	0.29
7	49.23	2.37	56.23	1.67
14	47.91	4.99	56.20	1.64
21	40.56	19.33	47.34	17.19
28	39.52	21.16	36.56	36.05

0* One hour before exposure to storage.

2. Influence of direct sunlight and UV ray exposure active ingredients fenitrothion and malathion :

The present date in Table (3) illustrated that the stability of fenitrothion and malathion active ingredient were 50.43% and 57.43% before exposure sun light for all

fenitrothion and malathion become after exposure sun light at the end of experiment 45.77 and 39.11% for 48 hrs. exposure sun light respectively. The percentage loses of fenitrothion and malathion were 24.58 and 22.13% after 48 hrs. of exposure of UV lamp.

Table (3): Influence of direct sunlight and UV ray exposure active ingredients fenitrothion and malathion.

Storage periods (Hours)	Sun light				UV ray			
	Fenitrothion 50 %	Loose	Malatoxs 57%	Loss	Fenitrothion 50 %	Loos	Malatoxs 57%	Loss
0*	50.43	00	57.43	00	57.43	00	57.43	00
1	50.33	0.19	57.12	0.61	57.33	0.17	57.00	0.74
5	49.23	2.38	57.00	0.59	55.86	2.73	57.00	0.74
12	47.50	5.81	55.23	3.83	55.09	4.07	55.34	3.48
24	47.46	5.88	41.45	27.82	48.26	15.96	53.96	6.04
36	46.51	7.58	40.77	29.00	44.82	21.19	53.00	7.71
48	45.77	9.24	39.11	31.89	43.32	24.58	44.72	22.13

3. Effect of storage temperature on stability of impurities fenitrothion and malathion 54 °C:

Data in Table (4) show that the impurities of Fenitrothion 50 % EC before storage were UND S-methyl Fenitrothion , TMPP Tetramethyl pyrophosphorothioat and water become after storage 1.17 , and UND and UND after 28 days from storage at 54 °C respectively this results according to

organization FAO specification maximum level impurities 2.5 % S-methyl fenitrothion . Also, malathion 57 % EC before storage meoops , moosPs , malaxoin and isomalathion after storage 0.75 , 0.217 , UND and 2.89 respectively . The percentage of meoops and isomalathion were more than the (FAO maximum levels 0.5 and 2.5 % , respectively).

Table (4): Effect of storage temperature on stability on impurities Fenitrothion and malathion at 54 °C.

Storage periods (Days)	Soumithion (KZ) (Fenitrothion 50 % EC)			Malatoxs (Malathion 57 % EC)			
	S-methyl fenitrothion	Tetramethyl pyrophospho rothioat (TMPP)	Water	eeoops ester	MooSPs	Malaxoin	ISO malathion
0*	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND
1	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND
3	UND	UND	UND	0.030	0.36 1	UND	0.204
7	0.69	UND	UND	0.036	0.141	UND	0.180
14	0.78	UND	UND	0.44	0.160	UND	1.88
21	1.07	UND	UND	0.519	0.216	UND	1.89
28	1.17	UND	UND	0.751	0.217	UND	2.89

0* One hour before exposure to storage.

4. Effect of storage temperature on stability on impurities fenitrothion and malathion at sun light and UV ray:

The present Tables in (5 and 6) showed that the impurities of Fenitrothion 50 % EC before influence exposure sun light and UV ray were UND S-methyl Fenitrothion , tetramethyl pyrophorothiate and water become after exposure sun light and UV lamp 1.92, UND, UND , 1.83 , UND and UND after 48 hrs. from exposure sun light and UV lamp

respectively . Also, malathion 57 % EC before exposure sun light and UV lamp UND meoooks , mooSPs , malathion and isomalathion after exposure sun light and UV ray 0.80 , 2.32 , UND , 2.80, 0.79 , 2.28, UND and 2.56 respectively . The percentage of meoooks , mooSPs and isomalathion were more than the FAO Maximum levels 0.5 , 1.6 and 2.5 %) .It was notes that isomalathion was increased by the storage period, this could be due the degradation of malathion.

Table (5): Effect of storage temperature on stability on impurities fenitrothion and malathion at sun light.

Storage periods (Days)	Fenitrothion			Malathion			
	S. Methyl fenitrothion	Tetramethyl pyrophorothiate	Water	Meoooks ester	MooSPs	Malaxoin	ISO malathion
0	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND
1	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND
5	UND	UND	UND	0.35	1.10	UND	0.29
12	UND	UND	UND	0.52	1.20	UND	0.34
24	1.02	UND	UND	0.66	1.97	UND	1.18
36	1.09	UND	UND	0.76	2.28	UND	1.38
48	1.92	UND	UND	0. 80	2.32	UND	2.80

0* One hour before exposure to storage.

Table (6): Effect of storage temperature on stability on impurities Fenitrothion and malathion at UV ray.

Storage periods (Days)	Fenitrothion			Malathion			
	S. methyl fenitrothion	Tetramethyl pyrophorothiate	Water	Meooops ester	MooSPs	Malaxoin	ISO malathion
0	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND
1	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND	UND
5	UND	UND	UND	0.24	1.05	UND	0.20
12	UND	UND	UND	0.56	1.45	UND	0.31
24	0.80	UND	UND	0.77	1.97	UND	1.29
36	1.00	UND	UND	0.79	2.28	UND	2.03
48	1.83	UND	UND	0.79	2.28	UND	2.56

0* One hour before exposure to storage.

Figure (1): Possible pathways for the formation of impurities of malathion during storage.

5. The degradation product on fenitrothion and malathion By GC/MS:

The data in present in Table (7) showed that fenitrothion and malathion degradation after 28 days product S – methyl fenitrothion and O,O S triethyl ester, malathion product isomalathion. This According to the chemical structure of malathion and metabolism, two pathway are proposed for malathion photodegradation Figure (1). In the first proposed pathway, the sulphur atom in the $\text{P}=\text{S}$ bond of malathion will be oxidized into $\text{P}=\text{O}$ by the ROS attack, such as OH radicals, which leads to the formation of isomalathion. The formation of oxidized derivatives has been documented in the photocatalytic degradation of organophosphorus pesticides containing $\text{P}=\text{S}$ group (Kraljet *et al.*, 2007 and Liu *et al.*,

2015). In the second proposed pathway, the sulphur atom in $\text{P}-\text{S}$ or $\text{S}-\text{C}$ bond could be attacked by positive holes to generate sulfide cation radicals initiate the degradation reaction. Under the sun light, photocatalytic reaction may produce a single electron from the sulfur atom, then initiate $\text{P}-\text{S}$ or $\text{S}-\text{C}$ cleavage. The cleavage of $\text{P}-\text{S}$ bond forms $\text{SCH}_2\text{CONHCH}_3$ radicals and the cleavage of $\text{C}-\text{S}$ bond forms $(\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2\text{SPS}$ radicals, $\text{SCH}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{NHCH}$ Radicals are easier dimerize and led to the formation of 1,2 Bis (Acetyl-N-methyl methane disulfide (Vidal *et al.*, 1999). Similarly, $(\text{CH}_2\text{O})_2\text{SOS}$. Radicals tend to combine with methyl radical (CH_3) to form the reaction mesia O, O, S trimethyl thiophosphorothioate will be generated after oxidization and successively mineralized SO_4 , PO_4 , CO_2 and H_2O

Table (7): The degradation product on Fenitrothion and malathion By GC/Ms.

Pesticides	RT Before	RT After	Compound product after storage 54 C.
Fenitrothion	-----	5.30	Dimethyl benzene
	-----	5.90	1,3 dimethyl
	-----	7.52	Methyl Parathion
	-----	7.97	CarboMethyl Fenitrothion
	-----	8.22	3-methyl 4-nitrophenol
	-----	10.23	S- methyl Fenitrothion*
	24.81	24.81	Fenitrothion
Malathion	-----	5.20	Ethyl benzene
	-----	5.91	Dimethyl benzene
	-----	12.11	O,O S triethyl ester *
	-----	12.23	Isomalathion*
	25.24	25.24	Malathion
	-----	<u>26.26</u>	O,s dimethyl phosphorodith

*Impurities.

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Seasonal abundance of the fig wax scale insect *Ceroplastes rusci* (Hemiptera: Coccidae) on medicinal plant *Withania somnifera* in Beni-Suef Governorate, Egypt

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 14 / 7 / 2020

Accepted: 16 / 9 / 2020

Keywords

Ceroplastes rusci,
medicinal plant,
Withania somnifera,
parasitoids, population
fluctuations and Egypt.

Abstract:

The present study dealt with the population fluctuations of *Ceroplastes rusci* (L.) (Hemiptera: Coccidae) during two successive seasons (2016-2017) and (2017-2018), on *Withania somnifera* (L.) (Ashwagandha) at Beba district, Beni-Suef Governorate. The obtained data showed that *C. rusci* had four annual peaks on *W. somnifera* in the two successive years of the study. These peaks were recorded during (May, August, October and December) and (May, August, October and January) in the first and second years, respectively. The relationship between the meteorological factors and the total population of the pest was studied in this investigation. During this work was recorded 6 parasitoids and one hyperparasitoid. These are *Habrolebis* sp., *Metaphycus helvolus* (Compere), *M. zebratus* Mercet and *Microterys nietneri* (Motschulsky) (Hymenoptera: Encyrtidae) ; *Scutellista caerulea* (Fonscolombe) (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae); *Tetrastichus ceroplastae* (Girault) (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) and hyperparasitoid, *Marietta leopardina* Motschulsky (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae). Also, the rate of parasitism of these parasitoids was studied.

Introduction

Withania somnifera (L.) (WS) (Ashwagandha), belonging to family Solanaceae, is a wild herb had many common names like Indian winter cherry and Indian ginseng that has been traditionally known since ancient times in India for its numerous beneficial health activities. WS is one of the most important herbs in Ayurveda, India which has been used for >3000 years in stress management, energy elevating and improving cognitive health and to lower inflammation blood sugar levels, cortisol, anxiety, and depression. The

plant is an erect, grayish, evergreen shrub with long tuberous roots, short stems, ovate and petiolate leaves, and greenish axillary and bisexual flowers. The leaves, roots, stems and flowers bear medicinal values with 29 common metabolites derived from the leaves and root extracts. Till now, this medicinal plant has been found to have anti-epileptic, anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritic, anti-depressant, anti-coagulant, antioxidant, anti-diabetic, anti-pyretic efficiencies along with palliative effects such as analgesic,

rejuvenating, regenerating and growth-promoting effects. Leaf extract showed that the highest activity against liver and breast cancer (Dutta *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, Mahrous *et al.* (2017) recorded that this plant is a common plant in Egypt. The extracts of different parts of the plant in the protection against oxidative stress and its therapeutic potential in the treatment of Alzheimer's.

Significant anticholinesterase activity, with the highest activity produced by the ripe fruit extract, significant nitric oxide scavenging activity, strong haemolysis protection as well as strong antioxidant activity. Unlike the Indian plant that is reputed for the medicinal use of its roots, both the fruits and leaves of Egyptian plant have promising activities. Withanolides isolated from its leaves extract, could be regarded as an interesting drug candidate for treatment of Alzheimer's. Nassra *et al.* (2017) recorded that WS is a well reputed plant in India as a multi-purpose medicinal agent and is well cherished for the cytotoxic activity of its extracts and isolates.

The fig wax scale (FWS), *Ceroplastes rusci* L. (Hemiptera: Coccidae), is one of the common scale insect species in Jordan (Mustafa-Al-Antary and Sharaf, 1994). In addition, La Notte *et al.* (1997) demonstrated that some species of wax are virus disease vectors, for example *C. rusci* is known to carry plant viruses. Also, Morsi and Mousa (2004) recorded that this scale insect had 2-3 annual peaks of abundance on leaves of guava in Beni-Suef Governorate. The natural enemies of FWS as the most important factor controlling the occurrence and severity of infection. Talhouk (1969) recorded the presence of three natural enemies from Jordan. These are: *Scutellista caerulea* (Fonscolombe) (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae), *Tetrastichus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) and

Coccidophaga scitula (Rambur) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae).

The aim of this research work is to provide further significant ecological data to enhance the integrated management of this scale pest in Egypt. Phenological details such as the number of generations and the population peaks give useful information about the time of applying insecticides or releasing a biocontrol agent.

Materials and methods

1. Seasonal abundance of the fig wax scale insect *Ceroplastes rusci*:

It was carried out for 2 years, (March, 2016 till February, 2018) at Beba District, Beni-Suef Governorate, Egypt. An orchard about one Fadden in area, cultivated with the fig trees, *Ficus carica* L. and heavily infested with the fig wax scale, *C. rusci* was chosen for this study. The orchard was not exposed to any chemical treatment during three years prior to the present study and during the investigation period. Every 15 day-intervals hundred leaves with different stages of the scale *C. rusci* were collected at random from the different directions of WS. The leaves represented the different sides, peripheral, inner zones, lower and middle strata of the tree. These leaves were kept in a paper bag and transferred to the laboratory for examination and counting the scale insects. The stages of scale insect considered in counting process were: 1. Nymphal instars. 2. Adult females (Virgin and gravid).

2. Survey of natural enemies:

A survey of the fig wax scale insect *C. rusci* parasitoids was carried out in Beni-Suef Governorate throughout two successive years, from March, 2016 till February, 2018. Samples of infested leaves and branches with WS. The samples were 30 branches (20 cm/ branch). They were packed in paper bags and transferred to the laboratory for examination. The parasitoids species

were identified in Biological Control Res. Dept. Plant Prot. Res. Institute, Agric. Res. Center. The examined leaves were enclosed in plastic jars of 15 cm. diameter and 20 cm height covered with muslin held in position by a rubber band and kept under preferential conditions for securing any emergence of parasitoids. The parasitoids were collected, sorted into species and preserved in vials contain 70 % ethyl alcohol and glycerin, in addition to slide mounting species for identification.

3. Abundance of the parasitoids associated with the fig wax scale insect *Ceroplastes rusci*:

WS leaves infested with nymphs and adult females, (Virgin and gravid females) of *C. rusci* were half monthly, (100 scale insects/15 days) from March, 2016 to February , 2018 . Each leaf was stored in well-ventilated glass emergence tube for its parasitoids emergence that their numbers were recorded daily and their percentages were calculated.

4. Percentage of parasitism:

The rates of parasitism in different stages of *C. rusci* infesting WS were estimated throughout two successive years of study from the beginning of March, 2016 to the end of February, 2018. Samples 100 randomly selected scales were chosen. These samples represented nymphal instars, the newly developed adult females, the full-grown adult females. This sample divided into 4 replicates with 25 scales. Each scale was removed, transferred and mulched on a slide in a water film. Scales in each sample were dissected under a binocular microscope and classified as follows:

Live unparasitized, parasitized scale insects having (Parasitic larvae, pupal parasitoids and emergence holes). The total percentage of parasitism of the fig scale insect was estimated from

data obtained throughout the two years 2016-2018 according to:

$$R = \frac{\text{Total population of the parasitoid}}{\text{Total population of the scale insect} + \text{Total population of the parasitoid}} \times 100$$

5. Effect of biotic and abiotic factors on the abundance of *Ceroplastes rusci*:

Weather factors as maximum, minimum temperature and relative humidity were considered from Central Laboratory for Agricultural Climate. The weekly maximum and minimum temperatures as well as relative humidity were calculated and total number of parasitism. Multiple regressions were conducted for weather factors combined as well as plant age as described. The obtained determination factor (R^2) of E.V. % was used to explain the effect of testing factors. Process Correlation and Regression were used in SAS to analysis the obtained data (SAS Institute, 1998).

Results and discussion

1. Seasonal abundance of the fig wax scale insect *Ceroplastes rusci*:

Data presented in, (Figures 1 and 2) illustrated that nymphs, adult females and gravid females stages curves had four peaks during the first year, (2016-2017) and four peaks during the second year, (2017-2018) on WS leaves. In the first year, (2016-2017) the peaks of nymphs recorded on (25th of April, 10th of August, 25th of October and 10th of December) with 390,520 ,479 and 295(nymph/30 branches), respectively. The peaks of adult females recorded on (The 10th of May, 25th of August, 25th of November and 25th of January 2017 with 273, 228, 227 and 91 individuals/30 branches), respectively. The peaks of gravid females recorded on (The 10th of May, 25th of August, 25th of November and 25th of January 2017 with 183,187,177 and 68 individuals/30 branches), respectively. The peaks of total

population of insects recorded on (10th of May, 10th of August, 25th of October and 25th of January 2016) with 817 ,905 ,875 ,392 individuals/30 branches), respectively. In the second year, (2017-2018) the peaks of nymphs recorded on (the 10th of May, 10th of August, 1st of October and 25th of December) with 343, 536, 469 and 319 (nymph/30 branches), respectively. The peaks of adult females recorded on (the 25th of May, 25th of August, 25th November and 25th of January 2018 with 270, 234, 226

and 95 individuals/30 branches), respectively. The peaks of gravid females recorded on (the 25th of May, 25th of August, 25th of October and 25th of January 2018 with 179, 192 ,177 and 71 individuals/30 branches), respectively. The peaks of total population of insects recorded on (the 25th of May, 10th of August, 25th of October and 10th of January 2018 with 781, 934, 836 and 420 individuals/30 branches), respectively.

Figure (1): Seasonal abundance of *Ceroplastes rusci* population in response to max., min. temperatures and relative humidity, on *Withania somnifera* branches at Beba district, Beni-Suef Governorate during 2016-2017.

Figure (2): Seasonal abundance of *Ceroplastes rusci* population in response to max., min. temperatures and relative humidity on *Withania somnifera* branches at Beba district, Beni-Suef Governorate during 2017-2018.

2. Age structure:

The results of using the age structure technique to be obtained from seasonal data of *C. rusci* along the two years of investigation on WS were graphically illustrated in Figure 3 (A and B). *C. rusci* had four generations in the first year, the highest generation started from end March to 1st June.

Ozsemerci and Askit (2003) observed that this scale had 2 generations / year on fig trees in Aydn province (Turkey). Although Oueed *et al.*, 2007 found that *C. rusci* had 3 generations / year on fig trees in North of Iraq. Biche *et al.* (2012) demonstrated that *C. rusci* had 2 generations autumnal and spring in the area of Medea (Algeria).

(B)
Figure (3): Age structure of *Ceroplastes rusci* on *Withania somnifera* branches 2016 (A) and 2017(B).

1. Survey of natural enemies:

During the present study was recorded 6 parasitoids and one hyperparasitoid. These are:

Family: Encyrtidae.

Habrolebis sp., *Metaphycus helvolus* (Compere), *M. zebratus* Mercet and *Microterys nieteri* (Motschulsky)

Family: Pteromalidae.

Scutellista caerulea (Fonscolombe)

Family: Eulophidae.

Tetrastichus ceroplastae (Girault)

Hyperparasitoid:

Family: Aphelinidae.

Marietta leopardina Motschulsky

Agyriou and Santorini (1980) surveyed the parasitoids of *C. rusci* on fig trees in Greece. They recorded these parasitoids,

Scutellista cyanea Motsch, *Eublemma scitulum* (Ramb.),

Coccophagus lycimina (Wlk.), *Paracera procerusitalicus* (Masi) and *T. ceroplastae*. Morsi and Mousa (2004) recorded that parasitoids of fig wax scale *C. rusci* on guava leaves in Beni-Suef Governorate, Egypt. These are, *M. helvolus*, *M.zebratus*, *Habrolepis* sp., *S. caerulea*, *M.nietneri*, *Microtyres* sp., *T. ceroplastae*. Awamleh *et al.* (2009) stated that parasitoids of the fig wax scale *C. rusci* in Jordan are: *M. helvolus*, *M. zebratus*, *S. cyanea* and *T. ceroplastae*.

4. Abundance of the parasitoid *Tetrastichus ceroplastae* attacking fig wax scale insect *Ceroplastes rusci*:

The parasitoid *T. ceroplastae* is an effective parasitoid which keeps populations of the wax scale under

control in Egypt. In the first year, 2016 there were four peaks of parasitism could be observed and three peaks in the second year. The highest peak was observed in 10th of August in two years. The highest rate of parasitism was 4.64 % in August in the first year 2016. While in the second year was 5% in 25th of April 2017 (Figure 4). These results are agreement with Morsi and Mousa (2004), the authors, Talhouk,1969; Ozsemerci and Aksit, 2003 and Hammad, 2006 also supported the same findings. They also, reported the highest parasitism was observed in month of March in both the year. Awamaleh *et al.* (2009) has also observed *T. ceroplastae* as a dominant parasitoid of *C. rusci*.

Figure (4). Total population and % parasitism of the parasitoid *Tetrastichus ceroplastae* associated with *Ceroplastes rusci* on *Withania somnifera* at Beba district, Beni-Suef Governorate during the two years.

5. Effect of biotic and abiotic factors on the abundance of *Ceroplastes rusci*:

We studied the effect of a biotic factor as parasitoids and abiotic factors maximum, minimum temperature and relative humidity. Correlation, regression analysis and multi regression between biotic and abiotic factors and population of *C. rusci* was in liner degree, in two years of study 2016/2017and 2017/2018. Statistically, the results represented in Tables (1 and 2) showed the effect of the weather

factors (maximum, minimum temperature and relative humidity) activity of *C. rusci*. With the respect to abiotic factors had significant effect on the population of the nymph stage *C. rusci* in the two years of study, while adult had significant effect on the population with maximum temperature in the wo years of study 2016/2017and 2017/2018 (Tables 1 and 2).

The combined effect of temperature and relative humidity was responsible for 73.94 % and 69.78 % of the nymph stage, adult females was

(60.84 % and 51.99 %), gravid females was (66.93 % and 52.62%) and total populations was (73.48 % and 69.15%) during the first and second seasons, respectively (Tables 1 and 2). To evaluate the common effect of biotic and abiotic factors was responsible for

89.22 % and 84.71 % of the nymph stage, adult females was (82.25 % and 79.06 %), gravid females was (81.62 % and 74.56%) and total populations was (93.73 % and 94.26%) during the first and second seasons, respectively (Tables 1 and 2).

Table (1): The simple correlation and regression coefficients and multiple regressions between the different stages of *Ceroplastes rusci* on *Withania somnifera* in Beba district, Beni-Suef Governorate, Egypt first year 2016/2017.

Factor		Simple correlation and regression			Multiple regression		
		R	B	P	F	P	E.V.%
Nymph	T. Max.	0.69	8.10	0.0002	18.91	<.0001	73.94
	T. min.	0.75	10.45	<.0001			
	RH.%	-0.36	-2.28	0.0870			
	Parasitoid	0.846	8.23	<.0001			
	All above				39.33	<.0001	89.22
Adult	T. Max.	0.76	5.85	<.0001	10.36	0.0003	60.84
	T. Min.	0.78	7.09	<.0001			
	RH.%	-0.62	-2.61	0.0011			
	Parasitoid	0.85	5.38	<.0001			
	All above				22.02	<.0001	82.25
Gravid	T. Max.	0.78	4.82	<.0001	13.49	<.0001	66.93
	T. Min.	0.79	5.82	<.0001			
	RH.%	-0.66	-2.22	0.0005			
	Parasitoid	0.79	4.08	<.0001			
	All above				21.10	<.0001	81.62
Total	T. Max.	0.80	18.77	<.0001	18.47	<.0001	73.48
	T. Min.	0.84	23.41	<.0001			
	RH.%	-0.56	-7.14	0.0045			
	Parasitoid	0.91	17.68	<.0001			
	All above				71.06	<.0001	93.73

T. Max.: Maximum temperature. T.Min.: Minimum temperature. RH.% : Relative humidity percentage.

Table (2): The simple correlation and regression coefficients and multiple regressions between the different stages of *Ceroplastes rusci* on *Withania somnifera* in Beba district, Beni-Suef Governorate, Egypt second year 2017/2018.

Factor		Simple correlation and regression			Multiple regression		
		R	B	P	F	P	E.V.%
Nymph	T. Max.	0.66	8.41	<.0001	15.39	<.0001	69.78
	T. Min.	0.75	11.06	<.0004			
	RH.%	-0.61	-2.79	<.0001			
	Parasitoid	0.79	8.66	<.0001			
	All above				26.32	<.0001	84.71
Adult	T. Max.	0.72	5.74	<.0001	7.22	0.0018	51.99
	T. Min.	0.72	6.68	<.0001			
	RH.%	-0.62	-2.92	0.0015			
	Parasitoid	0.80	5.79	<.0001			
	All above				17.94	<.0001	79.06
Gravid	T. Max.	0.72	4.72	<.0001	7.40	0.0016	52.62
	T. Min.	0.72	5.47	<.0001			
	RH.%	-0.63	-2.44	0.0011			
	Parasitoid	0.80	4.50	<.0001			
	All above				13.92	<.0001	74.56
Total	T. Max.	0.78	18.83	<.0001	14.94	<.0001	69.15
	T. Min.	0.82	23.16	<.0001			
	RH.%	-0.56	-8.13	0.0043			
	Parasitoid	0.90	18.95	<.0001			
	All above				78.00	<.0001	94.26

T. Max.: Maximum temperature. T.Min.: Minimum temperature. RH.% : Relative humidity percentage.

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Non-traditional approaches against spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) infesting cotton in Egypt

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 7/ 7/2020

Accepted: 12/8/2020

Keywords

Earias insulana.

Chrysoperla

carnea,

azdirachtin,

emamectin

benzoate, spinosad,

Bacillus

thuringiensis and

Beauveria

bassiana.

Abstract:

The spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is a major insect pest of cotton in Egypt. The present field study was carried out to evaluate the influence of nine treatments against *E. insulana* during two successive seasons 2018 and 2019. Agricultural practices including the 1st and 2nd treatments; plowing, irrigation and fertilization that showed a low percent of infestation reduction, while 3rd treatment including the bio-rational insecticides of (Azdirachtin, emamectin benzoate, spinosad) showed a reasonable infestation reduction, moreover, the 4th treatment was the release of the predator *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) alone achieved good results compared to the previous treatments, while, the 5th treatment was *Bacillus thuringiensis* and the 6th treatment was *Beauveria bassiana*, the 5th and 6th treatments were the least in infestation reduction when applied alone. However, the 7th, 8th and 9th treatments represent the three different combined treatments resulted in very good infestation reduction and were more effective during the two successive seasons of study 2018 and 2019. Combined treatments increased the infestation reduction and were of great value and should be applied to the promising ones only. This research paper may greatly improve the current knowledge and practices for sustainable development, ecology and environmental protections.

Introduction

The genus *Earias* has an extremely wide range through cotton-growing countries and is found to be distributed among most African countries, the Mediterranean basin, India, China, and Southeastern Asia (Reed, 1994). Due to its severity of infestation and type of damage, spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)

was recorded as a major pest and caused most serious cotton damage. Larvae attack and damage squares, flowers and cotton bolls; consuming seeds, destroying them with accumulation of feces which serve as a suitable media for secondary pests and fungus, larvae can destroy all the cotton bolls in the field resulting in yield losses (Van Hamburg and Guest,

1997; Hanumantharaya *et al.*, 2008; Ahmed *et al.*, 2012; Pappas *et al.*, 2011 and Bennett, 2015). There are many ways to reduce *E. insulana* infestation like cultivation of the resistance cotton varieties (Moustafa *et al.*, 2015).

The green lacewing *Chrysoperla carnea* (Stephens) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) is an important natural predator of many insect species attacking different crops. Chrysopids are generalist predators that recognized to be a voracious feeder on arthropod pests such as; aphids, whiteflies, eggs and larvae of cotton bollworms (Senior and McEwen, 2001; Atlihan *et al.*, 2004; Zia *et al.*, 2008 and Soomro *et al.*, 2020). In addition, Bhatti *et al.* (2007) reported that *C. carnea*, cause reasonable reduction in bollworms population.

The importance of bio-insecticides as alternative management methods is environmentally friendly and can help in natural balance. Such alternative bio-insecticides as, emamectin benzoate is a semisynthetic avermectin insecticide derived from the fermentation product avermectin B1 and it works as a chloride channel activator by binding gamma aminobutyric acid (GABA) receptor and glutamate-gated chloride channels disrupting nerve signals within arthropods (Grant, 2002). Spinosad is derived from a naturally occurring soil actinomycete bacterium, *Saccharopolyspora spinosa* (Thompson *et al.*, 1997) binding target sites on nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs) of the insect nervous system then cause disruption of acetylcholine neurotransmission (Qiao *et al.*, 2007).

Bacillus thuringiensis (*Bt.*) depends on endotoxin activity through the larval midgut which in turn affects the permeability of the epithelial cells and hence causing intoxication of

the larval hemolymph. Entomopathogenic fungus spores contact with the insect host body then germinate, penetrate the cuticle, and grow inside, killing the insect within a few days. Several species of entomopathogenic fungi produced commercially and used as biological control agents against many insect pests in many parts of the world as *Beauveria bassiana* isolates (Sevim *et al.*, 2015). The spores are sprayed on affected crops as an emulsified suspension or wettable powder. And, bio-insecticides like spinosad, emamectin benzoate and entomopathogenic fungi have less harmful effect on *C. carnea* (Moustafa, 2016a and Moustafa *et al.*, 2019). Also, application of plants extracts considered one of the best control measures because of their less toxicity against non-target organisms and their biodegradability (Singh *et al.*, 2001). Yousef and Moustafa (2013) found that *Melia azedarach* oil proved promising results against *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Among the plants with insecticidal activities, *Azadirachta indica* is the most promising, its natural compound, azadirachtin has been known to possess insecticidal properties for several years and it is active against nearly 550 insect species (Anuradha and Annadurai, 2008) and acts as antifeedant and repellent (Chaudhary *et al.*, 2017).

In this study, field application by using non-traditional and environmentally safe treatments such as azadirachtin, emamectin benzoate and spinosad, as well as, introducing the predator *C. carnea* as a biological control agent were used for spiny bollworm *E. insulana* management.

Materials and methods

Trials were conducted at Qaha experimental station, Qalyoubia Governorate, an area about 1400 m²

was cultivated with Giza 86 cotton variety at March 31st, 2018 and March 13th, 2019 seasons without chemical receive to evaluate the effect of all treatments on the population density of spiny bollworm infesting cotton plants. The trial was designed as randomized complete blocks, nine plots were designed for the treatments' application and one plot was left without treatments as a control (check), by three replicates for each plot.

1. Agricultural practices:

Prior to cultivation the soil was plowed using farming plow machine. Seeds are typically planted an inch below the soil surface, plowing give those seeds the best chance for growing and germination. Plowing breaks up the blocky structure of the soil which can aid in drainage and root growth. As cotton plants suffer drought during spring and summer months, therefore, plants of this treatment were irrigated during April, May, July and August each season, the commercial fertilizer (NPK), nitrogen: phosphorus: potassium at the rate of 20:10:10, these agricultural treatments were done free of insecticides application. Fertilization treatment was applied as follow; nitrogen at April, while, phosphate was applied after plowing and potassium at June.

2. Data of commercial formulation insecticides used:

2.1. Bio-rational insecticides treatments:

Recommended concentration of the bio-rational insecticides used as follow; Oikos 3.2% EC (Azadirachtin) obtained from Lutus company by rate of application 100cm/100Litre water, exellent 1.9% EC (Emamectin benzoate) obtained from Kafr El-Ziat for Pesticides and Chemicals by rate of application 300cm/feddan, and spintor 24% SC (Spinosad) obtained from Daw Chemicals Company by rate of application 50cm/feddan were locally

sprayed alternatively two weeks interval between sprays.

2.2. Microbiological treatments:

2.2.1. Bacterial treatment:

Zentari 54% DF (*B. thuringiensis*, subsp. Aizawai, Strain ABTS-1857) obtained from Shoura for Chemicals Company by rate of application 200gm/feddan was locally sprayed on the stem, branches, twigs and the whole vegetative system.

2.2.2. Fungal treatment:

Bio-Power 1.15% WP (*Beauveria bassiana*, 1 x 10⁸ spores i.e., CFU/g) obtained from Gaara Company at the rate of 1.5 kg/feddan were sprayed on stem, branches, twigs and the whole vegetative system.

3. Spraying for each treatment was conducted three times by two weeks interval between each spray. Treatment spraying was practiced by a knapsack sprayer Cifarili and mainly directed towards the vegetative system.

4. Release of *Chrysoperla carnea*:

The predator was obtained from the Center of Bio-Organic Agricultural Services (CBAS) in Aswan. Release of *C. carnea* 2nd instar larvae in the ratio of 250 larvae/200 m², they were simply sparse over the pest infested cotton plants was implemented three times at fourteen days intervals.

5. Combined treatments:

Three combinations of simultaneous treatments were applied. These include bio-rational insecticides spray and predator release, the second and third combined treatments were bio-rational insecticides spray, predator release and microbiological treatments. Check plants were left untreated for control. Insecticides were sprayed and predator release, with an interval of fourteen days. Dates of bio-rational insecticides and microbiological treatments application as following; the 1st, 2nd and 3rd spray were applied at June 25th, July 9th and July 25th during season 2018, whereas, they were July

1st, July 15th and July 30th 2019. Moreover, the three predator releases dates were as follow; July 2nd, July 16th and July 30th during season 2018, while, they were July 8th, July 22nd and August 6th during season 2019. However, dates of spray the three combined treatments were as following; the 1st combined treatment sprayed at June 25th, July 9th and July 25th during season 2018 and July 1st, July 15th and July 30th 2019 and predator released between them at July 2nd, July 16th and July 30th season 2018, while, they were July 8th, July 22nd and August 6th during season 2019. The 2nd and 3rd combined treatments sprayed at June 25th, July 9th, July 25th and August 1st during season 2018 and July 1st, July 15th, July 30th and August 6th during season 2019 and predator released between them.

To evaluate the effect of the nine treatments against spiny bollworm, samples of 50 bolls/plot were randomly picked weekly before and after each treatment until harvest. Check plants were left untreated for control. The collected bolls were carefully dissected, and number of exit holes was recorded. Percentage of larval infestation reduction in green boll was estimated according to **Henderson and Tilton (1955)**.

6. Statistical analysis:

The recorded data were statistically analyzed with CoStat program software [one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) (P <0.05%) Duncan's multiple range test of means (Duncan, 1955)].

Results and discussion

Data given in Tables (1 and 2) showed that the infestation reduction of nine treatments during the two successive seasons 2018 and 2019 as following:

1. Agriculture treatments:

1.1. Effect of plowing treatment alone:

The infestation reduction with *E. insulana* due to this treatment was low, it was 2.0, 3.5, and 2.0% during 2018 (Table 1) and was 4.5, 3.0 and 2.5% during 2019 for the infested squares, flowers and bolls, respectively (Table 2).

1.2. Effect of irrigation and fertilization treatment:

Slight degree of *E. insulana* infestation reduction was achieved when irrigation and fertilization treatments were applied together. The reduction percentages of the pest infestation reached 5.0, 8.0 and 6.5% during 2018 season and 9.5, 7.0 and 6.6% for squares, flowers and bolls during 2019 season, respectively.

2. Effect of bio-rational insecticides spray:

2.1. Alternative spray of azadirachtin, emamectin benzoate and spinosad:

Remarkable degree *E. insulana* infestation reduction was noticed (Table 1) when the alternative three applications of azadirachtin, emamectin benzoate and spinosad spray were applied. Insignificant infestation reduction percentages of *E. insulana* were 71.75 and 76.77% for squares and flowers, respectively and but significant reduction was 78.72% for bolls during 2018 season. During 2019 season, application of three alternative bio-rational insecticides sprays; azadirachtin, emamectin benzoate and spinosad resulted in significant grand infestation reduction by 73.98 and 81.32% for squares and bolls, respectively and significant reduction in flowers by 78.07% (Table 2).

Table (1): Effect of different treatments on reduction percentages of infestation by spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* larvae during season 2018.

Treatments	2018 season					
	Squares		Flowers		Bolls	
	Mean No. of infested squares	% Reduction	Mean No. of infested flowers	% Reduction	Mean No. of infested bolls	% Reduction
1.Agricultural treatments:						
1.1. Plowing treatment	19.8	2.0% ^c	22.9	3.5% ^b	17.2	2.0% ^c
1.2. Irrigation and fertilization treatment:	16	5.0% ^c	17.1	8.0% ^b	21.05	6.5% ^c
2.Bio-rational insecticides spray:						
2.1. Alternative spray of azadirachtin, emamectin benzoate and spinosad.	7.9	71.75% ^b	6.5	76.77% ^a	8.33	78.72% ^b
3. Predator release:						
3.1. <i>Chrysoperla carnea</i> release.	2.4	66.48% ^b	3.2	72.92% ^a	10.17	75.77% ^b
4. Microbiological treatment:						
4.1. Bacterial treatment: <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	7.3	11.70% ^c	6.5	9.18% ^b	14.5	12.35% ^c
4.2. Fungal treatment: <i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	12	8.60% ^c	10.3	10.50% ^b	8.2	11.60% ^c
5.Combined treatments						
5.1. Treatment 2.1. +3.1.	18	86.55% ^a	16.5	79.71% ^a	22.5	81.00% ^a
5.2. Treatment 2.1. +3.1. +4.1.	3.9	88.20% ^a	3.5	81.50% ^a	3.2	83.63% ^a
5.3. Treatment 2.1. +3.1. +4.2.	5.4	87.00% ^a	4.1	79.90% ^a	6.3	84.60% ^a
Untreated (Check)	24.83	----	27.08	----	31.58	----
LSD		14.18		13.62		13.69
F		76.81		65.16		36.56
P-value		.0000***		.0000***		.0000***

Values within the same column followed by the same letters are not significant different (ANOVA, Duncan's multiple range tests, $P < 0.05$).

3. Effect of predator release:

3.1. Release of *Chrysoperla carnea*:

Releasing three times of *C. carnea* 2nd instar larvae showed insignificant reduction in the squares and flowers by 66.48 and 72.92% but significant reduction in bolls infestation caused by *E. insulana* by 75.77%, respectively, during season

2018 (Table 1). *C. carnea* 2nd instar larvae release showed significant general infestation reduction for the three release in flowers by 82.76% but insignificant general reduction in squares and bolls reached 70.88 and 78.28%, respectively during season 2019 (Table 2).

Table (2): Effect of different treatments on infestation reduction percentages of by spiny bollworm *Earias insulana* larvae during season 2019.

Treatments	2019 season					
	Squares		Flowers		Bolls	
	Mean No. of infested squares	% Reduction	Mean No. of infested flowers	% Reduction	Mean No. of infested bolls	% Reduction
1. Agricultural treatments						
1.1. Plowing treatment	6	4.5% ^c	16	3.0% ^c	21	2.5% ^d
1.2. Irrigation and fertilization treatment	7.9	9.5% ^c	18	7.0% ^c	17	6.6% ^d
2. Bio-rational insecticides spray:						
2.1. Alternative spray of azadirachtin, emamectin benzoate and spinosad	3.3	73.98% ^b	4.2	78.07% ^b	5.67	81.32% ^b
3. Predator release						
3.1. <i>Chrysoperla carnea</i> release	2	70.88% ^b	2.5	82.76% ^a	6.75	78.28% ^b
4. Microbiological treatment						
4.1. Bacterial treatment: <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	8	9.43% ^c	11	8.43% ^c	10	13.33% ^c
4.2. Fungal treatment: <i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	11	10.14% ^c	8.5	13.55% ^c	17.5	14.10% ^c
5. Combined treatments						
5.1. Treatment 2.1. +3.1.	7	88.06% ^a	15.5	82.73% ^a	19	86.00% ^a
5.2. Treatment 2.1. +3.1. +4.1.	2.9	87.90% ^a	3	88.00% ^a	6.2	90.54% ^a
5.3. Treatment 2.1. +3.1. +4.2.	1.9	81.00% ^{ab}	1.1	84.60% ^a	2.1	87.00% ^a
Untreated (Check)	11.3	---	21.97	---	26.75	---
LSD		11.67		15.17		11.15
F		95.70		40.56		111.39
P-value		.0000***		.0000***		.0000***

Values within the same column followed by the same letters are not significant different (ANOVA, Duncan's multiple range tests, $P < 0.05$).

4. Effect of microbiological treatments:

4.1. Effect of *Bacillus thuringiensis* treatment:

Results in Table (1) showed that after three sprays of *B. thuringiensis* treatment; non-significant general infestation reduction percentage of *E. insulana* was as following; 11.70, 9.18 and 12.35% in squares, flowers and bolls, respectively, during season 2018. Results in Table (2) showed non-significant general infestation reduction caused by *E. insulana* after the three sprays of bacterial treatment was as following; 9.43, 8.43 and 13.33% in squares, flowers and bolls, respectively, during season 2019.

4.2. Effect of *Beauveria bassiana* treatment:

Results in Table (1) showed that after three sprays of *B. bassiana*; non-significant general reduction percentages of *E. insulana* infestation was 8.60, 10.50 and 11.6% in squares, flowers and bolls, respectively, during season 2018. Moreover, results in Table (2) showed that the general reduction of the three sprays of fungal treatment was 10.14, 13.55 and 14.10% in squares, flowers and bolls, respectively, during season 2019.

5. Effect of combined treatments:

5.1. Effect of alternative spray of azadirachtin, emamectin benzoate and spinosad and *Chrysoperla carnea* release:

This treatment showed good results by 86.55, 79.71, 81.00% infestation reduction on squares, flowers and bolls respectively non-significantly during 2018 season (Table 1), on the other hand, the same combined treatments gave 88.06, 82.73 and 86.00% infestation reduction on squares, flowers and bolls, respectively, during 2019 season (Table 2).

5.2. Effect of alternative spray of azadirachtin, emamectin benzoate and spinosad and *Chrysoperla carnea* release and bacterial treatment:

Satisfied results were obtained from this treatment during 2018 season by 88.2, 81.50 and 83.63% infestation reduction non-significantly on squares, flowers and bolls, respectively (Table 1), while, it was 87.9, 88.00 and 90.54% infestation reduction on squares, flowers and bolls, respectively, during 2019 season (Table 2).

5.3. Effect of alternative spray of azadirachtin, emamectin benzoate and spinosad and *Chrysoperla carnea* release and fungal treatment:

This treatment showed very good results 87.00, 79.90 and 84.60% infestation reduction non-significant during 2018 season (Table 1) and 81.00, 84.60 and 87.00% on squares, flowers and bolls, respectively, during 2019 season (Table 2). Results of this study revealed that combined treatments were more effective against *E. insulana* infestation during the two successive years of study. Such observations were supported by Mirmoayedi *et al.* (2010), they applied botanical and bio-control methods to manage bollworms, and they evaluated the more efficient insecticide between three bio-insecticides in a chemical control of spiny bollworm. Spinosad had the lowest number of damaged bolls and had the minimum number of blind damaged bolls, followed by neem-azal and *Bt*. Similarly, Moustafa (2016

b) showed that *E. insulana* larvae was more susceptible to the toxicity of *M. azedarach* than *P. gossypiella* larvae after 2, 5 and 7-days post laboratory treatments. Moreover, AgNPs from *O. marjorana* plant leaf extract showed promising toxicity against *E. insulana* (Al Shater *et al.*, 2020). And, Nboyine *et al.* (2013) assessed field efficacy of neem-based bio-pesticides, obtained results showed that neem reduced the abundance of bollworms. Alkaloids and hydrocarbon of the pepper oil substances exhibited latent effect against the newly hatched larvae of spiny bollworm (El –Mesallamy *et al.*, 2015). Venugopal *et al.* (2017) showed somehow similar results when they applied *Beauveria bassiana* on cotton crop (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) against pink bollworm *P. gossypiella* they found that *B. bassiana* may be useful in devising proper integrated pest management strategy against pink bollworm.

Regarding, predator release, many reports agreed with the obtained data such as Salman *et al.* (2014) found that biological control treatments of releasing *C. carnea* decreased significantly the population of spiny bollworm *E. insulana*. Concerning combined treatments Mansoor *et al.* (2007) showed that integration of bio-control agents such as *C. carnea* with insecticides was effective as chemical control using recommended insecticides against spotted bollworms. Also, Hanumantharaya *et al.* (2008) used combined treatments of fertilizers, bio-control agent and botanicals to manage the insect pests on cotton, two sprays of neem seed kernel extract (5%) on cotton and release of *C. carnea* reduced *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hub.) eggs and larval population and increased the seed cotton yield. Similarly, Sree *et al.* (2019) found that five combined treatments of fertilization and bio-control agents cause high reduction in

insect population of okra. Combined treatments based on azadirachtin and *B. thuringiensis* or azadirachtin and *B. bassiana* improved the efficacy of controlling *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) (Jallow *et al.*, 2019).

It could be concluded that, from the foregoing results that combined treatments were more effective against *E. insulana* during the two successive years of study than any treatment alone. It was noticed that combined treatments increased the infestation reduction and were of great value and should be applied to the promising ones only. Although microbiological treatments were mostly ineffective during 2018 and 2019, respectively. Statistical analysis and grouping of nine treatments applied for two successive seasons 2018 and 2019, clarified that there was significance difference between treatments.

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First record of the cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (Hemiptera: Coccoidea: Pseudococcidae) as a novel pest on new host plants in Alexandria, Egypt

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received:12/7 /2020

Accepted:3 /9 /2020

Keywords

Mealybug,

Phenacoccus

solenopsis, *Lagenaria*

siceraria, *Helianthus*

tuberosus and new host

plants.

Abstract:

Recently, the cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsely (Hemiptera: Coccoidea: Pseudococcidae) is a major pest infested different economic crops in Egypt. This insect sucks plant sap, injects toxins and secretes “honeydew” stimulating the development of black sooty moulds which adversely affect photosynthesis. Following the monitoring of new host plants, the present study recorded the cotton mealybug *P. solenopsis* on bottle gourd *Lagenaria siceraria* L., Jerusalem artichoke *Helianthus tuberosus* L. and cowpea *Vigna unguiculata* (L.) at two locations in Alexandria. In addition, during the survey conducting through 2019-2020, the mealybug was recorded on two new ornamental plants and one fruit crop, with a total of seven new host plants. All belong to six families, Acanthaceae, Astraceae, Cucurbitaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Fabaceae, and Rutaceae.

Introduction

The cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsely (Hemiptera : Coccoidea : Pseudococcidae) was a serious invasive pest. It was first recorded in Egypt by Abd-Rabou *et al.* (2010). It was revised in Egypt by Badr *et al.* (2020), as it has medium impact on some ornamental plants grown in urban area. The non-commercial products of urban areas had high impacts in spreading of the pest (Malumphy *et al.*, 2013).

The mealybug was easily recognized in the field according to its diagnostic features. Its distribution on the plant was mainly dependent on the differences in humidity. However, it's well above foliage and stems, in higher humidity, but in dry and hot regions, its

very close to the soil level (Hodgeson *et al.*, 2008).

Acalypha wilkesiana family Euphorbiaceae, common names copper-leaf and Jacob's coat, it is growing to 3 metres (9.8 ft) high and 2 metres (6 ft 7 in) across. It has a closely arranged crown, and an erect stem with many branches. Branches and leaves are hairy and plumule. Their leaves may be flat or crimped; large and broad; serrate around the edge. And it can be 10–20 c.m. (3.9–7.9 in) as long and 15 c.m. (5.9 in) in wide. Also leaves are coppery green with red blurring, giving them a mottled appearance. Separate male and female flowers appear on the same plant. The male flowers are in long tuft which hang downwards while the female flowers are in short tuft. The

flower shanks are 10–20 cm long (Airy Shaw, 1975 and Holdsworth, 1977).

Family: Cucurbitaceae is a wide family comprises many species of squashes, pumpkins, zucchinis and gourds. All the species with many economic importance and useful values. *Cucurbita* sp., the common species for field pumpkin and gourds in Egypt, however, currently, many new varieties of gourds were cultivated. More recently, based on broad cultivation, for example bottle gourd *Lagenaria siceraria* (Molina) Stand., the calabash gourd synonymy *Lagenaria vulgaris* Ser., as it was new implantation cultivation, the subject of the current study. Species were grown for their medicinal values. Moreover, they were cultivated at Alexandria and Nubaria district for their nutritional value. For instance, *Cucurbita pepo* can endure high levels of salt in the soil as well as difficult climates.

Helianthus tuberosus L. Family: Astraceae, the root vegetables common name Jerusalem artichoke was a perennial minor crop. The edible part was the root which resembles ginger. The plant grows to a height of 2 to 3 m and a width of 0.6 m and is grown in Egypt since about eight to ten years (Ismail and Moustafa, 2012). For consistency, the growth aspects of the plant may be affected by environmental conditions and genetics. The lower part of the plant has a hairy branches and stems which boost heavy infestation with mealybugs.

Lime (*Citrus aurantifolia*) Family: Rutaceae, is one of the most consumed and widely distributed fruits in the world. Citrus fruits might be classified into types: compressed mandarins, tangerines, oranges, pomelos, hybrids, lemons, limes, etc. citrus fruits, (Lime) , one of the most consumed fruits with great economic importance, has a smooth thin skin, greenish-yellow in color, with a very small neck, a flat

base, and a small nipple at the apex. However, lime ripens green to yellow and, hence, tends to become softer to perishable during storage .

Sanchezia (*Sanchezia nobilis*) of the family Acanthaceae is an evergreen semi-woody shrub that grown in tropical and sub-tropical regions for its handsome foliage. It has bright green leaves (up to 30cm in length) with prominently marked white veins. The flowers are narrowly tubular, yellow with reddish-orange bracts and are carried on stems in long spikes (Abdel-Razak, 2012). *Sanchezia* has potential as an ornamental pot plant, if the growth can be controlled.

Vigna unguiculate (L.) was an important legume crop of family Fabaceae. Common name cowpea vegetable crop was tolerant for sandy soil and low rain fall; which aligns with the criteria put by the Ministry of Agriculture to rationalize water usage as a new regulation in agriculture in Egypt. It has potential for soil reclamation in disturbed industrial sites, where its root system helps degrading organic and inorganic contaminant (El-Ghamery and Basuoni, 2018).

The aim of the study is to shed light on the gravity of *P. solenopsis* and its rapid adaptation, even regarding plants with special conditions in cultivation. Consequently, this article promotes the local markets of these three edible vegetables, Jerusalem artichoke, bottle gourd and cowpea.

Materials and methods

The field survey was carried out through 2019-2020 at two farms in Alexandria Governorate. The first farm was in Abis location, experimental farm of Agricultural Research center, and the second was in Nubaria location. Samples of different parts of each plant were randomly collected in polyethylene bags and carried to the laboratory for identification. Each part of the plants was examined under a

binocular microscope. Identification of the pest was done by the third author. In addition, literature studies were performed. The course of study was provided by pictures by the first and second authors. The surveyed plants were cultivated by Mohamed E. Abou Kamer Researcher at Cross Pollinated Vegetable Department, Horticulture

Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center.

Results and discussion

New records of the mealybug *P. solenopsis* encountered in association with inspected vegetables crops are given below (Table 1). Also, the study comprises fruits and ornamental plants at Alexandria locality, through the years 2019-2020.

Table (1): List of host plants, families and plant types infesting by the mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* include seven different plants in Alexandria Governorate, during 2019 – 2020.

Families	Host plants	Common name	Plant type	Benefit part	Uses
Acanthaceae	<i>Sanchezia speciosa</i> L.	shrubby white vein	Ornamental plant	All	Ornamental
Astraceae	<i>Helianthus tuberosus</i>	Jerusalem artichoke	Vegetable	Root	Medical and public herb
Cucurbitaceae	<i>Lagenaria siceraria</i> (Molina) Standl.	Bottle gourd	Vegetable	Fruit	Medical
	<i>Cucurbita pepo</i>	Field pumpkin	Vegetable	Fruit	Edible
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha wilkesiana</i>	Copperleaf	Medical plant	Leaves	Medical
Fabaceae	<i>Vigna unguiculata</i> (L.)	Cowpea	Vegetables	Fruit	Edible
Rutaceae	<i>Citrus aurantium</i>	Lime	Citrus Fruit	fruit	Edible

The plants start to grow in March for Family Cucurbitaceae, and in May for Family Astraceae and Fabaceae. They attain their final colour and size in August and September. The numbers of crawlers begin to realize on leaves, branches and stems of above-mentioned plants (Table 1). As a result of adhesive cultivation, for different types of crops. It was distinctly obvious that *P. solenopsis* feed on certain parts of the plants causing damage to the crop. The transmission of crawlers between parts, occurring during growth phases. The following observations were made based on field experimentation. All these families share the defining characteristics of the villi of the cotton plant family (Malvaceae) at a certain age. In turn, this facilitated the transmission of the pest between host plants leading to its widespread. This clarifies that these families are not cultivated in the same or adjacent fields.

1. Vegetables crops:

Total of four vegetables field crops were surveyed *Helianthus*

tuberosus, *Lagenaria siceraria*, *Cucurbita pepo* and *Vigna unguiculata* with three different families.

1.1. Family : Cucurbitaceae

Although field pumpkin with edible fruit *Cucurbita pepo*, Wang *et al.* (2012), it was the alternative diet for all mealybug species in the laboratory, it was not recorded as a field host plant before for this pest, it infested leaves branches and stems at the field. This study recorded it as the first record for *P. solenopsis* in Egypt in the field. Alexandria as the locality of the current survey considers a typical Mediterranean coastal ecological zone. All above mentioned species was recorded infested with the mealybugs for the first time, especially for the new species of *L. siceraria* (Plate a).

1.2. Family: Fabaceae

Vigna unguiculata, common name cowpea. Edible part was the pods, *P. solenopsis* infested the leaves branches and stems, condensed in the terminal buds (Plate b).

1.3. Family: Astraceae

Helianthus tuberosus, common name Jerusalem artichoke. Edible part was the roots, *P. solenopsis* infested the leaves branches and stems. Condensed in the terminal buds (Plate c).

2. Ornamental plants:

The field survey carried out revealed the presence of two ornamental host plants, they were as follow: In case of the host plant *Sanchezia speciosa*, it's the first to record it as a host of *P. solenopsis* in Egypt (Plate d). When the weather conditions were suitable, crawlers move freely to fix themselves to the adjacent plants.

2.1. Family: Euphorbiaceae

Acalypha wilkesiana, the crawlers take a ride to this host plant (Plate f). Finally, this study was the first to record this Medication plant as new

host plant of *P. Solenopsis* in Egypt especially at Alexandria Governorate.

3. Fruit crop:

3.1. Family: Rutaceae

Only one fruit crop was added *Citrus aurantifolia*, (Plate e), common name lime, with many different varieties of lemon cultivated in Egypt, but acid lemons also called Egyptian lime is the main variety depends on cultivated area. The present study was conducted in Nubaria district Alexandria Governorate, were the trend were similar in infestation with *P. solenopsis*

Plate (1): New host plants infested with *Phenacoccus solenopsis* at two farms locations, Alexandria. Declared the following plates.

a: *Lagenaria siceraria* b :*Vigna unguiculata* c: *Helianthus tuberosus* d: *Sanchezia speciosa* e: *Citrus aurantifolia* f: *Acalypha wilkesiana*

The current work elucidates that Alexandria locality as a typical coastal zone with highest humidity most of the year. This aspect accompanied with the shared characteristic of villi of families of vegetable plants, Astraceae, Cucurbitaceae and Fabaceae induced never to cultivate these plants in the same or adjacent areas. In addition, the study pushes the marketing of the economically vegetable crops bottle gourd *L. siceraria* Jerusalem artichoke, *H. tuberosus* and cowpea *V. unguiculata* for the international markets.

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Comparative of different formulations for some compounds (Neonicotinoids) against the aphid *Aphis gossypii* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) on zucchini and cucumber plants

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 13/ 7/2020

Accepted: 27/ 8 /2020

Keywords

Formulations,
neonicotinoids, aphids,
zucchini, cucumber and
Egypt.

Abstract:

The aphid *Aphis gossypii* Glover (Hemiptera: Aphididae) is a polyphagous aphid found on more than 900 plant species. It is distributed throughout the world but prefers the warmer regions. It has been a pest in different locations in Egypt, particularly affecting vegetables. The present work was conducted in two field experiments in Etay-El-Baroud, Agricultural Research Station, Beheira Governorate, during 2019 and 2020 seasons to evaluate the efficiency of some different formulations of neonicotinoid insecticides against the aphid *A.gossypii* on zucchini and cucumber plants. The results showed that a decrease in the number of aphids in all treatments, insecticides that caused a significant decrease compared to the control. General mean of % reduction aphid number were 91.75, 90.79 and 88.10%, for imidacloprid, acetamiprid and thiamethoxam, respectively, at 2019, while were 91.94, 90.65 and 88.97%, respectively, at 2020 season on zucchini fields. On cucumber field general mean of % reduction was 91.94, 90.65 and 88.97%, for imidacloprid, acetamiprid and thiamethoxam, respectively, at 2019, while were 91.03, 92.71 and 92.36%, respectively, at 2020 season. The results confirmed the presence of small significant differences between the formulations of imidacloprid, acetamiprid and thiamethoxam, and while all formulations indicated a significant decrease in the number of aphids in zucchini and cucumber plants compared to control during the two seasons.

Introduction

The Cucurbitaceae family possesses economically important species including cucumber, melon, watermelon, calabash, squash, and pumpkin. Many hundreds of varieties and cultivars of these are grown around the world and are major agricultural

commodities. The most important are used as food and industrial crops (El-Adawy and Taha, 2001; Acquah, 2005 and Practices and Leffingwell, 2015). Zucchini (*Cucurbita pepo* L.) is one of the most popular vegetable crops for human nutrition, not only in Egypt. It is

cultivated in Egypt all over the year, outdoor in summer and indoor either in green houses or in tunnels in winter (Seleim *et al.*, 2015). It is good source of minerals like iron, manganese, phosphorus, zinc and potassium in addition to its content of antioxidant vitamin-C and A (Abd El-Wareth and Ahmed, 2017). Cucumber one of the most important crops in Egypt and worldwide and during its growth stages is threatened by several pests including aphids which lead to deleterious effects growth, yield (Shams El Din *et al.*, 2012).

Aphis gossypii Glover (Hemiptera: Aphididae), is a major pest of Cucurbitaceae production, often causing leaf yellowing, curling, plant wilting and stunting. The danger of aphids is not only the direct damage through sucking the sap from the leaves and stems, but also the indirect damage caused either by viruses transmission or by exuding honeydew which induce sooty mold growth on the greenish part of the plants (Abdu-Allah and Hashem, 2017). This damage causes a high loss of yield, so controlling aphids in crops is very important. Insecticides are one of the most effective traditional tools that have been usually applied by farmers to control aphids. Although, there are many advantages of these insecticides in controlling aphids (Casida and Durkin, 2013 and Xiaohua *et al.*, 2020).

Pest control with insecticides is widely used in the world to avoid pest damage to crops (Schiess *et al.*, 2017). In recent years, selective insecticides, like neonicotinoids because insect pests became resistant to the most of conventional insecticides. Neonicotinoids represent the fastest-growing class of insecticides introduced to the market since the launch of pyrethroids (Nauen and Bretschneider, 2002). Because of their physicochemical properties,

neonicotinoid can be useful for a wide range of application techniques, including foliar, seed treatment, soil drench and stem application. Neonicotinoids, a new class of insecticides, act preferably on insect nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs) as their agonists (Elbert *et al.*, 1998 and Viera *et al.*, 2019). These selective insecticides are environmentally friendly (Yeh *et al.*, 1997), and have quick knock down effect on target pest by interfering with transmission of impulse in the nerve system. Neonicotinoid application reduces infection rate and spread of many crop viruses (Westwood *et al.*, 1998; Bethke *et al.*, 2001 and Elzen, 2001). Neonicotinoid insecticides represent the fastest-growing class of insecticides introduced to the market since the launch of pyrethroids (Nauen and Bretschneider, 2002). Because of their physicochemical properties, neonicotinoid can be useful for a wide range of application techniques, including foliar, seed treatment, soil drench and stem application.

In the short term, the intensive and careless use of insecticides has produced biological imbalance and increased environmental contamination (Schiess *et al.*, 2017). The purpose of formulating pesticide active ingredients for crop protection is to uniformly spread a small amount of an active chemical over a large area and ensure safety in during application and to optimize pesticide efficacy (Hazra and Purkait, 2019). Pesticides are available in various formulations may be created according to the standard of the product for any of the purposes such as to achieve effects that cannot be obtained from its components when these are used singly, achieve a higher degree of effectiveness, facilitate any potential synergistic action of their components, and improve handling properties and often safety for the user. Consequently,

the competently designed formulations for particular applications are safer, more effective and more economical than any of their components used singly (Sarwar, 2015).

Therefore, two field experiments were carried out in Etay-El-Baroud, Agricultural Research Station, Beheira Governorate, during 2019 and 2020 seasons to evaluate the efficiency of some different formulations of neonicotinoid insecticides against the aphid *A. gossypii* on zucchini and cucumber plants in field.

Materials and methods

1. Used Insecticides:

Imidacloprid (ImiDOR 35%SC), (JOUN 70%WG) and (Canopus 70%WG).

Acetamiprid (CETAM 20%EC), (Kera 20%WP) and (Mospilan 20%SP).

Thiamethoxam (Actara 25%WG), (Lex-Extra 25%WDG) and (Golden Horse 25%WDG).

2. The field trials:

The field trials were carried out in zucchini and cucumber plants in field at Etay-El-Baroud Agricultural Research station, Beheira Governorate, during 2019 and 2020 summer seasons. Experimental site was divided into 20×4 plots, each plot 1/100 feddan (42m²). Randomized complete blocks design was used with four replicates for each treatment with the control plots. Every plot was separated from the other

plot by one meter to reduce interference from another treatment drift. Motor sprayer with used to spray the tested pesticides with the recommended dose. For counting the numbers of aphid, *A. gossypii*, samples of 25 leaves were collected at random in the morning for both diagonals of the inner square area of each experimental plot. Reduction percentages of numbers were calculated according to Henderson and Tilton equation (1955) and subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) (CoStat Statistical Software, 1998).

Results and discussion

Results presented in Tables (1 and 2) showed that the reduction percentages of aphids on zucchini plants after one, seven and ten days of treatment by some neonicotinoid formulations of imidacloprid (ImiDOR 35% SC, JOUN 70%WG and Canopus 70%WG), acetamiprid (CETAM 20% EC, Kera 20%WP and Mospilan 20% SP) and thiamethoxam (Actara 25%WG and Lex-Extra 25% WDG) during 2019 and 2020 seasons. General mean of % reduction was 92.09, 90.73 and 87.79 %, for imidacloprid, acetamiprid and thiamethoxam, respectively, at 2019, while were 91.81, 90.67 and 88.97%, respectively, at 2020 season. The results showed a decrease in the number of aphids in all treatments, insecticides that caused a significant decrease compared to the control.

Table (1): Reduction percentages of the aphid *Aphis gossypii* on zucchini plants treated with different formulations of neonicotinoids at season 2019.

Common Name	Formulations	Rate/200L/ feddan	% Reduction after treatment (day)				General mean
			1	7	10	Mean	
Imidacloprid	ImiDOR 35% SC	40ml	90.10	93.10	93.80	92.33a	92.09 a
	JOUN 70%WG	60gm	90.10	93.20	94.00	92.43a	
	Canopus70%WG	35gm	89.20	92.30	93.00	91.50a	
Acetamiprid	CETAM 20%EC	100ml	88.80	92.30	92.70	91.26a	90.73 ab
	Kera 20%WP	50gm	89.20	91.60	92.00	90.93a	
	Mospilan 20%SP	50gm	89.70	90.30	90.60	90.00a	
Thiamethoxam	Actara 25%WG	60gm	88.80	92.20	92.50	91.16a	87.79 b
	Lex-Extra 25%WDG	40gm	87.20	88.30	88.70	88.06ab	
	GoldenHorse 25% WDG	80gm	73.90	84.40	94.10	84.13b	
LSD 0.05					5.07	3.93	

Means within the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different according to the LSD_{0.05}.

Table (2): Reduction percentages of the aphid *Aphis gossypii* on zucchini plants treated with different formulations of neonicotinoids at season 2020.

Common Name	Formulations	Rate/200L /feddan	% Reduction after treatment (day)				General mean
			1	7	10	Mean	
Imidacloprid	ImiDOR 35% SC	40ml	89.90	91.90	92.10	91.30a	91.81a
	JOUN 70% WG	60gm	90.20	93.30	93.30	92.27a	
	Canopus70% WG	35gm	89.80	92.90	92.90	91.87a	
Acetamiprid	CETAM 20%EC	100ml	89.10	92.20	93.10	91.47a	90.67a
	Kera 20% WP	50gm	89.30	91.20	91.90	90.80ab	
	Mospilan 20%SP	50gm	88.00	90.80	90.40	89.73abc	
Thiamethoxam	Actara 25% WG	60gm	91.16	91.80	92.50	91.82a	88.97a
	Lex-Extra 25% WDG	40gm	83.40	84.10	93.10	86.87c	
	GoldenHorse 25% WDG	80gm	87.90	88.50	88.30	88.23bc	
LSD 0.05						2.91	3.61

Means within the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different according to the LSD_{0.05}.

Results presented in Tables (3 and 4) showed the reduction percentages of aphids on cucumber plants after one, seven and ten days of treatment by some neonicotinoid formulations of imidacloprid (ImiDOR 35% SC, JOUN 70% WG and Canopus 70% WG), acetamiprid (CETAM 20% EC, Kera 20% WP and Mospilan 20%

SP) and thiamethoxam (Actara 25% WG and Lex-Extra 25% WDG) during 2019 and 2020 seasons. General mean of % reduction was 92.21, 92.73 and 92.40%, for imidacloprid, acetamiprid and thiamethoxam, respectively, at 2019, while were 91.93, 92.46 and 92.13%, respectively, at 2020 season.

Table (3): Reduction percentages of the aphid *Aphis gossypii* on cucumber plants treated with different formulations of neonicotinoids at season 2019.

Common Name	Formulations	Rate/200L /feddan	% Reduction after treatment (day)				General mean
			1	7	10	Mean	
Imidacloprid	ImiDOR 35% SC	40ml	91.90	92.10	92.40	92.13c	92.21a
	JOUN 70% WG	60gm	90.70	92.80	93.20	92.63bc	
	Canopus70% WG	35gm	91.20	92.00	92.40	91.87c	
Acetamiprid	CETAM 20%EC	100ml	92.00	92.00	92.80	92.26bc	92.73a
	Kera 20% WP	50gm	92.70	92.80	93.20	92.90ab	
	Mospilan 20%SP	50gm	92.10	93.40	93.60	93.03a	
Thiamethoxam	Actara 25% WG	60gm	92.60	92.60	93.30	92.83ab	92.40a
	Lex-Extra 25% WDG	40gm	92.00	92.50	92.90	92.47abc	
	GoldenHorse 25% WDG	80gm	91.20	92.10	92.40	91.90c	
LSD 0.05						0.68	1.03

Means within the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different according to the LSD_{0.05}.

Table (4): Reduction percentages of the aphid *Aphis gossypii* on cucumber plants treated with different formulations of neonicotinoids at season 2020.

Common Name	Formulations	Rate/200L /feddan	% Reduction after treatment (day)				General mean
			1	7	10	Mean	
Imidacloprid	ImiDOR 35% SC	40ml	92.00	92.60	93.40	92.67a	91.93a
	JOUN 70% WG	60gm	90.70	92.00	92.40	91.70bc	
	Canopus70% WG	35gm	90.80	91.70	91.80	91.43c	
Acetamiprid	CETAM 20%EC	100ml	91.80	92.90	93.50	92.73a	92.46a
	Kera 20% WP	50gm	91.90	92.40	92.80	92.37a	
	Mospilan 20%SP	50gm	91.70	92.50	92.70	92.30ab	
Thiamethoxam	Actara 25% WG	60gm	92.40	92.30	93.20	92.63a	92.13a
	Lex-Extra 25% WDG	40gm	91.90	92.20	93.00	92.36a	
	GoldenHorse 25% WDG	80gm	90.20	91.10	92.90	91.40c	
LSD 0.05						0.63	0.70

Means within the same column followed by the same letters are not significantly different according to the LSD_{0.05}.

In family Cucurbitaceae fields, pests with sucking mouthparts, especially *A. gossypii* have been the main cause of plant damage, seriously influencing zucchini production (Messing and Klungness, 2002). As major pests all over the world, aphids not only cause direct damage by feeding, but also lead to infection by acting as viral vectors (Brault *et al.*, 2007). The morphological characteristics of plants could clearly influence the feeding and spawning behaviors of insects (Buchman and Cuddington, 2009 and Legrand and Barbosa, 2014). It has important effects on the landing and attachment of aphids, and predation of natural enemies (Dorry and Assad, 2001 and Larson and Whitham, 1997). Leaf hairs and thorns have been important anti-aphid characteristics of plants, thereby making them fly away because of lack of food (Harris and Bradley, 1973). Chemical pesticides have been long widely used as an effective approach for preventing aphid infestation (Ayala *et al.*, 1996). However, the accumulation of pesticide residue due to overuse of chemical pesticide has become a major issue (Wu, 2005). The present results are agreement with those obtained by Chen *et al.*, 2007; Subhash *et al.*, 2017 ; Roditakis *et al.*, 2017 and Wang *et al.*, 2017. They found that, neonicotinoids were very toxic to sucking pests compared by conventional insecticides. Sarwar (2015) reported that, an insecticide formulation can be principally a wettable powder (WP), soluble powder (SP), water-dispersible granules (WDG), water soluble (WS) or emulsifiable concentrate (EC). These formulations are relatively easy to handle, transport, store, little agitation is required, do not settle out or separate when equipment is running, non-abrasive, cannot plug screens or nozzles, and leaves little visible residue

on treated surfaces. Consequently, the competently designed formulations for applications are safer, more effective and more economical than any of their components used singly. Preftakes *et al.* (2019) suggested that spray drift was reduced by 37% when comparing the SC to the WP formulation. These findings can be used to develop a classification scheme for formulated products and tank additives based on their potential for reducing spray drift.

The results confirmed the presence of small significant differences between the formulations of imidacloprid, acetamiprid and thiamethoxam, and while all formulations indicated a significant decrease in the number of aphids in zucchini and cucumber plants compared to control during the two seasons.

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Bionomics of the jasmine whitefly *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) in Egypt as well as seasonal abundance of this pest and its parasitoid on jasmine

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 16/7/2020

Accepted: 21 /9/2020

Keywords

Bionomics, jasmine whitefly, *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* , seasonal abundance, *Eretmocerus corni* , jasmine and Egypt.

Abstract:

Jasmine is one of the oldest traditional flowers and it is an important flowering group of plants which are commercially grown for their fragrant flowers and oil production. The jasmine whitefly *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* (Kotinsky) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) is one of the most important pest of jasmine all over the world and Egypt. Larvae and adults of this pest suck the sap from the under surface of the leaves and infested leaves turn yellow. The aim of this work is to study the bionomics of *D. kirkaldyi* as well as seasonal abundance of this pest and its parasitoid on jasmine plant . The results indicated that *D. kirkaldyi* infested by 12 host plants distributed in 9 Governorates and recorded associated with 4 parasitoids in Egypt as well as taxonomy studies of it was provided. It also was found infesting jasmine plants at Gharbiya Governorate, Egypt. To obtain basic ecological data for the whitefly , *D. kirkaldyi* and its parasitoid *Eretmocerus corni* Haldeman (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) every two weeks intervals throughout two seasons (August to December 2018 and 2019). Seasonal fluctuations of alive total population, nymphs and adults of *D. kirkaldyi* throughout the tested year. The seasonal abundance for both nymph and adult recorded one peak on middle of October in two seasons. The effects of four ecological factors (3 abiotic +1 biotic) on the population dynamics of alive larvae and adult population were estimated. The parasitoid *E. corni* showed highly significant correlation with larvae of *D. kirkaldyi* by ($r= 0.91$ and 0.92) in two seasons.

Introduction

Jasmine products are important natural raw materials in the perfume industry. Jasmine flowers are used for making gariands for ceremonial offering, for adoring hair by ladies and for production of “attar” and concrete in cosmetic industry. These flowers are also used in toiletries, food essences, chewing tobacco, dental preparations

and confectioneries. Even different parts of the plants such as leaf, stem, bark, root and fruits are also used for medicinal purposes (Guledagudda *et al.*,1997) . Jasmine trade is estimated to pull in some \$6.5 million annually for Egypt, providing income to around 50,000 people, according to the International Federation of Essential

Oils and Aroma Trades (AFP, 2020). Jasmine is infested by several insect and mite pests. The lepidopteran pests like bud borer, *Hendecasis duplifascialis* (Hampson) (Crambidae; Lepidoptera); bud borer/gallery worm, *Elasmopalpus jasminophagus* (Hampson) (Pyralidae: Lepidoptera), and leaf webworm, *Nausinoe geometralis* (Guenee) (Crambidae; Lepidoptera) are of major importance. Sucking pests like eriophyid mite, *Eryophes* spp (Acarina: Eriophyidae); tingid bug, *Corythauma ayyari* (Drake) (Hemiptera: Tingidae); whitefly, *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* (Kotinsky) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and flower thrips, *Isoneurothrips orientalis* (Bagn.) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) cause minor damage to the crop. Dipteran pest like blossom midge, *Contarinia maculipennis* Fabricius (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) sometimes infests the crop (Pal and Chakravarthy, 2020). The most important pests are whiteflies, specially in the Mediterranean region, so it is attacked by 16 species of whiteflies ; These are *Aleuroclava jasmini* (Takahashi), *Aleurodicus dispersus* Russell , *Aleurolobus bidentatus* Singh, *Aleurothrixus* sp. , *Aleurotrachelus trachoides* (Back) , *Bemisia giffardi* (Kotinsky) , *Bemisia jasminum* David & Subramanian , *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) , *Dialeurodes citri* (Ashmead), *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* (Kotinsky) , *Dialeurodes* sp. , *Dialeurodes vulgaris* Singh, *Minutaleyrodes minutus* (Singh) , *Singhiella citrifolii* (Morgan), *Singhius hibisci* (Kotinsky) and *Trialeurodes vaporariorum* (Westwood) . The dangerous pest of them is *D. kirkaldyi* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae). The several biotic and abiotic factors are responsible for low productivity and quality deterioration of jasmine production, but the damage caused by

multitudes of arthropod pests constitutes the most important limiting factor. To overcome these pests, the above mentioned IPM measures can be successfully imposed wherever applicable for the management of pests in jasmine. The minimum yield loss caused by these pests can even be avoided (Rabeena *et al.*, 2020).

D. kirkaldyi has a history of spreading internationally. It was first described in 1907 on *Jasminum grandifolium* from Hawaii (Kotinsky, 1907), although the area of origin of the species is uncertain (Martin *et al.*, 2000). The nymphs and adults of whitefly suck the sap from lower surface of the leaves in large numbers and cause yellowing. It invites sooty mould fungus thereby photosynthesis will be affected and reduction in yield occurs (Rabeena *et al.*, 2020).

It attacked by different host plant species in Egypt and the world by Abd-Rabou (1996 and 1997) , Evans (2007) and Sundararaj and Dubey (2006). *D. kirkaldyi* is a widely distributed species that is found on (Russell , 1964; Sundararaj and David , 1992; Evans, 2007 and Chiun-Cheng *et al.*, 2010). Also is a mainly tropical and sub-tropical oligophagous whitefly of relatively little importance to UK Plant Health. Its main hosts are *Jasminum* species. It is already present in the EU (Portugal and Cyprus) (Mifsud *et al.*, 2010).

As a potential pest of citrus, southern EU MS should be aware of this organism. It is likely to spread within the Mediterranean region. Citrus producing regions should monitor the scientific literature for further information on this organism. The most favoured hosts, on which high numbers of *D. kirkaldyi* can be found, are *Jasminum* spp. and *Morinda citrifolia* (Evans and Bennett, 1996 and Martin *et al.*, 2000). Also, it was found on several species of host plants in Florida,

including citrus, but high populations of this whitefly are only known to occur on jasmine species (Nguyen *et al.*, 1993).

However, immature stages and adults do cause damage by feeding on plant sap (Nguyen and Hamon, 1989). Larvae and adults of this pest suck the sap from the under surface of the leaves and infested leaves turn yellow and is associated with vectoring yellow ring mosaic disease of jasminum (Mariappan and Ramanujam, 1975 and Mound, 1983).

Nguyen *et al.* (1993) and Polaszek *et al.* (1999) recorded one parasitoid species, *Encarsia protransvena* Viggiani (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae), has been reported from *D. kirkaldyi*. Evans and Bennett (1996) recorded *Eretmocerus rosei* Evans and Bennett for the first record of an *Eretmocerus* species that has been reared from this whitefly species, and only the second record of an *Eretmocerus* species that attacks this whitefly genus. Denmark (1964) reported on the introduction of an undetermined species of the genus *Eretmocerus* into Florida as a natural enemy of the citrus whitefly *Dialeurodes citri* (Ashmead).

Eretmocerus corni Haldeman (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) is one of the most important parasitoids associated with whitefly species and first recorded in Egypt by Priesner and Hosny (1940). It is recorded associated with 16 host whitefly and 14 countries of the world and 3 whitefly species in 6 Governorates in Egypt (Abd-Rabou, 1998c). The three whitefly hosts, *B. tabaci*, *Siphoninus phillyreae* (Haliday) and *Trialeurodes ricini* (Misra). In 1998, Abd-Rabou and Abou-Setta recorded seven parasitoids attacking *S. phillyreae* one of them *E. corni*. Also, Abd-Rabou (1998 a,b,c and 2002) recorded this species associated with *B. tabaci* and *T. ricini*.

The aim of this work is to study the taxonomy, host plants, distribution and parasitoids of *D. kirkaldyi* as well as seasonal abundance of this pest and its parasitoid on jasmine plant.

Materials and methods

1. Survey of host plants, distribution and parasitoids of the jasmine whitefly *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi*:

A survey of the jasmine whitefly *D. kirkaldyi* host plants, distribution and parasitoids were carried out in different locations in Egypt throughout two successive years. Samples of infested leaves and branches with *D. kirkaldyi*. The samples were packed in paper bags and transferred to the laboratory for examination. The examined leaves were enclosed in plastic jars covered with muslin held in position by a rubber band and kept under preferential conditions for securing any emergence of parasitoids. The parasitoids were collected, sorted into species and preserved in vials contain 70 % ethyl alcohol and glycerin, in addition to slide mounting species for identification.

2. Seasonal abundance of the jasmine whitefly *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi*:

It was carried out for 2 years, (August till December, 2018 and 2019) at Gharbiya Governorate, Egypt. A farm about one Fadden in area, cultivated with jasmine and heavily infested with *D. kirkaldyi* was chosen for this study. The farm was not exposed to any chemical treatment during three years prior to the present study and during the investigation period. Every 15 day-intervals 30 leaves with different stages of the whitefly, *D. kirkaldyi* were collected at random from the different directions of jasmine plant. The leaves represented the different sides, peripheral, inner zones, lower and middle of the plant. These leaves were kept in a paper bag and transferred to the laboratory for examination and

counting the whitefly insects. The stages of whitefly insect considered in counting process were larval instars and adults .

3. Seasonal abundance of the parasitoid *Eretmocerus corni* associated with the jasmine whitefly *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi*:

Jasmine leaves infested with larval instars of *D. kirkaldyi* were half monthly ,(30 leaves /15 days) from August till December ,2018 and 2019. Each leaf was stored in well-ventilated glass emergence tube for its parasitoid emergence that its numbers were recorded daily was calculated. Samples 30 leaves randomly selected whitefly were chosen. These samples represented larval instars, . Each larval whitefly was removed, transferred and mulched on a slide in a water film.

4. Effect of biotic and abiotic factors on the abundance the jasmine whitefly *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi*:

Weather factors as maximum, minimum temperature and relative humidity were considered from Central Laboratory for Agricultural Climate. The weekly maximum and minimum temperatures as well as relative humidity were calculated and total number of parasitoids. Multiple regressions were conducted for weather factors combined as well as plant age as described. The obtained determination factor (R^2) of E.V. % was used to explain the effect of testing factors. Process Correlation and Regression were used in SAS to analysis the obtained data (SAS Institute, 1998).

Results and discussion

1. Taxonomy of *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi*:

1.1. Order: Hemiptera

Suborder : Sternorrhyncha

Superfamily: Aleyrodoidea

Family : Aleyrodidae

Genus : *Dialeurodes*

Species: *kirkaldyi*

1.2. Genus *Dialeurodes* Cockerell

1.2.1.Synonyms :

Aleyrodes (Dialeurodes) Cockerell 1902: 283. Type species. *Aleyrodes citri* Riley and Howard 1893, by original designation, a synonym of *A. citri* Ashmead 1885.

Dialeurodes Cockerell; full genus, **Quaintance and Baker 1914**: 97.

Kanakarajiella David and Sundararaj 1993. Type species. *Dialeurodes vulgaris* Singh 1931, by original designation; synonymy according to Martin and Mound 2007: 28.

Lankaleurodes **David 1993**: 23. Type species. *Dialeurodes radiipuncta* Quaintance and Baker 1917, by original designation; synonymy according to **Martin and Mound 2007**: 28.

Shanthinia David 2000, in P.M.M. **David 2000**: 125. Type species - *Shanthinia sheryli* David 2000, by monotypy and original designation; synonymy according to **Martin and Mound 2007**: 28.

*Dialeurodes (Rabdostigma) Quaintance and Baker 1917: 426, *Dialeurodes (Gigaleurodes)* Quaintance and Baker 1917: 426, and *Dialeurodes (Dialeuroplata)* **Quaintance and Baker 1917**: 435*

Dialeuronomada Quaintance and Baker; full genus by Sundararaj and David, 1991.

1.2.2. Diagnostic characters:

Pupal case dark brown or yellowish, puparial outline not laterally indented abdominally ; puparial margin smooth, or more coarsely crenulate. Thoracic and caudal tracheal openings at margin in form of distinct invaginated pores which are smooth or finely crenate internally. Vasiform orifice relatively small, subcircular posterior margin often with small median tubercle. Operculum usually concealing lingula. Inner margins toothed or smooth.

1.2.3. Key to Genus *Dialeurodes* members in Egypt:

1. Subdorsal setae not extending beyond margin of pupal case. Anterior rim short, length about one-eighth of length of vasiform orifice.....*Dialeurodes*

elbaensis Priesner & Hosny

-Subdorsal setae different. Anterior rim long.....2

2. 1st abdominal setae present. A brown area, in the median area of the dorsum. The margin of vasiform orifice without median tubercle posteriorl..*Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* (Kotinsky)

-1st abdominal setae absent. No brown area in the median area of the dorsum. The margin of vasiform orifice with median tubercle posteriorly*Dialeurodes citri* (Ashmead)

1.3. *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* (Kotinsky)

1.3.1. Synonyms :

Aleyrodes kirkaldyi Kotinsky **1907: 95-96**. Syntypes. USA: Hawaii, on unidentified trailing shrub.

Beaumontia grandifolia, *Morinda citrifolia* and *Jasminum grandiflorum*, USNM.

Dialeurodes kirkaldyi (Kotinsky);

Quaintance and Baker 1914: 98.

Dialeurodes yercaudensis **Jesudasan and David 1991: 307.**

1.3.2. Dignostic characters:

Median line of puparium often pigmented brownish (examine several); A brown area, in the median area of the dorsum; first abdominal setae present but very small ; eighth abdominal setae opposite, or posterior to, widest part of operculum . The margin of vasiform orifice without median tubercle posteriorly, vasiform orifice toothed; pale species with median thoracic pigmentation. Submarginal setae absent.

2. Host plants of *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi*:

2.1. In Egypt : Combretaceae: *Terminalia* sp., *Terminalia chebula*. Covelvulaceae: *Convolvulus arvensis*. Malvaceae: *Malva rotundifolia*, *Malva silvestri*. Myrtaceae: *Pisdium guava*.

Oleaceae: *Jasminum grandiflorum*, *Jasminum officinale*, *Jasminum sambac*. Ranunculaceae: *Ranuculus repens*. Rubiaceae: *Coffea* sp., *Coffea arabica*.

2.2. In World: Apocynaceae: *Allamanda neriifolia*, *Beaumontia grandiflora*, *Plumeria acuminata*, *Plumeria acutifolia*, *Tabernaemontana* sp., *Trachelospermum jasminoides*; Combretaceae: *Terminalia* sp.; Ebenaceae: *Diospyros kaki*, Ebenaceae: *Diospyros* sp., *Diospyros virginiana*; Geraniaceae: *Pelargonium* sp.; Jugandaceae: *Juglans regia*; Lauraceae: *Persea americana*; Loganiaceae: *Fagraea fragrans*; Lythraceae: *Lagerstroemia indica*; Malpighiaceae: *Hiptage benghalensis*, *Hiptage madablota*; Malvaceae: *Malva sylvestris*; Oleaceae: *Jasminum amplexicaule*, *Jasminum arabica*, *Jasminum auriculatum*, *Jasminum biflorum*, *Jasminum multiflorum*, *Jasminum nitidum*, *Jasminum officinale*, *Jasminum sambac*, *Jasminum volubile*, Oleaceae: *Jasminum frutiscens*, *Ligustrum walkeri*, *Syringa* sp.?; Rubiaceae: *Coffea arabica*, *Coffea* sp., *Gardenia tahitiensis*, *Jasminum sambac*, *Morinda citrifolia*, *Morinda royoc*; Rutaceae: *Citrus sinensis*, *Citrus x paradisi*; Verbenaceae: *Clerodendrum fragrans*, *Premna integrifolia*.

3. Distribution of *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* :

3.1. In Egypt: Alexandria, Assiut, Aswan, Cairo, Gharbiya, Giza, Ismailia, Portsaid and Qalyubiya.

3.2. In World: Australia, Azores, Bahamas, Barbados, Burma, Caroline Is., China, Cook Is., Costa Rica, Cuba, Egypt, Fiji, Ghana, Greece, Guam, Guyana, Hawaii, Hong Kong, India, Iran, Israel, Jamaica, Japan, Lebanon, Malaysia, Mexico, Pakistan, Philippines, Puerto Rico, Samoa, Sri Lanka, Syria, Tahiti, Taiwan, Thailand, Trinidad, Turkey, UK, USA.

4. Parasitoids of *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* :

4.1. In Egypt: Aphelinidae: *Encarsia lutea* (Masi) , *Encarsia protransvena* Viggiani, *Eretmocerus corni* Haldeman and *Eretmocerus mundus* (Mercet).

4.2. In World: Aphelinidae: *Encarsia abundantia* Chou & Su, *E. bothrocera* Huang and Polaszek, *E. dialeurodis* Hayat, *E. lahorensis* (Howard) , *E. lutea* (Masi), *E. neoporteri* Myartseva and Evans , *E. nigricephala* Dozier, *E. perflava* Hayat, *E. protransvena* Viggiani, *Encarsia* sp., *E. strenua* (Silvestri) , *E. strenua* group, *E. tabacivora* Viggiani,, *Eretmocerus portoricensis* Dozier, *Er. rosei* Evans and Bennett, *Eretmocerus* sp.

5. Seasonal abundance of the jasmine whitefly *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi*:

Data presented in, (Tables 1 and 2) illustrated that larvae and adults stages curves had one peak during the first year, (2018) and the second year (2019) on jasmine leaves. In the first year, (2018) the peak of larvae recorded on (15th of October) with 1019 individuals (30 leaves) and the peak of adult recorded on (15th of October), with 422 individuals (30 leaves). While in the second year (2019) the peak of larvae also, recorded on (15th of October) with 1028 individuals (30 leaves) and the peak of adult recorded on (15th of October), with 430 individuals (30 leaves). **Helmi (2005)** *D. kirkaldyi* had three annual field generations which lasted 170, 90 and 100 days, respectively.

6. Seasonal abundance of the parasitoid *Eretmocerus corni* associated with the jasmine whitefly *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi*:

The parasitoid *E. corni* is an effective parasitoid which keeps populations of the *D. kirkaldyi* under control in Egypt. In the first year (2018) and the second (2019), the highest peak was observed in 15th of October in two years (Tables 1 and 2). The parasitoid

E. corni showed highly significant correlation with larvae of *D. kirkaldyi* by (r= 0.91 and 0.92) in two seasons.

7. Effect of biotic and abiotic factors on the abundance of *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi*:

We studied the effect of a biotic factor as parasitoid (Biotic) and abiotic factors maximum, minimum temperature and relative humidity. Correlation, regression analysis and multi regression between biotic and abiotic factors and population of *D. kirkaldyi* was in liner degree, in two years of study 2018 and 2019. Statistically, the results represented in Table (3) showed the effect of the weather factors (maximum, minimum temperature and relative humidity) activity of *D. kirkaldyi*. With the respect to abiotic factors had significant effect on the population of the larval stage of *D. kirkaldyi* in two years of study, while adult had significant effect on the population with maximum temperature in two years of study 2018 and 2019 (Tables 1 and 2). El-Borollosy *et al.* (1990) tested the effect of maximum and mean temperature as well as mean percentage of relative humidity on *D. kirkaldyi* abundance they stated that these three factors had influence on the population density of this whitefly species, this influence differed significantly from one influence on the population density of this whitefly species, this influence differed significantly from one weather factor to another and from one season to another. Later Helmi (2005) obtained results of statistical analysis for the effects of some ecological factors on the population dynamics of *D. kirkaldyi* nymphs revealed that maximum, minimum and mean temperature had high positive significant effects on nymph seasonal. While mean percentage of relative humidity had positive insignificant effects.

Table (1) : Total population the jasmine whitefly *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* and number of its parasitoid *Eretmocerus corni* on jasmine at Gharbiya Governorate during the first year 2018.

Date	Mean number of <i>Dialeurodes kirkaldyi</i>		Mean number of <i>Eretmocerus corni</i>	Climatic Factors		
	larvae	Adults		Max. Temp. °C	Min. Temp. °C	Mean RH. %
1 August	650	212	187	35.4	22.6	58.1
15-Aug	813	419	199	35.2	21.9	58.8
1 Sep.	939	390	243	33.8	21.3	61.5
15 Sep.	963	399	260	33.9	20.8	62.7
1 Oct.	995	412	322	31.4	19.7	62.1
15 Oct.	1019	422	436	30.2	18.8	63.1
1 Nov.	643	271	302	27.1	17.7	61.8
15 Nov.	635	268	232	26.1	16.4	57.3
1 Dec.	543	231	101	21.0	15.0	58.3
15 Dec.	553	235	15	18.3	14.1	57.0

Table (2): Total population the jasmine whitefly *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* and number of its parasitoid *Eretmocerus corni* on jasmine at Gharbiya Governorate during the second year 2019.

Date	Mean number of <i>Dialeurodes kirkaldyi</i>		Mean number of <i>Eretmocerus corni</i>	Climatic Factors		
	Larvae	Adults		Max. Temp. °C	Min. Temp. °C	Mean R.H. %
1 August	701	190	175	35.8	20.7	59.7
15-Aug	822	428	207	35.7	22.7	59.6
1 Sep.	948	398	251	35.4	21.1	60.5
15 Sep.	971	408	269	33.7	20.7	61.7
1 Oct.	1004	421	330	34.1	19.9	62.7
15 Oct.	1028	430	444	31.6	18.9	63.9
1 Nov.	651	280	310	28.6	17.5	62.1
15 Nov.	644	277	240	27.4	16.2	58.5
1 Dec.	551	240	109	26.1	15.1	59.1
15 Dec.	561	244	20	20.4	14.6	60.6

Table (3) : The simple correlation and regression coefficients and multiple regressions between the different stages of *Dialeurodes kirkaldyi* , climatic factors and *Eretmocerus corni* in 2018 and 2019 years.

Factors		Simple correlation and regression						Multiple regression	
		R		P		B		E.V %	
		2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019
larvae	Max. Temp. °C	0.67	0.71	0.036	0.022	21.2	26.1	79.58	80.77
	Min. Temp. °C	0.60	0.71	0.068	0.021	38.6	48.4		
	Mean R.H.%	0.82	0.66	0.003	0.038	66.0	72.3		
	<i>Eretmocerus corni</i>	0.75	0.75	0.012	0.012	1.2	1.2		
	All above							80.05	82.12
Adults	Max. Temp. °C	0.59	0.53	0.072	0.112	8.8	9.7	63.78	59.23
	Min. Temp. °C	0.52	0.61	0.126	0.059	15.6	20.8		
	Mean R.H.%	0.72	0.55	0.020	0.101	26.8	29.8		
	<i>Eretmocerus corni</i>	0.65	0.65	0.043	0.043	0.5	0.5		
								66.83	69.62

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Functional response and predation efficiency of the flower bug *Orius albidipennis* (Hemiptera: Anthocoridae) to different densities of the cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) under laboratory conditions

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 15/7/2020

Accepted: 24/9/2020

Keywords

Predatory bug, *Orius albidipennis*, *Phenacoccus solenopsis*, predation efficiency rate and functional response parameters.

Abstract:

The cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Sternorrhyncha: Coccoidea: Pseudococcidae) is considered a very dangerous pest of various vegetable crops in Egypt. Also, the predator *Orius albidipennis* Reuter (Hemiptera: Anthocoridae) is one of the most effective control methods of many insect pests infested vegetables crops in Egypt. This Study aimed to investigate the predation efficiency and functional response of *O. albidipennis* to different densities of cotton mealybug *P. solenopsis* (10, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35) eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars during 24 hrs. period under laboratory conditions at 28 ± 2 °C, 60 ± 5 % RH. and L18:D6 photoperiod. The results showed that *O. albidipennis* preferred eggs compared with 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of the cotton mealybug. *O. albidipennis* good fitted to holling type II functional responses for each stage of this predator. The increasing in prey densities lead to increase in the search efficiency (a), decreasing in handling time (T_h) and increasing the predation efficiency of different stages of *O. albidipennis*. The handling time was shorter when fed on 2nd nymphal instar than the eggs and 1st nymphal instar (0.026, 0.0128 and 0.00926 hrs.) for 4th, 5th and females of *O. albidipennis*, respectively. As well as, the rate of successful search (a) was higher when fed on 2nd nymphal instar than other stages (0.4841, 0.8318 and 1.1664 hrs.) for 4th, 5th nymphal instars and females of *O. albidipennis*, respectively. The maximum predation rate of females of predator was higher than the other stages (80.04 d⁻¹) for eggs when compared with other stages of the cotton mealybug. As well as, the females of this predator was consumed more eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of the cotton mealybug than 4th and 5th nymphal instars of the predator. The mean numbers of consumed different stages of *P. solenopsis* were increased by increasing prey densities. So, we can use the females, 4th and 5th nymphal instars of *O. albidipennis* in controlling eggs and small nymphal stages of the cotton mealybug in greenhouse or field on vegetables crops.

Introduction

The cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis* Tinsley (Hemiptera: Sternorrhyncha: Coccoidea: Pseudococcidae) has become invasive worldwide mealybug species. This species is a polyphagous insect, it was reported to infest more than 200 plant species from almost 24

countries located in tropical and subtropical regions around the world. In Egypt, it was recorded for the first time by Abd-Rabou *et al.* (2010) and it was recorded on about 29 host plants belonging to 16 families (Abdel-Razzik *et al.*, 2015 and Nabil *et al.*, 2015).

P. solenopsis recorded about 8-12 generations a year. This mealybug species infests almost all plant parts with a destructive effect especially in heavy infestation as it sucks a large amount of plant sap which lead to plant wilt, leaves turn to yellow then dry and fall. Also, it secretes a large amount of honey dew which consider a suitable media to the growth of the black sooty mold fungi on leaves which blocks photosynthesis and respiration operation (Wu and Zhang, 2009). In 2005-2009 in India and Pakistan, *P. solenopsis* outbreak caused loss in cotton yield ranged between 30-60% (Jeyakumar *et al.*, 2009). Different natural enemies were recorded on *P. solenopsis* about 12 predators and 16 parasitoids (Attia and Awadallah, 2016 and Nabil and Hegab, 2019). That's why it was extremely important to control this pest to minimize its massive destructive effect on different plants.

Orius albidipennis Reuter (Hemiptera:Anthocoridae) is a very effective predator of many insect pests in Egypt (Sobhy *et al.*, 2010 and Al-Kherb, 2013). As well as, it has a numerous host preys such as thrips (Tan *et al.* 2013), spidermites (Zhou *et al.*, 2006), mealybugs (Elbahrawy *et al.*, 2020) and the eggs of moth (Zhou and Lei, 2002, Butler and O'Neil, 2007 and Zhou *et al.*, 2006). Mass Rearing of this predator at laboratory and releasing its nymphal stage and adults in the field and greenhouse will support the controlling of this insect pests and suppressing it's population in the field, which leads to, reduce of using pesticides (Shapiro and Ferkovich, 2006).

Numerical responses and daily prey consumption of *O. albidipennis* to different pests is very imperative studies on controlling these pest and decreasing population densities on different crops (Lia and Yano, 2010; Ganjisaffar and Thomas, 2015 and Wang *et al.*, 2018). This study will provide us the primary data about using *O. albidipennis* in biological control programs for controlling *P. solenopsis* on vegetable crops. Therefore, the present work aimed to evaluate the feeding response and predation consumption of *O. albidipennis* Reuter in different densities and stages of cotton mealybug *P. solenopsis* under laboratory conditions. As well as, the laboratory experiment was conducted to evaluate the efficacy of the predator *O. albidipennis* against *P. solenopsis* as a biological control agent which may play an important role in IPM program.

Materials and methods

1. Mass rearing of the predator *Orius albidipennis*:

O. albidipennis adults were obtained from unsprayed sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.) fields in Qalyoub region, Qalyubiya Governorate, Egypt. *O. albidipennis* had been reared under laboratory conditions at 28 ± 2 °C, 60 ± 5 % RH. and L18:D6 photoperiod. The predators were reared using the methods described by (Isenhor and Yeorgan, 1981a). Adults and nymphs of *O. albidipennis* were kept in plastic jars of (10 cm ×20 cm) covered with muslin and held in place by means of rubber bands. Each jar was provided with both small pieces of cardboard to reduce cannibalism behavior and put 2 gm of frozen *E. kuehniella* eggs as nutrition source for the enclosed predators (Bonte and De Clercq, 2008). A piece of bean pod (3cm) (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) was placed in each jar as an ovipositional substrate and piece of cotton soaked in sugar water (1:1)

(Isenhor and Yeargan, 1981 b). Eggs are inserted into the tissue of bean pods. Newly deposited eggs inside bean pods were kept in new plastic jars. Jars were examined daily until hatching. Soon after hatching; newly-hatched nymphs were carefully transferred to new plastic jars and provided with frozen eggs of *E. khunellia*.

2. Mass rearing of the prey cotton mealybug *Phenacoccus solenopsis*:

Cotton mealybug *P. solenopsis* was collected from eggplant, *Solanum melongena* L. (Solanaceae) orchards in Benha district, Qalyubiya Governorate, Egypt and placed in plastic bags. Then, the mealybugs were reared on sprouted potatoes. Potatoes tubers were placed in cartoon box (80 cm length x 45 cm width x 45 cm height). Potato tubers, *Solanum tuberosum* L. (Solanaceae) were washed thoroughly in water and put it on plastic dishes 40 cm and kept it in a refrigerator at 7°C for 10 days and then returning them to room temperature again. After three weeks, potatoes sprout of 6-8 cm height. Then the insects were transferred carefully with the aid of a fine camel hair brush to the potatoes sprouts. The mealybug females settled on potatoes sprouts started to lay eggs. The crawlers emerged out and started feeding and developed to adults. The eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars were used as a prey.

3. Predation consumption by 4th, 5th nymphal instars and females of *Orius albidipennis*:

Newly individual emerged nymphs of *O. albidipennis*. (0-12 hrs.) were collected from the stock colony which reared in laboratory and were put in separate plastic petri dishes (7 cm diameter) and provided with different densities of prey (10,15, 20, 25, 30 and 35) eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *P. solenopsis*. The number of consumed prey by 4th and 5th nymphal instars of *O. albidipennis* were checked by using a stereomicroscope (20×) after 24 hrs.

Couples of newly emerged adults (male and female) were placed separately in plastic petri dish (7cm diameter) without preys to stimulate mating occurrence. Later after 12 hrs., males were removed. Then, these dishes were supplied with different densities of prey (10, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35 individuals of eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *P. solenopsis*). The tests were conducted for a 24 hrs. period. The numbers of consumed prey by adults of *O. albidipennis* were checked by using a stereomicroscope (20×). There were 6 replicates per each cotton mealybug's density. A predator was tested only once. A control experiment was conducted of similar setups but without the predator.

4. *Orius albidipennis* functional response to *Phenacoccus solenopsis* different densities at 28 ±2 °C, 60 ± 5 % RH. and L18:D6 photoperiod:

The predation ability of the developmental stages (4th, 5th nymphal instars and females) of *O. albidipennis* feeding on eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *P. solenopsis* at various densities were compared by analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS program for Windows Version 16.0. Also, analysis of variances were used to compare differences in the mean numbers of different densities of *P. solenopsis* different stages consumed by *O. albidipennis*. The mean values of different treatments were compared using Duncan's multiple range test at probability P<0.05. The functional response data were fitted to type-II responses (Holling, 1959). Parameters of a type-II model were estimated by the Holling disc equation:

$$N_a = \frac{aTN_0}{1+aT_hN_0}$$

Where(N_a)is the number of eggs consumed,) N_0) is the initial density of eggs,) a) is the predator attack rate or

instantaneous searching rate, T is the time of exposure of predator to prey ($T = 24$ h) and T_h is the handling time.

Results and discussion

1. Predation capacity for 4th and 5th of nymphal instars and females of *Orius albidipennis* on different densities of eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* during 24 hrs. under laboratory conditions:

Predation capacity for 4th and 5th of nymphal instars and females of *O. albidipennis* on different densities of eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *P. solenopsis* at 28°C during 24 hrs. Results in Table (1) showed that there was a positive relation between the densities of mealybug and the mean number of consumed different stages of mealybug (Eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars). Where there were increase in predator consumption with the increase of the prey numbers. Also, the consumption of the *O. albidipennis* different stages to *P. solenopsis* can be arranged ascendingly as follows; 4th then 5th nymphal instar followed by females. Where females consumed higher numbers of the prey than the other nymphal instars (Figure 1).

In addition, it was clear that the consumption of the predator to the eggs of *P. solenoids* was higher than the consumption of 1st nymphalid followed by the 2nd nymphal instar. That's may be because the eggs are steady and easier to locate on the plant. Besides females of the predator prefer the egg stage of the prey where females of the predator need large portion of protein (found in eggs) for the eggs development. Statistical analysis showed that, almost there were no significant differences between mean numbers of consumed *P. solenopsis* different stages (eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars) in case of the prey densities 10 and 15 individuals in all treatments, the same was recorded between the prey densities 20 and 25

individuals and between 30 and 35 individuals. I.e. the 4th nymphal instar of *O. albidipennis* consumed about 2.57 ± 0.173 eggs when the prey density was 10 eggs with no significant difference with the prey density 15 eggs with 4.14 ± 0.295 eggs.

However, there were significant differences between the pairs of prey densities (15 and 20) individuals and (20 and 25) individuals and between (30-35) individuals. For example, the consumption of *O. albidipennis* 4th nymphal instar to mean number of *P. solenopsis* eggs in case of the densities 10 and 15 eggs has significant differences with both eggs densities 20 and 25 eggs as well both eggs densities 30 and 35 eggs with F value = 6.071. It was clear from the review of literature collected that the trials conducted to estimate the efficiency of *O. albidipennis* against *P. solenopsis* was very rare but there were other trials evaluated different preys which we can be taken as a pilot review. Kaewpadit (2018) stated that the 4th and 5th nymphal of *Orius maxidentex* Ghauri (Hemiptera: Anthocoridae) could feed on the averaged 7.17 ± 1.71 and 9.28 ± 2.27 nymphs of whiteflies, respectively. The individual adult could feed on the averaged 85.73 ± 32.61 nymphs of whiteflies under laboratory conditions. Sánchez *et al.* (2018) in Spain, they mentioned that *O. laevigatus* preyed on the eggs and larvae of *Spodoptera exigua* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) as well as the 4th and 5th nymphal instars had a greater consumption of eggs than younger ones. The intrinsic rate of natural increase did not differ between *O. laevigatus* fed with *S. exigua* eggs and those offered eggs of the substitute host *Ephestia kuehniella* (Zeller) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). Thus, *O. laevigatus* is a good candidate for the biological control of *S. exigua*, a cosmopolitan pest of many crops. They

mentioned that *O. laevigatus* preyed on the eggs and larvae of *S. exigua* as well as the 4th and 5th nymphal instar had a greater consumption of eggs than younger ones. The intrinsic rate of natural increase did not differ

between *O. laevigatus* fed with *S. exigua* eggs and those offered eggs of the substitute host *E. kuehniella*. Thus, *O. laevigatus* is a good candidate for the biological control of *S. exigua*, a cosmopolitan pest of many crops.

Table (1): Predation capacity for 4th, 5th of nymphal instars and females of *Orius albidipennis* on different densities of eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* at 28°C during 24hrs.

Predator stages	Mean No. of <i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> consumed			
	Densities of prey	Mean No. of consumed <i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> eggs±SE	Mean No. of consumed <i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> 1 st nymphal instar ±SE	Mean No. of consumed <i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> 2 nd nymphal instar ±SE
4 th Nymphal instar	10	2.57±0.173a	1.14±0.163a	0.28±0.129a
	15	4.14±0.295a	2.0±0.310a	1.05±0.173a
	20	6.42±0.369b	3.14±0.463a	2.07±0.275b
	25	8.71±0.258b	4.85±0.129b	2.47±0.264b
	30	10.09±0.632c	5.42±0.238b	3.85±0.163c
	35	12.85±0.547c	8.42±0.258c	6.42±0.369c
F value		6.071	3.71	1.093
5 th Nymphal instar	10	6.14±0.12a	4.66±0.13a	3.9±0.15a
	15	9.57±0.23a	7.28±0.17a	5.71±0.13a
	20	12.85±0.37b	10.14±0.23b	8.85±0.16a
	25	17.14±0.33b	11.71±0.47b	10.29±0.17b
	30	20.14±0.51c	15.36±0.54c	12.57±0.32b
	35	24.28±1.28c	20.71±0.57c	17.0±0.40c
F value		11.615	24.848	10.292
Females	10	11.57±0.31a	8.714±0.21a	5.85±0.21a
	15	16.71±0.588a	11.0±0.42a	7.85±0.47a
	20	20.57±0.435b	13.57±0.61b	10.57±0.25b
	25	24.04±0.282b	17.42±0.25b	12.28±0.55b
	30	26.85±0.310c	19.71±0.34c	14.57±0.40c
	35	30.0±0.489c	23.71±0.60c	16.85±0.40c
F value		12.240	11.708	9.46

In the same column, figures followed by the same letters are not significantly differed by Duncan's Multiple (1955) Range Test, P= 0.05.

Figure (1 A, B, C): Mean No. of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* consumed by *Orius albidipennis* under laboratory conditions during 24 hrs.

2. Functional response of 4th and 5th and females of *Orius albidipennis* to different densities of eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* during 24 hrs. under laboratory conditions:

Data in Table (2) obtained from logistic regression analysis revealed that the functional response of 4th, 5th nymphal instars and females of *O. albidipennis* were fitted to Type II

(Holling, 1959), the functional response curves of different stages of *O. albidipennis* on *Ph. solenopsis* were shown in Figures (2-4) and all parameters of a type-II functional response were estimated by the Holling's disc equation. The handling times (T_h) of 4th nymphal instar of *O. albidipennis* when fed on eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal stages of *P. solenopsis* were 0.03583, 0.02940 and 0.02662 h,

respectively, and the attack rates (a) were 0.3581, 0.4075 and 0.4841 h⁻¹, respectively (Figure 2). For 5th nymphal instar when fed on eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *P. solenopsis* the handling time were 0.0237, 0.0155 and 0.0128 h, respectively, and the attack rates were 0.7215, 0.8318 and 0.8704 h⁻¹ (Figure 3). The handling time for females of *O. albidipennis* when fed on eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *P. solenopsis* were 0.0125, 0.00987 and 0.00926 h, respectively and the attack rate were 0.8925, 1.0761 and 1.1664 h, respectively (Figure 4). The Predation efficiency for 4th nymphal instar of this predator when fed on eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *P. solenopsis* were 20.34, 12.10 and 9.74 individuals, respectively. Whereas, the predation efficiency for 5th nymphal stages of this predator when fed on eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *P. solenopsis* were 53.84, 43.32 and 36.48 individuals, respectively. Finally, The Predation efficiency for females of *O. albidipennis* when fed on eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of cotton mealybugs were 55.40, 44.0 and 40.1 individuals, respectively. The expected maximum consumption/ day for 4th nymphal instar of *O. albidipennis*. As well as, the expected consumption of for females of *O. albidipennis* were 80.04, 74.07 and 55.07 individuals respectively. In this paper, the number of consumed eggs or nymphs of *P. solenopsis* by different stages of *O. albidipennis* increased with increasing prey density. As well as, the functional responses of *O. albidipennis* to different densities of the eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of cotton mealybugs were type II. Also, we found that the increasing in prey density lead to increase in attack rate and decreasing in handling time. Results indicate that, *O. albidipennis* preferred feeding on eggs and 1st nymphal instar than 2nd nymphal

instars. As well as, the females of *O. albidipennis* consumed more eggs, 1st and 2nd than 4th and 5th nymphal instars. In many researches, indicated that, *Orius* spp. was fitted in type II functional response (Holling, 1965 and Serkan *et al.*, 2020). Whereas, Hassanzadeh *et al.* (2015) reported that, *O. albidipennis* showed type II functional response to different densities of *Tetranychus turkestanii* Ugarov and Nikolski (Acari: Tetranychidae). As well as, Kasap and Atlihan (2011) indicated that the consumption rate of predators is related to prey size. *Stethorus* species feed on all prey life stages, but eggs usually are consumed in the largest numbers (Houck, 1991) because eggs are immobile and it easy to handle than other stages and therefore predators must consume more eggs to take their needs of nutrients. On the other hand, functional response is very important tool for evaluating the role of natural enemies in biological control program and the behavior of predators on controlling pests. To evaluate the effectiveness of a predator in relation to its prey, handling time is very important parameter to show how long a predator takes to capture and kill its prey (Atlihan *et al.*, 2010). The handling time was shortest when adult female *O. strigicollis* were offered *T. vaporariorum* nymphs. The handling time was higher when adult female *O. albidipennis* fed on nymphs of *B. tabaci* (Shahpouri *et al.*, 2019). This study showed that, the handling time was shortened when females of *O. albidipennis* fed on 2nd nymphal instars of cotton mealybugs. Increasing in prey densities due to increase in the predator attack rates and reducing handling time (Hassell *et al.*, 1977).

It can be concluded that *O. albidipennis* showed an efficiency as a predator against *P. solenopsis* under laboratory conditions therefore it

encourage further application under field conditions as an effective and successful biological control agent where the adult females proved an influential predation against the mealybug *P. solenopsis* especially the egg stage therefore it can be included in the integrated pest management program (IPM). As well as, 4th, 5th nymphal stages and females of *O. albidipennis* showed type II of functional responses to different densities of cotton mealybugs *P. solenopsis* under laboratory conditions. Females of *O. albidipennis* was more effective in feeding on eggs and 1st

nymphs than the larger nymphs. As well as, females of *O. albidipennis* consumed more *P. solenopsis* different stages than nymphs of predator. Increasing in density of preys causes increasing in attack rate and predation efficiency. This study in evaluating the response and studying the behavior of *O. albidipennis* in controlling *P. solenopsis* which cause various damage on vegetables crop. Biological control by using the *O. albidipennis* will be the most effective method to control *P. solenopsis* on greenhouse or on the field.

Table (2): Effect of different densities of eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of the cotton mealybugs, and *Phenacoccus solenopsis* on the parameters of functional response of 4th, 5th nymphal instars band females of the predator *Orius albidipennis* under laboratory conditions

Predator stages	<i>Phenacoccus solenopsis</i> stages	Coefficient of correlation (r)	The rate of successful search	Handling time (T _h)	Predation efficiency	The expected maximum consumption/ day	R ²	χ ²	P -value
			(a)						
4 th Nymphal instar	Egg	0.995	0.3581	0.03583	20.34	30.63	0.9909	0.564	0.01513
	1 st	0.989	0.4075	0.0294	12.1	25.4	0.9988	0.721	0.02932
	2 nd	0.995	0.4841	0.02662	9.74	20.16	0.9995	1.012	<0.0001
5 th Nymphal instar	Egg	0.972	0.7215	0.0237	53.84	74.62	0.9844	0.971	0.03066
	1 st	0.996	0.8318	0.0155	43.32	64.51	0.9933	0.664	0.03641
	2 nd	0.982	0.8704	0.0128	36.48	43.85	0.9645	0.845	0.05971
Female	1 st	0.999	1.0761	0.00987	44	74.07	0.999	1.194	<0.0001
	2 nd	0.981	1.1664	0.00926	40.1	55.07	0.9639	1.068	<0.0001

Figure (2 A, B , C): Functional response of 4th of *Orius albidipennis* to eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* under laboratory conditions.

Figure (3 A, B , C): Functional response of 5th of *Orius albidipennis* to eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* under laboratory conditions.

Figure (4 A, B , C): Functional response of female of *Orius albidipennis* to eggs, 1st and 2nd nymphal instars of *Phenacoccus solenopsis* under laboratory conditions.

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Impact of some plant seeds and kernels against adults of the white garden snail *Theba pisana* and the brown garden snail *Eobania vermiculata* (Gastropoda: Helicidae) and their effects on activity of amylase and invertase enzymes

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 19/7/2020

Accepted: 14/9/2020

Keywords

Snails, *Theba pisana*, *Eobania vermiculata*, amylase enzyme and invertase enzyme.

Abstract:

The molluscicidal impact of apple seeds *Malus domestica* L., Sinai peach kernels *Prunus persica* L. and amar apricot kernels *Prunus armeniaca* L. were assessed against adults of the white garden snail *Theba pisana* (Müller) and the brown garden snail *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) using baits technique under laboratory conditions. Data indicated that mortality percentages of *T. pisana* and *E. vermiculata* snails were (0.0, 0.0, 6.67 %) and (0.0, 0.0, 0.0 %) for apple seeds powder at concentrations 3.75, 7.50 and 15 %, respectively. While, peach kernels powder mortalities were (6.67, 13.33, 33.33 %) and (0.0, 6.67, 13.33 %) at the same concentrations, respectively. Whereas, mortality percentages of apricot kernels powder were (20.00, 53.33, 100 %) and (6.67, 13.33, 40.00 %) at the same concentrations, respectively, after three weeks of treatment. Apricot kernels gave the highest molluscicidal effect, due to the presence of the amygdalin compound in apricot kernels more quantitative than peach kernels and apple seeds. So, amygdalin compound was used against adults of *T. pisana* and *E. vermiculata* snails. Results revealed that mortality percentages of adults of *T. pisana* and *E. vermiculata* snails using amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels were (26.67, 40.00, 73.33, 100 %) and (0.00, 6.67, 13.33, 33.33 %) at concentrations 0.375, 0.750, 1.5 and 3 %, respectively after three weeks of treatment, due to *E. vermiculata* snail more weight than *T. pisana* snail. As regards, high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) used for verification of amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels. Finally, biochemical studies stated that decrease in the activity of amylase and invertase enzymes in adults of *T. pisana* and *E. vermiculata* snails treated with amygdalin separated from apricot kernels compared to control at concentrations 0.375, 0.750, 1.5 and 3 %.

Introduction

Land snails such as the white garden snail *Theba pisana* (Müller) and the brown garden snail *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae), feed on a wide variety of

plants, including cereals, vegetables, fruits, herbs, many ornamentals. They destroying seedlings, stunting growth, and reducing yields. Not only do they directly damage the plants they feed on

but the wounds they create allow plant pathogenic fungi to infect plants. The snails can also be vectors of various plant pathogens, and their mucus trails can contaminate grains, vegetables, fruits, and herbs. In large numbers, their bodies and shells can be contaminants of mechanically harvested crops. The importance of land snails as pest organisms has drastically increased in the past few decades (Godan, 1983; Garthwaite and Thomas, 1996 and Barker, 2002). Terrestrial gastropods are from the most significant threats to sustainable agriculture around the world (Barker, 2002). Furthermore, damage caused by snails is due mainly to feed and to contaminate with their bodies, faces or slime, leading to deterioration of the product quality besides and the financial loss (Lglesias *et al.*, 2003). The terrestrial snails were recorded to be harmful snails in many districts of Egypt attacking various plants (Eshra, 2013). Jeyaratnam (1990) found that about 25 million agricultural workers in developing countries are poisoned every year by pesticides. Wherefore, used of natural baits as plant seeds against land snails. Also, natural products from plant origin have received much attention as potentially useful bio-active compounds to develop alternatives to the conventional pesticides (Singh and Singh, 2004 and Gabr *et al.*, 2006).

The aim of this research is to study efficiency of plant seeds powder such as some the Rosaceae family seeds against the white garden snail *T. pisana* and the brown garden snail *E. vermiculata* adults and their effects on changes in amylase and invertase enzymes activities using poison bait technique of amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels under laboratory condition.

Materials and methods

1. Tested animals:

Land snail, the white garden snail *T. pisana* and the brown garden snail *E. vermiculata* adults were collected from orchard cultivated with navel orange, *Citrus sinensis* L. at Menia El-Kamh district, Sharkia Governorate, Egypt. The collected snails were immediately transferred in white cloth bags to the laboratory. Healthy and similar individuals were chosen and kept in glass terrarium filled with moist clay soil adjusted at 75 % of water field capacity. Snails were fed daily with bran for two weeks before treatment for acclimatization.

2. Tested seeds and kernels :

Seeds and kernels used were anna apple seeds *Malus domestica* L. cultivated in Egypt, Sinai peach kernels *Prunus persica* L. cultivated in Sinai, Egypt and amar apricot kernels *Prunus armeniaca* L. cultivated in Egypt. All of seeds and kernels purchased from the local market. Seeds and kernels are members of the family Rosaceae.

3.Toxicity studies:

3.1. Preparation of tested seeds and kernels:

Apple seeds, peach kernels and apricot kernels pulled out fruit, and then dried at room temperature for 6 days. After the outer shells of kernel have been cracked out. Seeds and kernels dried previously are pulverized by means of a blender.

3.2. Poisonous baits technique:

Three concentrations 3.75, 7.50, and 15 % for tested seeds and kernels powder and four concentrations 0.375, 0.750, 1.5 and 3 % for amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels were prepared by incorporating the appropriate amount of each compound with bran bait. Three plastic boxes (3/4 kg capacity) were used for each concentration. Five grams of baits were spread into each box. Control treatment was prepared using bran bait. Five adult individuals of *T. pisana* and *E. vermiculata* snails were put into each

plastic box, then covered with muslin cloth and secured with rubber band. Dead individuals were counted using stainless steel needle according to **El-Okda (1980)**. Mortality percentages were calculated after 1, 3, 7, 14 and 21 days and corrected by **Abbott's formula (1925)**.

4. Chemical analysis:

4.1. Sampling and extraction procedure for apricot fruits:

Kernels are pulled out fruits, and then dried at room temperature for 6 days to achieve standard drying and subsequently kept in electrical oven at 30 °C for 24 hrs. After the outer shells of the apricot kernel have been cracked out, the extracted kernels dried previously are pulverized by means of a blender. 5 gram of each sample is extracted three times with 100 mL iso-propanol using soxhlet technique for 3 h at 90 °C. The contents are passed through a filter paper (Wattmann 42), and then the extract is set aside for 72 hrs. until amygdalin compound precipitate settle down. The product is washed out three times with ethylic ether to obtain a dry powder of amygdalin compound (Muhammad *et al.*, 2013).

4.2. High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis of amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels using an amygdalin compound standard was purchased from sigma-Aldrich (USA):

Amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels analyzed by HPLC Chromatograph YL-9100 system with LC-18 (250 mm × 4.6 mm × 5µm). The mobile phase used was methanol: acetonitrile : Water 30 : 30 : 40 (v/v), at a 1 ml / min. The detection was made at wave length of 220 nm. Analyzes were performed at Micro Analytical Center, Cairo University, Giza Governorate, Egypt.

5. Biochemical studies:

5.1.Preparation of snails for biochemical assay:

The mollusca shells of adults of *T. pisana* and *E. vermiculata* snails were removed and the soft tissues were weighed, pooled, and homogenized as 1:10 (w/v) in distilled water. The homogenates were centrifuged at 5000 r.p.m for 20 minutes at 5 °C according to Abd El-Haleim *et al.* (2006). The supernatants were immediately assayed to determine the activities of amylase and invertase enzymes by the method of Ishaaya and Swiriski (1976).

6. Statistical analysis:

The statistical analysis was determined by using one-way test, (ANOVA), **Cohort Software (2005)**.

Results and discussion

1. Impact of apple seeds, peach kernels and apricot kernels powder against adults of *Theba pisana* and *Eobania vermiculata* snails:

Data presented in Tables (1 and 2) indicated that after three weeks, mortalities of adults of *T. pisana* and *E. vermiculata* snails were (0.0, 0.0, 6.67 %) and (0.0, 0.0, 0.0 %) with apple seeds powder at concentrations 3.75, 7.50 and 15 %, respectively. While, peach kernels powder mortalities were (6.67, 13.33, 33.33 %) and (0.0, 6.67, 13.33 % %) at the same concentrations, respectively. In the case of mortality percentages of apricot kernels powder were (20.00, 53.33, 100 %) and (6.67, 13.33, 40.00 %) at the same concentrations, respectively. Results revealed that apricot kernels powder exhibited the highest mortality action followed by peach kernels powder while, apple seeds powder gave the lowest effect, due to the presence of the amygdalin in apricot kernels more percentage than peach kernels or apple seeds. Moreover, results revealed a highly significance between the three concentrations of tested snails by time elapsing except one day of *T. pisana* snail and one day and three days of *E.*

vermiculata snail compared control. The results agreed with those obtained by Vickery *et al.* (1987) found that amygdalin compound is considered a main component of apricot kernel. However, its toxic cyanogenic glycosides. Geller *et al.* (2006) showed that consumption of cyanogenic plants, such as apricot kernels in humans , have been reported to cause both acute and sub-acute health problems (Depending on dose) such as headache, nausea, vomiting, abdominal cramps, dizziness, weakness, mental confusion, convulsions, cardiac arrest, respiratory failure, coma and in extreme causes death. Silem *et al.* (2006) mentioned that amygdalin compound contain high

amount of cyanogenetic glycoside might cause acute or chronic toxicity in animals. Donald (2009) explained that amygdalin compound is a cyanogenic glycoside present in kernels and seeds of fruits such as apples, apricots, almonds, cherries, plums and peaches. Halenar *et al.* (2013) indicated that amygdalin compound is a major component of the seeds of Prunasin family plants such as apricots, almonds, peaches, apples and other rosaceous plants. Bolarinwa *et al.* (2014) reported that amygdalin compound content of seeds and kernels from Rosaceae species were 14.37 mg/g of apricot kernels, 6.81 mg/g of peach kernels and 2.96 mg/g of apple seeds.

Table (1): Impact of apple seeds, peach kernels and apricot kernels powder on adults of *Theba pisana* snail using baits technique under laboratory conditions.

Days Seeds and kernels	Concentrations	Mortality percentages				
		One day	Three days	One week	Two weeks	Three weeks
Apple powder seeds	3.75 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^e	0.00 ^f
	7.50 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^e	0.00 ^f
	15 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d	6.67 ^{de}	6.67 ^{ef}
Peach powder kernels	3.75 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^e	6.67 ^{ef}
	7.50 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^d	6.67 ^{cd}	13.33 ^{cd}	13.33 ^{de}
	15 %	0.00 ^b	6.67 ^c	13.33 ^c	20.00 ^c	33.33 ^c
Apricot powder kernels	3.75 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^d	6.67 ^{cd}	13.33 ^{cd}	20.00 ^d
	7.50 %	0.00 ^b	13.33 ^b	26.67 ^b	40.00 ^b	53.33 ^b
	15 %	13.33 ^a	40.00 ^a	60.00 ^a	86.67 ^a	100 ^a
Control		0.00 ^b	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^e	0.00 ^f
LSD _{0.05}		3.59*	6.22***	8.03***	8.81***	*** 8.78

Table (2): Impact of apple seeds, peach kernels and apricot kernels powder on adults of *Eobania vermiculata* snail using baits technique under laboratory conditions.

Days Seeds and kernels	Concentrations	Mortality percentages				
		One day	Three days	One week	Two weeks	Three weeks
Apple powder seeds	3.75 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c
	7.50 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c
	15 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c
Peach powder kernels	3.75 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c
	7.50 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^{bc}
	15 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^{bc}	13.33 ^b
Apricot powder kernels	3.75 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^{bc}
	7.50 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	6.67 ^b	13.33 ^b	13.33 ^b
	15 %	6.67 ^a	6.67 ^a	20.00 ^a	33.33 ^a	40.00 ^a
Control		0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^e	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c
LSD _{0.05}		3.58*	3.58*	5.08***	6.22***	8.03***

2. High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) study:

HPLC is used for proving of amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels by the comparison the retention time of the standard amygdalin with that amygdalin separated from apricot kernels under conditions that specified in method at 2.02 min (Figures 1, 2). Similar observations were obtained by Viorica-Mirela *et al.* (2006) reported that amygdalin quantity analyses by HPLC

method. Yan *et al.* (2006) whom found that amygdalin was successfully separated from the crude extract of *Prunus armeniaca* L. using high-speed countercurrent chromatography. Muhammad *et al.* (2013) studied that amygdalin in Iraqi plant seeds was extracted and determined by high performance liquid chromatography. Bolarinwa *et al.* (2014) applied a high-performance liquid chromatographic procedure for amygdalin quantification to investigate extraction efficiency.

Figure (1): Chromatogram of the standard amygdalin compound.

Figure (2): Chromatogram of amygdalin separated from apricot kernels.

3. Impact of amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels on adults of *Theba pisana* and *Eobania vermiculata* snails:

Results in Tables (3 and 4) showed that, mortality percentages of *T. pisana* and *E. vermiculata* snail were (6.67, 40.00, 73.33, 100 %) and (0.00, 6.67, 13.33, 33.33 %) at concentrations 0.375, 0.750, 1.5 and 3 %, respectively after three weeks of treatment using

amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels, due to *E. vermiculata* snail more weight than *T. pisana* snail. Otherwise, data found that a highly significance between the four concentrations in tested snails by time elapsing except one day and three days were no significance of *E. vermiculata* snail than control. Results agree with Walker and Kriebel (1990) reported that amygdalin compound is a toxic

cyanogenic glycoside. It is hydrolyzed by β -glucosidase into d-glucose, benzaldehyde and prussic acid (Hydrogen cyanide). Suchard *et al.* (1998) found that the ingestion of apricot kernels can thus cause cyanide poisoning. Chwalek and Ple. (2004) found that amygdalin compound is a cyanogenic glucoside initially isolated from the seeds of bitter almonds (*Prunus dulcis*). Viorica-Mirela *et al.*

(2006) reported that apricot kernels have considerable quantity of amygdalin compound is a toxic substance for human organism. Zhao (2012) explained that amygdalin compound is usually present in apricot kernels, bitter almonds and the seeds of other members of the genus *Prunus*. It is potentially dangerous because it can undergo hydrolysis to produce hydrogen cyanide (HCN).

Table (3): Impact of amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels on adults of *Theba pisana* snail using baits technique under laboratory conditions.

Days Compound	Concentrations	Mortality percentages				
		One day	Three days	One week	Two weeks	Three weeks
Amygdalin	0.375 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c	6.67 ^d	0.00 ^d	6.67 ^d
	0.750 %	0.00 ^b	6.67 ^{bc}	20.00 ^c	33.33 ^c	40.00 ^c
	1.50 %	0.00 ^b	13.33 ^b	33.33 ^b	53.33 ^b	73.33 ^b
	3.00 %	20.00 ^a	33.33 ^a	60.00 ^a	100 ^a	100 ^a
Control		0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^e	0.00 ^e
LSD _{0.05}		5.43***	9.39***	10.85***	9.39***	9.40***

Table (4): Impact of amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels on adults of *Eobania vermiculata* snail using baits technique under laboratory conditions.

Days Compound	Concentrations	Mortality percentages				
		One day	Three days	One week	Two weeks	Three weeks
Amygdalin	0.375 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c
	0.750 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	6.67 ^{bc}
	1.50 %	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	6.67 ^{ab}	6.67 ^{ab}	13.33 ^b
	3.00 %	6.67 ^a	6.67 ^a	13.33 ^a	26.67 ^a	33.33 ^a
Control		0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c
LSD _{0.05}		5.42 ^{ns}	5.42 ^{ns}	7.67**	7.67**	9.39***

4. Biochemical studies:

Results in Tables (5 and 6) found remarked decrease in the activity of amylase and invertase enzymes in adults of *T. pisana* and *E. vermiculata* snails treated with amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels compared to control. The decreasing percentages reached its maximum level for tested snails by time elapsing were recorded (-19.33, - 29.48, - 52.32 and - 61.91) and (- 12.38, - 29.85, - 50.09 and - 60.70) of amylase and invertase enzymes for *T. pisana* snail, at concentrations 0.375, 0.750, 1.5 and 3 %, respectively after one week of treatment, (-9.16, - 10.04, - 42.22 and - 50.21) and (- 6.12, - 11.09,

- 40.93 and - 48.72) of amylase and invertase enzymes for *E. vermiculata* snail, at the same concentrations, respectively after one week of treatment. Results showed that a significance between the four concentrations in adults of *T. pisana* snail by time elapsing of amylase and invertase enzymes except three days of amylase enzyme than control. Otherwise, there were no significance between the same concentrations in adults of *E. vermiculata* snail by time elapsing except one week of the two enzymes. For instances, Farag (2012) recorded decrease in the activity of amylase and invertase enzymes in *Monacha cartusiana* (Müller)

(Gastropoda:Hygromiidae) and *E. vermiculata* snails treated with plant extracts such as castor oil compared to control. AS regards, when the route of amygdalin administration is oral then it is decomposed into prunasin by enzymes present in digestive tract after passing through the salivary and gastrointestinal stages. The major component of amygdalin in digestive fluids is prunasin which was incubated in a caco-2 cell culture system. Prunasin was decomposed into the mandelonitrile by β -glucosidase and hydroxylase through the small intestinal

wall producing hydroxymandelonitrile. Benzaldehyde is also component of amygdalin when it is decomposed by enzymes it can reduce pepsin activity and cause damage to digestive function (Heikkila and Cabbat, 1980; Shim and Kwon, 2010 and Song and Xu, 2014). Otherwise, Farag (2017) remarked increase in the activity of aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) enzymes in *M. cartusiana* snail treated with amygdalin compound compared to control.

Table (5): Changes in amylase and invertase enzymes activities in adults of *Theba pisana* snail treated with amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels using baits technique.

SA = Specific activity as (ml glucose / ml)

Enzymes Compound	Conc. (%)		Amylase			Invertase		
			One day	Three days	One week	One day	Three days	One week
Amygdalin	0.375 %	SA	19.53 ^a	18.94 ^{ab}	17.24 ^{ab}	21.79 ^{ab}	20.77 ^a	20.31 ^{ab}
		RA%	- 6.78	- 10.19	- 19.33	- 1.54	- 2.99	- 12.38
	0.750 %	SA	17.39 ^{ab}	16.83 ^{ab}	15.07 ^b	18.92 ^{ab}	17.87 ^{ab}	16.26 ^{bc}
		RA%	- 16.99	- 20.20	- 29.48	- 14.51	- 16.46	-29.85
	1.50 %	SA	14.73 ^{bc}	12.63 ^{ab}	10.19 ^{bc}	16.87 ^{bc}	14.09 ^{bc}	11.57 ^{cd}
		RA%	- 29.69	- 40.11	- 52.32	- 23.77	- 34.13	- 50.09
3 %	SA	12.63 ^c	10.59 ^b	8.14 ^c	13.23 ^c	11.13 ^c	9.11 ^d	
	RA%	-39.71	- 49.79	- 61.91	- 40.22	- 47.97	- 60.70	
Control		SA	20.95 ^a	21.09 ^a	21.37 ^a	22.13 ^a	21.39 ^a	23.18 ^a
L.S.D _{0.05}			3.82**	9.28 ^{ns}	8.65*	4.95*	5.81*	5.21***

RA% = (Relative activity %) = [(Treatment – Control) / Control] × 100

Table (6): Changes in amylase and invertase enzymes activities in adults of *Eobania vermiculata* snail treated with amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels using baits technique.

Enzymes Compound	Conc. (%)		Amylase			Invertase		
			One day	Three days	One week	One day	Three days	One week
Amygdalin	0.375 %	SA	16.76 ^a	15.92 ^{ab}	15.47 ^a	14.78 ^a	14.32 ^a	13.97 ^a
		RA%	- 0.65	-2.75	- 9.16	-3.21	- 4.34	- 6.12
	0.750 %	SA	16.01 ^a	15.33 ^{ab}	15.32 ^a	14.49 ^a	13.76 ^{ab}	13.23 ^a
		RA%	- 5.10	- 6.35	- 10.04	-5.11	- 8.08	-11.09
	1.50 %	SA	13.63 ^a	11.76 ^{ab}	9.84 ^b	11.35 ^{ab}	10.09 ^{ab}	8.79 ^b
		RA%	- 19.21	-28.16	- 42.22	- 25.67	- 32.60	- 40.93
3 %	SA	12.03 ^a	10.93 ^b	8.48 ^b	9.57 ^b	8.31 ^b	7.63 ^b	
	RA%	- 28.69	- 33.23	- 50.21	-37.33	- 44.49	- 48.72	
Control		SA	16.87 ^a	16.37 ^a	17.03 ^a	15.27 ^a	14.97 ^a	14.88 ^a
L.S.D _{0.05}			5.21 ^{ns}	5.02 ^{ns}	5.15*	6.99 ^{ns}	5.52 ^{ns}	3.04***

SA = Specific activity as (ml glucose / ml)

RA% = (Relative activity %) = [(Treatment – Control) / Control] × 100

The presented results studied especially those contained amygdalin using some plant seeds and kernels compound for controlling of *T. pisana*

and *E. vermiculata* snails. It suggests probability of using amygdalin compound that has the possibility to play an important role as molluscicidal for snails control. Results also found that decrease in the activity of amylase and invertase enzymes in snails treated with amygdalin compound separated from apricot kernels compared to control, so leading to death of snails.

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Alteration of protein and amino acids at different developmental stages of *Schistocerca gregaria* (Orthoptera: Acrididae)

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 22/7/2020

Accepted: 29/9/2020

Keywords

Schistocerca gregaria, protein, amino acids, nymph and gender.

Abstract:

The composition changes in total protein and total amino acids (AA) of *Schistocerca gregaria* Forsskål (Orthoptera: Acrididae) were estimated according to stages and gender. The concentrations of protein and amino acids in samples showed wide range variations. Results showed that *S. gregaria* contained high amount of total protein contents (49.64 – 67.9% of dry matter). Seventeen amino acids were detected as the basic components of proteins, which play an important role in insect metabolism they were; threonine (Thr), valine (Val), methionine (Met), isoleucine (Ile), leucine (Leu), phenylalanine (Phe), lysine (Lys), histidine (His), arginine (Arg), cysteine (Cys), aspartic acid (Asp), serine (Ser), glutamic acid (Glu), glycine (Gly), alanine (Ala), tyrosine (Tyr) and proline (Pro). The results revealed the AA possibly divided based on essentiality: essential, semi-essential and non-essential; which average concentrations in males and females were 1.94-2.42 and 2.19-2.44 mg/100 mg, respectively. Semi-essential with the average concentrations in both sex's males and females were 1.5- 1.71 and 1.46-1.7 mg/100 mg. And non-essential AA its average concentrations in males and females were 3.24-3.89 and 3.53-4.04 mg/100 mg respectively. Also, another possibly divided based on the concentrations as high >3, moderate >2 and low <2 mg/100 mg. Differences of amino acids were found during developmental stages and sexual maturation. The average concentrations of AA showed detraction of the immature and mature stages of two sexes comparing with the first nymphal stages. The present investigations could give a sight about the physiology of total protein and AA in *S. gregaria*.

Introduction

The desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria* Forsskål (Orthoptera: Acrididae) is an economically damaging pest of a wide range of crops, mainly cereals in the Sahel region of Africa. It occurs in many parts of Africa and Asia. *S. gregaria* plagues can be an

important contributing factor to famines and a threat to food security in many regions of the world (FAO, 2012). The most important functions of amino acids, the building blocks of the proteins that are derived from the insect diet, include the synthesis of structural

proteins of the integument and the synthesis of hormones and enzymes that participate in the synthesis nucleic acids (Klowden, 2007). Amino acids are also required by insects for transport and storage and as receptor molecules. Besides, some amino acids are involved in morphogenesis (Chapman, 2002). The pattern of hemolymph amino acids can be modified by development, oogenesis, feeding, cuticular tanning, silk production, or flight activity (Blum, 1985).

The present study was designed to evaluate total protein and total amino acids which play an important role in physiology, metabolism and development at different developmental stages in *S. gregaria* at both sexes.

Materials and methods

1. Mass rearing of insects:

This study has been executed in the laboratory of locust and Grasshopper Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, ARC, Dokki, Giza. The insects were maintained in the laboratory under crowded and controlled conditions at $30\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 30-65% RH and reared according to Robert *et al.* (2002).

2. Biochemical analysis:

2.1. Sample preparation for the assay of total protein and amino acids:

This study was conducted to estimate protein and amino acids (AA) content in different insect stages and sexes. Groups of 50 hoppers of 1st instar to 4th nymphal instars were used as one sample but separation according to gender started with 5th instar. The whole insects of each stage were collected individually, then refrigerated and stored at -5°C and then dehydrated in the oven 48-72h at $55-60^{\circ}\text{C}$. Samples were homogenized to get homogenate dry powder. Homogenates were weighted and kept until the biochemical determinations (Ahmed *et al.*, 2019 and Abd-El Wahed and Ahmad, 2019).

2.2. Analysis of total protein content and amino acids:

Determination of proteins and amino acids was carried out at Regional Center for Food and Feed, ARC, Giza, according to AOAC (2012). The Kjeldahl method was used for protein determination. Amino acids were determined by high perform Amino Acid analyzer (Biochrom 30) and EZ chrome manual (software for data collection and processing).

Results and discussion

1. Total protein in body homogenate of *Schistocerca gregaria* :

The values of total protein in the *S. gregaria* of males and females of different ages are shown in Figure (1) . In general, the percentage of total protein content was higher in nymphal instar compared with adults stages. Data presented in Figure (1) shows that the content of total protein was 66.63% of dry matter in the interval from 1st to 4th instar. At 5th instar this value decreased in the males to 61.06% of dry matter and increased in the female to 67.9% of dry matter. This decreasing continued until immature stage where the total protein recorded 61 and 60.27% % of dry matter in the adults immature in both males and females, respectively. Also found sharply diminishing of protein content of mature adult males and females 49.64 and 56.24%, respectively.

The increasing at 5th nymphal females in protein content of *S. gregaria* may be due to proteins represent the main component of the nutrient composition and development of insects, overall, that showed solid agreement with Abd-El Wahed and Ahmad (2019), they reported, the protein percentages in both adults and nymphs of *S. gregaria* contained more than 55%, but in nymphs were higher than adults the values were 65.92 and 56.79%, respectively. The highest percentage of protein 76 and 70% were

found in *S. gregaria* and the cricket *Grylloides sigillatus* (tropical house cricket), respectively (Ewelina *et al.*, 2015). Similar value (77%) was shown by Ramos-Elorduy *et al.* (1997) for *Sphenarium histrio* Gerstaecker (Orthoptera: Pyrgomorphidae) and,

slightly lower (61%) for *Schistocerca* sp. The content of protein in *Tenebrio molitor* (Orthoptera: Tenebrionidae) (mealworm beetle) was 52.35% and this value is comparable with the results of Rumpold and Schlüter (2013).

Figure (1): The percentage of total protein in total body homogenate of *Schistocerca gregaria*. 1st to 4th nymphal instar, 5th nymphal instar males (5th M), 5th nymphal instar females (5th F), Adult immature males (AImM), Adult immature females (AImF), Adult mature males (AMM), Adult mature females (AMF) based on dry matter.

2. Total amino acids of *Schistocerca gregaria* at different stages:

According to the obtained data in Tables (1 and 2) and Figure (2), seventeen amino acids were detected; threonine (Thr), valine (Val), methionine (Met), isoleucine (Ile), leucine (Leu), phenylalanine (Phe), lysine (Lys), histidine (His), arginine (Arg), cysteine (Cys), aspartic acid (Asp), serine (Ser), glutamic acid (Glu), glycine (Gly), alanine (Ala), tyrosine (Tyr) and proline (Pro), seven are essential consisted of Thr, Val, Met, Ile, Leu, Phe and Lys; three are semi-essential: His, Arg and Cys, while seven are non-essential: Asp, Ser, Glu, Gly, Ala, Tyr & Pro, this results in full agreement with (El-Shennawy, *et al.* 2019 and Abd-El Wahed and Ahmad, 2019). The seventeen AA were identified in all stages of *S. gregaria*. AA is not only the building blocks of proteins but also key regulators of

various pathological and physiological processes (Sankar and Yogamoorthi, 2012) and including immune responses (Yoneda *et al.*, 2009). From the results, the variations of AA composition in all developmental stages of *S. gregaria*. The AA composition was detected by the changes in the percentages. The essential AA showed that Met was the smallest value in 1st to 4th instar (5.12%) while the highest value was for Leu in adult males mature and adult females immature, were 23.12% and 23.47%, respectively. Whereas in the semi-essential AA represent Cys was represented the lowest 16.02% while Arg was the highest value at 58.23% for 1st to 4th instar. But in the non-essential AA, the lowest and highest values were Ser and Ala 5.64 and 28.47%, respectively in adult males mature whilst adult females immature were 6.83 and 29.70%, respectively.

Table (1): The composition of amino acids in the total body homogenate of *Schistocerca gregaria* of 1st - 4th to immature and mature adult male.

Amino acids AA	1 st to 4 th instar		5 th instar			Adult (immature and mature)					
	AA con.	%	AA con.	%	% Change than 1 st to 4 th instar	AA con.	%	% Change than 5 th instar	AA con.	%	% Change than adult immature
Essential											
Threonine (Thr)	2.09	12.74	1.91	12.16	8.61	2.1	12.40	-9.95	1.49	10.97	29.05
Valine (Val)	3.27	19.93	3.3	21.01	-0.92	3.27	19.30	0.91	2.74	20.18	16.21
Methionine (Met)	0.84	5.12	0.81	5.16	3.57	1.25	7.38	-54.32	0.84	6.19	32.80
Isoleucine (Ile)	2.11	12.86	2.08	13.24	1.42	2.2	12.99	-5.77	1.92	14.14	12.73
Leucine (Leu)	3.56	21.69	3.47	22.09	2.53	3.71	21.90	-6.92	3.14	23.12	15.36
Phenylalanine (Phe)	1.61	9.81	1.55	9.87	3.73	1.59	9.37	-2.58	1.29	9.50	18.88
Lysine (Lys)	2.93	17.86	2.59	16.49	11.60	2.82	16.65	-8.88	2.16	15.91	23.40
Sum	16.41		15.71			16.94			13.58		
Average	2.34		2.24			2.42			1.94		
Semi-essential											
Histidine (His)	1.19	25.76	1.17	22.81	1.68	1.17	24.63	0	0.98	21.78	16.24
Arginine (Arg)	2.69	58.23	2.66	51.85	1.12	2.69	56.63	-1.13	2.33	51.78	13.38
Cystine (Cys)	0.74	16.02	1.3	25.34	-75.68	0.89	18.74	31.54	1.19	26.44	-33.71
Sum	4.62		5.13			4.75			4.5		
Average	1.54		1.71			1.58			1.5		
Non-essential											
Aspartic acid (Asp)	3.93	14.74	3.73	14.26	5.09	3.92	14.41	-5.09	3.05	13.44	22.19
Serine (Ser)	2.18	8.18	1.83	7.01	16.06	2.07	7.61	-13.11	1.28	5.64	38.16
Glutamic acid (Glu)	6	22.51	5.42	20.76	9.67	5.86	21.54	-8.12	4.47	19.70	23.72
Glycine (Gly)	2.64	9.90	2.75	10.53	-4.17	2.96	10.88	-7.64	2.49	10.97	15.88
Alanine (Ala)	6.13	22.99	6.69	25.62	-9.14	7.04	25.87	-5.23	6.46	28.47	8.24
Tyrosin (Tyr)	2.75	10.32	2.7	10.34	1.82	2.11	7.76		2	8.82	5.21
Proline (Pro)	3.03	11.37	2.99	11.45	1.32	3.25	11.94		2.94	12.96	9.54
Sum	26.66		26.11			27.21			22.69		
Average	3.81		3.73			3.89			3.24		

*Con.=Concentration

$$\% \text{Change} = \frac{\text{Treatment} - \text{Control}}{\text{Control}} \times 100$$

Data expressed as mg/100mg of dry matter.

Table (2) The composition of amino acids in the total body homogenate of *Schistocerca gregaria* of 1st - 4th to immature and mature adult females

Amino Acids AA	1 st to 4 th Instar		5 th instar			Adult (immature and mature)					
	AA con.	%	AA con.	%	% Change than 1 st to 4 th nymphal instar	AA con.	%	% Change than 5 th instar	AA con.	%	% Change than adult immature
Essential											
Threonine (Thr)	2.09	12.74	2.13	12.77	-1.91	1.79	11.39	15.96	1.83	11.92	-2.24
Valine (Val)	3.27	19.93	3.38	20.26	-3.36	3.33	21.20	1.479	3.02	19.67	9.31
Methionine (Met)	0.84	5.12	0.9	5.40	-7.14	0.78	4.97	13.33	0.9	5.86	-15.39
Isoleucine (Ile)	2.11	12.86	2.21	13.25	-4.74	2.16	13.75	2.26	2.07	13.49	4.17
Leucine (Leu)	3.56	21.69	3.6	21.58	-1.12	3.73	23.74	-3.61	3.55	23.13	4.83
Phenylalanine (Phe)	1.61	9.81	1.63	9.77	-1.24	1.46	9.29	10.43	1.46	9.51	0
Lysine (Lys)	2.93	17.86	2.83	16.97	3.41	2.46	15.66	13.07	2.52	16.42	-2.44
Sum	16.41		16.68			15.71			15.35		
Average	2.34		2.38			2.44			2.19		
Semi-essential											
Histidine (His)	1.19	25.76	1.26	24.66	-5.88	1.16	24.22	7.9 4	1.13	25.86	2.59
Arginine (Arg)	2.69	58.23	2.89	56.56	-7.43	2.67	55.74	7.6 1	2.49	56.98	6.74
Cystine (Cys)	0.74	16.02	0.96	18.79	-29.73	0.96	20.04	0	0.75	17.16	21.88
Sum	4.62		5.11			4.79			4.37		
Average	1.54		1.7			1.6			1.46		
Non-essential											
Aspartic acid (Asp)	3.93	14.74	4.05	14.34	-3.05	3.44	13.2	15.06	3.46	14.01	-0.58
Serine (Ser)	2.18	8.18	2.21	7.82	-1.38	1.78	6.83	19.46	1.88	7.61	-5.62
Glutamic acid (Glu)	6	22.51	6.14	21.74	-2.33	5.12	19.65	16.61	5.07	20.53	0.98
Glycine (Gly)	2.64	9.90	2.92	10.34	-10.61	2.28	8.75	21.92	2.62	10.61	-14.91
Alanine (Ala)	6.13	22.99	7.22	25.56	-17.78	7.74	29.70	-7.20	6.88	27.85	11.11
Tyrosin (Tyr)	2.75	10.36	2.32	8.21	15.64	2.49	9.56	-7.33	2.03	8.22	18.47
Proline (Pro)	3.03	11.37	3.39	12	-11.88	3.21	12.32	5.31	2.76	11.17	14.02
Sum	26.66		28.25			26.06			24.7		
Average	3.81		4.04			3.72			3.53		

*Con.=concentration

$$\% \text{Change} = \frac{\text{Treatment} - \text{Control}}{\text{Control}} \times 100$$

Data expressed as mg/100mg of dry matter.

Figure (2): The composition of amino acids in the total body homogenate of *Schistocerca gregaria*. (A) 1st to 4th nymphal instar, (B) 5th nymphal instar male, (C) 5th nymphal instar female, (D) Adult immature male, (E) Adult immature female, (F) Adult mature male, (G) Adult mature female.

The results in Table (3) revealed that in examined samples, the AA possibly divided based on the concentrations as high, moderate, and low, which were >3 , >2 , and <2 mg/100 mg, respectively. In examined samples, some of the AA was present in approximately the same amount, while others fluctuated; these fluctuations may be because of different stages of development, the same results found by (El-Shennawy *et al.*, 2019; Ahmed *et al.*, 2019 and Abd-El Wahed and Ahmad, 2019) or different sex (Kulkarni and Mehrotra, 1970). From Table (3) the high concentrations of AA (more than 3 mg/100 mg) in an essential AA fluctuated in Val between 3.38 and 3.02 mg/100 mg at the females of 5th nymphal instar and in adult mature females, respectively; also in Leu between 3.73 and 3.14 mg/100 mg at adult immature females and adult mature males, respectively. Semi-essential AA was not detected. Moreover, non-essential AA of Asp, Glu and Pro they recorded in females 5th nymphal instar were 4.05, 6.14 and 3.39 mg/100 mg, respectively, but Ala was 7.74 mg/100 mg in adult immature females; these AA fluctuated until reach low values, in Asp and Glu were 3.05 and 5.07 mg/100 mg at adult mature males and females respectively, and both of AA Ala and Pro were 6.13 and 3.03 mg/100 mg respectively, in 1st to 4th nymphal instar.

The moderate concentrations of AA (more than 2 mg/100 mg), in an essential AA of Thr and Ile their values in females of 5th nymphal instar were 2.13 and 2.21 mg/100 mg respectively;

but fluctuated between the previous values and 2.09 & 2.16 in 1st to 4th nymphal instar and in adult mature females, respectively, also the values were fluctuated in Lys AA between 2.93 and 2.46 mg/100 mg in 1st to 4th nymphal instar and an adult mature females, respectively. There was only one of AA in semi-essential it was Arg it has values between 2.89 and 2.33 mg/100 mg in females of 5th nymphal instar and adult mature males, respectively. In non-essential AA there were Ser, Gly, Tyr, and Pro with values between (2.21 and 2.07), (2.96 and 2.28), (2.75 and 2), and (2.99 and 2.76) mg/100 mg in (females of 5th nymphal instar and adult immature males), (adult immature males and females), (1st to 4th nymphal instar and adult mature males) and (males of 5th nymphal instar and adult mature females), respectively.

The low concentrations of AA (less than 2 mg/100 mg) in an essential were at Thr, Met and Phe with values (1.91 and 1.49), (1.25 and 0.78) and (1.63 and 1.29) mg/100 mg in (males of 5th nymphal instar and adult mature males), (adult immature males and females) and (females of 5th nymphal and adult immature males), respectively. However, the values of AA in semi-essential were at His and Cys their between (1.26 and 0.98) and (1.3 and 0.74) mg/100 mg in (5th nymphal instar females and adult mature males) and (5th nymphal instar males and 1st to 4th nymphal instar), respectively. As a non-essential AA Ser was 1.88 and 1.28 mg/100 mg in adult mature females and males, respectively.

Table (3): Summarized data for the concentration of amino acids (mg/100mg) in the total body homogenate of *Schistocerca gregaria*.

Amino acids			1 st to 4 th nymphal instar	5 th nymphal instar		Adult immature		Adult mature	
				Males	Females	Males	Females	males	Females
>3	Essential	Val	3.27	3.3	3.38	3.27	3.33	-----	3.02
		Leu	3.56	3.47	3.6	3.71	3.73	3.14	3.55
	Semi-essential		-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	
	Non-essential	Asp	3.93	3.73	4.05	3.92	3.44	3.05	3.46
		Glu	6	5.42	6.14	5.86	5.12	4.47	5.07
	Ala	6.13	6.69	7.22	7.04	7.74	6.46	6.88	
	Pro	3.03	-----	3.39	3.25	3.21	-----	-----	
>2	Essential	Val	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	2.74	-----
		Thr	2.09	-----	2.13	2.1	-----	-----	-----
		Ile	2.11	2.08	2.21	2.2	2.16	-----	2.07
		Lys	2.93	2.59	2.83	2.82	2.46	2.16	2.52
	Semi-essential	Arg	2.69	2.66	2.89	2.69	2.67	2.33	2.49
	Non-essential	Ser	2.18	-----	2.21	2.07	-----	-----	-----
		Gly	2.64	2.75	2.92	2.96	2.28	2.49	2.49
		Tyr	2.75	2.7	2.32	2.11	-----	2	2.03
		Pro	-----	2.99	-----	-----	-----	2.94	2.76
	<2	Essential	Thr	-----	1.91	-----	-----	1.79	1.49
Met			0.84	0.81	0.9	1.25	0.78	0.84	0.9
Ile			-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	1.92	-----
Phe			1.61	1.55	1.63	1.59	1.46	1.29	1.46
Semi-essential		His	1.19	1.17	1.26	1.17	1.16	0.98	1.13
		Cys	0.74	1.3	0.96	0.89	0.96	1.19	0.75
Non-essential		Ser	-----	1.83	-----	-----	1.78	1.28	1.88

Several studies have shown that; the concentration of some AA varied during metamorphosis (Mansingh, 1967 and Mitsuhashi, 1978). Many of AA increased of immature and mature stages this observed results partially agreed with Pal *et al.* (1973) who stated that; the AA in general are more concentrated in the pupal stage, of *Euproctis fraterna* Moore (Lepidoptera: Lymantriidae) this could be due to increased proteins breakdown. The variations in the pattern of AA at various insect developmental stages revealed a shift of AA requirements during growth and development (Rock and King, 1966). Amino acid levels can also be affected by changes in the levels of other substances such as carbohydrates and their metabolic intermediates and derivatives, which

also change during metamorphosis (Somme, 1967 and Chino, 1958). Abd-El Wahed and Ahmad (2019) found that the total AA concentration in *S. gregaria* were higher in nymphs than adults, essential, semi-essential and nonessential were (16.27 and 15.40), (4.95 and 4.60), and (27.01 and 25.17) mg/100g, respectively. Dang and Doharey (1968) studied the AA compositions variations in the larval and pupal stage of *Chilo zonellus* (Swinhoe) (Lepidoptera: Crambidae) (maize borer) and have shown that free Pro, Tyr and Asp acid were absent in the larvae, but appeared in the pupae. PAL *et al.* (1973) reported that AA fluctuating between accession and detracting during metamorphosis in *E. fraterna*. These are partially agreement with this study whereas AA fluctuating

between increasing and decreasing during developmental stages of *S. gregaria* except decreasing for Met and Cys of first nymphal stages. The sulfur containing amino acids Met and Cys play important roles in cell metabolism for instance, Met initiates the protein synthesis in all eukaryotic cells (Brosnan and Brosnan, 2006). Protein synthesis is believed to be initiated with the AA Met because the Aug translation initiation codon of mRNAs is recognized by the anticodon of initiator Met transfer RNA (Sasaki and Nakashima, 2000). Furthermore, Met is a methyl and sulfur donor and an important factor for antibody response (Swain and Johri, 2000 and Bunchasak, 2009). Cys is directly involved in body sulfur transport processes, active sulfate biosynthesis, and the synthesis of taurine, coenzyme A, and Glu (Wu, 2009; Baker *et al.*, 1996 and Baker, 2006). The results showed that, the increasing in Ala concentration of mature males and immature females are believed to be involved in cuticle hardness or metamorphosis this is in agreement with Pant and Agrawal (1964), who mentioned that; the variation in AA concentration may be due to the role of transport during morphing from pupae to adult. Also, AA in hemolymph plays an important role in the synthesis of cuticle constituents and silk production. The decrease in Cys concentration during morphing from 1st to 4th instar means it could be used in developing embryo in the egg stage (Fyhn and Serigstad, 1987). Results represented in Table 2 and 3 showed increasing in Leu value of mature males and immature females of essential group. Also observed increasing in Arg concentration of 1st and 4th nymphal instar of semi-essential group. Whereas in non-essential group found decreasing in Ser concentration of mature males and immature females. The fact that Leu and Arg increased

during different developmental stages was related to its proposed function in the metabolic process in the healthy nymph or to its accumulation as guanidine derivative (Pant and Agrawal, 1964). It was observed that the decrease of Ser value of mature males and immature females is partially in agreement with Blum (1985), who reported that; the use of AA for osmoregulation may at times be passive process in which all AA increase or decrease proportionally, but the change in specific AA titers in some insects indicates active regulated processes. Amino acids have long been recognized to differ in its composition according to studied insect tissue so it could be used as a taxonomic tool (Sankar and Yogamoorthi, 2012 and Schaefer and Wallace, 1967). Besides, it also differed according to the studied insect stage and host plant (Haag and Sullivan, 1984 and Pal *et al.*, 1973), detecting method as well as insect and the insect stage (Kleiner and Peacock, 1971; Ahmed, 2020 and Abd-El Wahed and Ahmad, 2019).

Acknowledgments

Special thanks are extended to Prof. Alia Abd El-Hafez, Prof. Kariem Hassan, Dr. Dina Ahmed, and Dr. Manal El-Sharkawy from Plant Protection Research Institute, for their technical support of our study, Also Dr. Abeer Fouad from Regional Centre for Food and Feed for her help

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Insecticidal activity of diesel oil and synthetic plant materials against pink sugar cane mealybug *Saccharicoccus sacchari* (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae)

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ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 5/7 /2020

Accepted: 17 /9/2020

Keywords

Insecticidal activity, diesel oil, thymol, camphor, *Saccharicoccus sacchari* and pink sugar cane mealybug.

Abstract:

The pink sugar cane mealybug *Saccharicoccus sacchari* (Cockerell) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) is considered one of the dangerous pests of sugarcane (*Saccharum officinarum* L.). The infestation of this pest caused poor growth and yellowing of the stem and leaves. Physico-chemical properties of crude diesel oil and botanical synthetic materials (Thymol and camphor) were studied and prepared as emulsifiable concentrate formulation (EC). Prepared formulations passed successfully specified testes, then their toxicity was investigated against different stages of the pink sugar cane mealybug *S. sacchari* under laboratory conditions. Results indicated that all tested formulations showed high toxicity against all tested insect stages. The mixing, thymol or camphor with diesel oil increased toxicity of oil against *S. sacchari*, whereas mixture, thymol with diesel oil was more effective than camphor with diesel oil. LC50 values after two days of application were 4.46 and 5.01 ml/l for diesel oil, while it was 0.20 and 0.24 ml/l for mixture of oil and thymol, and 1 and 1.23 ml/l for mixture of diesel oil and camphor for nymph and adult stages of *S. sacchari* respectively. While LC50 values after three days of application were: 1.51 and 1.69 ml/l for diesel oil, while it was 0.05 and 0.12 ml/l for mixture of oil with thymol, and 0.20 and 0.17 ml/l for mixture of oil with camphor for nymph and adult stages of *S. sacchari*, respectively. Results showed that the efficacy of tested materials increased by increasing concentration and period after application. Mixing botanical synthetic materials with diesel oil increased toxicity against pink sugar cane mealybug *S. sacchari*.

Introduction

Saccharicoccus sacchari (Cockerell) (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) is the major pest in Egypt and the world. It lives on sugarcane both under-ground and on aerial stem tissue. Crawlers infest upper internodal tissue behind leaf sheaths and develop through a series of juvenile

instar stages before becoming adult. It obtains nutrition from the plant's phloem and excess carbohydrate is exuded as honeydew and the ability of *S. sacchari* to transmit virus particles. Inkerman *et al.* (1986) and Beardsley (1960) stated that the numbers of pink sugar cane mealybug increased in stem

tissue develops and heavy infestations of *S. sacchari* effect of crop yield. Later Mohamed *et al.* (2009), it effects of a reduction in juice quality. *S. sacchari* is considered as a pest of continued commercial interest (Lockhart *et al.*, 1992).

Petroleum oils are highly refined, paraffinic oils that are used to manage pests and diseases of plants. Similar paraffinic oils are found in automotive and household lubricants and cleansers. Petroleum oils may be referred to many names, including horticultural oil, spray oil, dormant oil, summer oil, supreme oil, superior oil, Volck oil or white mineral oil.

Oils have been used as pesticides for centuries and are some of the most effective, safe alternatives to synthetic insecticides and fungicides. Pesticides with mineral oil as the active ingredient are used as insecticides and acaricides for treating trees and shrubs. They are available as concentrates to be diluted before use (Cranshaw and Baxendale, 2011). Mineral oils still have the advantage of being effective against resistance of strains, and development of resistance was not recorded for mineral oils (Micks and Berlin, 1970). Plant essential oils have been long been used in perfumes and foods, and are now being used for the development of reduced risk pesticides. Essential oil-based insecticides are considered relatively safe to humans and mixtures of essential oil constituents have been proven to be effective against many insects.

The aim of this work is to study the effect diesel oil alone and its mixture with botanical synthetic materials (thymol and camphor) against different stages of the mealy bug *S. sacchari* under laboratory conditions.

Materials and methods

1- Tested chemicals:

1.1. Active ingredient:

1.1.1. Diesel oil: It is a light medium cut of petroleum oil (Solar cut), It was bought from fuel station, Cairo, Egypt.

1.1.2. Thymol extra pure (C₁₀H₁₄O): It was supplied by El- Gomhoria Co., Cairo, Egypt.

1.1.3. Camphor (C₁₀H₁₆O): was supplied by El- Gomhoria Co., Cairo, Egypt.

1.2. Solvents: Acetone, xylene and dimethyl formamide., were supplied by El- Gomhoria Co., Cairo, Egypt.

1.3. Surface active agents: Toximol, Toximol-R and Toximol-H., were supplied by El- Gomhoria Co., Cairo, Egypt. Poly ethylene glycol 600 di-lurate., were supplied by the Egyptian Starch, Yeast and Detergents Co., Alexandria, Egypt.

2. The physico-chemical properties of the basic formulation components:

2.1. Active ingredient:

2.1.1. Solubility:

It was measured by calculating the volume of distilled water, acetone and xylene for complete solubility or miscibility of one gram of active ingredient at 20 °C (Nelson and Fiero, 1954).

2.1.2. Free acidity or alkalinity:

It was measured by using the method described by WHO specification (1979).

2.2. Surface active agents:

2.2.1. Surface tension:

It was measured using surface tensiometer for solutions at 0.5 % (W/V) surfactant according to ASTM D-1331 (2001).

2.2.2. Critical micelle concentration (CMC):

The (CMC) of the tested surfactants was measured by using the method reported by (Osipow, 1964).

2.2.3. Hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB):

The (HLB) of the tested surfactants were measured by using the method reported by (Lynch and Griffin, 1974). Free acidity or alkalinity: It was

measured by using the method that mentioned above.

2.3. Preparation of diesel oil and mixed with 10% thymol and 10% camphor oil as emulsifiable concentrates (EC):

Emulsifiable concentrates a liquid formulation contains technical material, organic water-immiscible solvents and emulsifiers (surface active agents). When EC formulations are diluted with water in a spray tank, they form a spontaneous emulsion. For preparing diesel oil, diesel oil + thymol and diesel oil + camphor in form of emulsifiable concentrate formulation, several trials were carried out as follow: Diesel oil and its mixtures prepared as ECs by adding different weights to other different weights of suitable emulsifier or blend of emulsifier and stirring to homogeneity. Emulsion stability test was done for all formulated formulas by using the method reported by CIPAC MT 36.1 (2002) to determine which of them will pass and suitable for application.

2.4. Determination of the physico-chemical properties of the prepared emulsifiable concentrates formulation (EC):

2.4.1. Emulsion stability: It was measured by using the method reported in CIPAC MT 36.1 (2002)

2.4.2. Persistent foam: it was determined by using the method reported in CIPAC MT 47.2 (2002).

2.4.3. Free acidity or alkalinity: It was determined by using the same method that mentioned above.

2.4.4. Stability at elevated temperature 54 ± 2 °C (accelerated storage): It was determined by using the method reported in CIPAC MT 46.3 (2002)

2.5. Determination of the physico-chemical properties of the spray solution of the local prepared formulation at the field dilution rate:

2.5.1. Surface tension: It was measured by using the method that mentioned above.

2.5.2. pH: It was measured by using Cole-Parmer pH conductivity meter 1484-44 by using the method described by Dobrat and Martijn (1995).

2.5.3. Viscosity: It was measured by using Brookfield Viscometer Model DVII+Pro, by using the method reported in ASTM D-2196 (2005).

2.5.4. Electrical conductivity: It was measured by using Cole-Parmer pH/Conductivity using the method described by Dobrat and Martijn (1995).

3. Bioassay:

Laboratory experiment:

Toxicity of the tested materials was conducted by using the method reported by Eskander *et al.* (2020) with some modifications. Samples of infested sugar cane collected randomly from infested internodes and transferred to the laboratory. The nymphs and adult individuals of pink sugar cane mealybug, *S. sacchari* using the concentrations (1, 0.5, 0.25 and 0.125 %) for the three locally prepared formulations used in the study and every concentration. Treated internodes were kept in a jar, four replicates were done for each treatment and four replicates treated by water as a control. Inspection was conducted after 24, 48 and 72 hours from treatment by counting dead and a live of the different stages of *S. sacchari* by the aid of stereomicroscope. Also, a precount was taken for each treatment as an index; percentages of mortalities were calculated according to Abbot's formula (1925).

4. Statistical analysis:

Mortality percentages were calculated according to Abbot's formula (1925). To estimate the LC₅₀ values, the corrected mortality percentages were subjected to probit analysis according to Finney (1952).

Results and discussion

1. Formulation part.

Results in Table (1) showed that diesel oil, thymol and camphor were non-soluble in water, while diesel oil was miscible in xylene and acetone but immiscible with dimethyl formamide

(DMF), however thymol and camphor were soluble in acetone, xylene and dimethyl formamide. All of them cleared that slightly acidic property, the acidity values as % H₂SO₄ were 0.049, 0.098 and 0.059 for diesel oil, thymol and camphor respectively.

Table (1):Physico-chemical properties of the active ingredients.

Compounds	Solubility % (W/V)				Free acidity as % H ₂ SO ₄
	Water	Xylene	Acetone	DMF	
Diesel oil	N.S	Miscible	Miscible	Immiscible	0.049
Thymol	N.S	142.85	100	125	0.098
Camphor oil	N.S	100	100	100	0.059

N.S = insoluble.

Data presented in Table (2) showed the physico- chemical properties for the suggested surfactants called Toximol R, Toximol H, Tween 80 and polyethylene glycol 600 di-oleate (PEG 600DO) were measured to determine if they were suitable to prepare the tested materials (Diesel oil and synthetic plant materials) as emulsifiable concentrates. According to HLB values, Toximol R, Toximol H, and polyethylene glycol 600 di-oleate were considered as emulsifying agent (emulsifiers) where its values were 10- 12, whereas tween 80 was greater than 13 it could be considered as dispersing or emulsifying agent. On

the other hand, these surfactants reduced the surface tension values compared with water, their values were 32, 36, 39.2 and 38.6 dyne/cm for Toximol R, Toximol H, Tween 80 and PEG 600DO respectively. All of them were acidic and the acidity values as % H₂SO₄ were: 0.49, 0.2, 0.5 and 0.88 respectively. PEG600DO had the highest CMC value followed by Tween 80, toximol H and Toximol R. the mentioned results showed clearly that, the tested surfactants were suitable to formulate diesel oil and synthetic plant materials (Thymol and camphor) as emulsifiable concentrates because it acts as emulsifiers.

Table (2): Physico- chemical properties of surface active agents.

Surface active agent	Surface tension at 0.5% (dyne/cm)	CMC %	HLB	Free acidity as % H ₂ SO ₄
Toximol- R	32	0.3	10-12	0.49
Toximol-H	36	0.3	10-12	0.2
Tween 80	39.2	0.5	>13	0.50
PEG 600 DO	38.6	0.9	10-12	0.88

PEG 600 DO: poly ethylene glycol 600 dioleate.

According to data presented in Table (3), the local prepared formulations (ECs) passed successfully from storage at 54 °C for three days where no observable

changes in emulsion stability and foam were before and after storage. On the other hand, there was a little increase in free acidity values with all prepared formulations.

Table (3): Physico-chemical properties of the locally prepared emulsifiable concentrates (ECs) before and after accelerated storage.

Compounds	Before storage					After storage				
	Emulsion stability (ml. cream. Sep.)		Foam (cm ³)		Free acidity as % H ₂ SO ₄	Emulsion stability (ml. cream. Sep.)		Foam (cm ³)		Free acidity as % H ₂ SO ₄
	H.W	S.W	H.W	S.W		H.W	S.W	H.W	S.W	
Diesel oil 90% EC	0	0	0	0	0.059	0	0	0	0	0.11
Diesel oil + thymol	1	0	0	0	0.186	2	1	0	0	0.24
Diesel oil + Camphor oil	0	0	1	0	0.166	0	0	2	1	0.22

H.W: Hard water (342 ppm as CaCO₃) S.W: Soft water (57 ppm)

As shown in Table (4) the properties of prepared emulsifiable concentrate at the field concentration (0.5%) were measured and the results obtained that, the spray solution possesses low values of surface tension and high values of viscosity compared with water values. Reducing in surface tension value of pesticide spray solution give an indication of rising spreading on the treated surface with a consequence increase in pesticide

efficacy (Ryckaert *et al.*, 2007). Increasing the viscosity of spray solution causes reducing drift, retention sticking and insecticidal efficacy (Spanoghe *et al.*, 2007). On the other hand, spray solution for all prepared formulations had the same percentage of salinity values as same as water these lower values increased the formulations biological activity, whereas all of them showed a little increase in the electrical conductivity values.

Table (4): Physico-chemical properties of spray solution of prepared emulsifiable concentrates (ECs) at field dilution rate (0.5 %).

Compounds	Viscosity (Centipoise)	Electrical conductivity (μ mhos)	% Salinity	Surface tension (Dyne/cm)
Diesel oil	2.0	436	0.2	44
Diesel oil + thymol	1.94	442	0.2	35.2
Diesel oil + camphor	1.94	439	0.2	39.5
Water	1.0	417	0.2	72.0

2. Bioassay part:

The efficacy of prepared ECs formulations against *S. sacchari*. The toxicity of diesel oil, diesel oil + thymol and diesel oil + camphor emulsifiable concentrate formulations (ECs) were measured by conducting a laboratory experiment using serial concentrations. The results in Table (5 and 6) indicated that diesel oil + thymol mixture was the most effective formulation against the

nymph and adults pink sugar cane mealybug, *S. sacchari* followed by diesel oil + camphor and diesel oil, it means that the formulated mixture of synthesized plant oils (thymol or camphor) with mineral oil (diesel oil) was more effective than the formulated diesel oil. However, the efficacy for all tested formulations was increased by increasing concentrations and the period after application.

Table(5):The insecticidal efficacy of formulated tested materials against pink sugar cane mealybug *Saccharicoccus sacchari*.

Material	Con. m/L	<i>Saccharicoccus sacchari</i>											
		1 st nymph			2 nd nymph			3 rd nymph			Adult		
		Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
Diesel oil 90% (EC)	1.25	19.6	26.8	46.3	16.4	24.8	45.4	15.8	24.4	43.4	14.6	21.9	41.2
	2.5	32.4	40.0	64.8	31.6	37.7	63.4	30.7	36.7	61.3	28.3	34.3	58.7
	5.0	35.2	54.6	80.3	34.2	52.2	78.8	34.1	50.6	77.1	32.9	48.6	74.7
	10.0	40.8	68.6	90.7	38.7	66.4	89.5	39.2	64.4	88.4	38.4	63.2	86.6
Diesel oil (65%) + thymol (10%)	1.25	50.7	81.7	97.9	49.4	80.6	97.9	47.2	78.6	96.9	41.4	72.95	91.1
	2.5	75.4	88.4	99.2	74.2	87.7	99.2	72.8	87.1	99.1	66.7	80.90	95.9
	5.0	84.6	93.3	99.7	83.1	92.7	99.7	81.7	92.9	99.8	74.3	87.23	98.3
	10.0	88.7	96.4	100	87.1	96.0	100	86.9	96.4	100	77.3	91.94	99.4
Diesel oil (70%) + camphor (10%)	1.25	35.8	57.8	96.1	34.4	55.4	93	32.4	52.8	91.0	30.3	50.2	84.9
	2.5	61.2	72.3	98.9	58.9	70.6	98.2	56.7	69.5	96.9	51.2	64.6	91.6
	5.0	70.4	83.7	99.8	69.4	82.8	99.7	67.3	82.9	99.2	63.6	77.2	95.8
	10.0	78.9	91.6	100	78.2	91.2	100	77.1	91.7	99.8	73.4	86.8	98.1

Table (6): LC₅₀, LC₉₀ and Slope values of ECs formulations against *Saccharicoccus sacchari*.

Material	Parameter	% Mortality of <i>Saccharicoccus sacchari</i>			
		Nymphs		Adults	
		48 hrs.	72 hrs.	48hrs.	72 hrs.
Diesel oil 90% (EC)	LC ₅₀	4.46	1.51	5.01	1.69
	LC ₉₀	51.60	10.40	55.44	12.32
	Slope	1.2077	1.5316	1.2012	1.4101
Diesel oil(65%) + thymol (10%)	LC ₅₀	0.20	0.05	0.24	0.12
	LC ₉₀	3.27	0.40	7.1	1.12
	Slope	1.0406	1.3879	0.8744	1.3214
Diesel oil (70%) + camphor (10%)	LC ₅₀	1.00	0.20	1.23	0.17
	LC ₉₀	8.58	0.95	13.25	2.01
	Slope	1.3721	1.8741	1.231	1.0623

On the other hand there was slight differences in efficacy among the different developmental insect stages, where the LC50 values of diesel oil + thymol for nymph and adults after two days were: 0.20 and 0.24 ml/L respectively, while they were: 0.05 and 0.12 ml/L after three days of application. While the LC50 values of diesel oil + camphor for nymphs and adults after two days were: 1 and 1.23 ml/L respectively but they were: 0.20 and 0.17 ml/L respectively after three days of application. Whereas the LC50 values of diesel oil for nymph and adults after two days were: 4.46 and 5.01 respectively but were: 1.51 and 1.69 ml/L respectively after three days of application. The insecticidal efficacy

of formulated tested materials against *S. sacchari* (Table 5).

Mineral oils block the insect air holes (spiracles) which insects breathe, causing them to die from asphyxiation. Also, the spread of oil through the respiratory pores and block the insect's trachea which leads to insect death. Oils may act as poisons, interacting with the fatty acid of insect and interfering with normal metabolism. Also, may disrupt how an insect feed. Dissolve the external waxy layer on the insect body causing dehydration (Helmy *et al.*, 2012 and Eskander *et al.*, 2020).

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to Dr. Magdi Adli Eskander (Pesticide Formulation Department, Central Agricultural Pesticides Laboratory (ARC). who

prepared the materials , Diesel oil (EC) , Diesel oil + thymol (EC) 3_ Diesel oil +Camphor as emulsifiable concentrates.

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Evans and Abd-Rabou (2005): Two new species and additional records of Egyptian Aphelinidae. Zootaxa, 833:1-7.

Simmons, A. and Abd-Rabou, S. (2006): Whitefly populations in vegetables crops with different fertilizers. 52nd Annual meeting of the South Carolina Entomological Society, Mc Cormick, Sc., October 19-20.

Abd-Rabou, S. and Simmons, A. M. (2012): *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) whitefly as a pest in Egypt. Advances In Agricultural Research In Egypt, 10 (1): 1-82.

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